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Deliverable D1.1: **Report on security crises with high societal impact**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Mapping European crises

- Chapter 2 involved a mapping exercise which sought to understand what types of crises affected the security of citizens in European Member States over the last 10 years (2003 to 2013).
- There are four types of crises that were “typical” to Europe, in that they occurred most often: flood, extreme temperature, storm and wildfire.
- Partners identified six types of crises that European Member States have been exposed to that have resulted in a high physical and high societal impact: flood, extreme temperature, storm, wildfire, earthquake and man-made disasters.

Group impacts

- Partners assessed the impact of six types of crises on groups in society. In all six case studies citizens, critical infrastructure and the government were affected in the immediate aftermath of the crisis.
 - Similarities and differences in “who” within these broad groups were affected has been found across the different types of crises (e.g., communication was impacted by the man-made crisis, but not others).
- In five out of the six crises (Flood, extreme temperature, wildfire, earthquake and man-made disaster) there was evidence to suggest that different types of industry had also been affected.
- Results suggested that when one group is affected this can cause another group to also be affected (e.g., the impact of damage to critical infrastructure can impact citizens and the functioning of industry).
- Findings suggest that the extent of the impact of a crisis on different groups is highly dependent on the scale of the crisis.

The security of the citizen

- Crises affect the security of the citizen in a multitude of ways, including: the physical and mental well-being, the destruction of communities and supporting critical infrastructure, the loss of personal property, the loss of life and historically, in extreme cases, the destruction of entire civilisations. As COSMIC concerns social media during crises, citizens are the potential users of such media; their behaviour is largely determined by the crisis itself and its evolution. This, in turn, is dependent on the response by organised forms of society charged with mitigating the effects.
- Partners found that in order to mitigate the threat to citizens’ security, crises require monitoring, prediction, preparation, intervention plans and dedicated organisations.

- Dedicated organisations are found at the Member States in the form of security forces, purpose-led emergency services and rescue agencies, medical teams, fire fighting bodies and others. At EU level the partners found that organisations such as the Community Mechanism for Civil Protection and the GMES Emergency Response Service offer cross-border assistance where it is needed, in response to calls by individual states both from the EU and elsewhere. At an even higher level, the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) has an extensive track record of intervention in distress situations all over the world. These efforts are supplemented by a variety of Civil Society (Non-Governmental) Organisations, which, thanks to their flexibility, can offer substantial support to communities in need.
- There are several emerging frameworks manifested as regulations, guidelines and warning systems that are being introduced at the European level to help build resilience within European communities regarding future crises. COSMIC, as an advocate of an emerging crisis management method (social media) has to be aware of such frameworks, therefore their examination in this document. A notable example is the Commission's expressed intention of drafting guidelines (in the form of good practice) to adequately prepare for disasters. These will align with the United Nations' Hyogo Framework for Action for building the resilience of nations and communities to such phenomena.
- From the policy point of view in Europe, partners found that policy measures for disasters, such as heat waves, floods and storms, tend to be viewed within the framework of climate change. A recent example is the European Commission's announcement in April 2013 of its strategy to strengthen Europe's preparedness towards different types of disasters. This is embedded in the framework of adaptation measures to tackle climate change.

Societal dynamics

- The partners have identified some striking similarities between the individual, organisational and societal dynamics in crisis situations.
- Citizens have a strong desire to help those who suffer. Individually, citizens are rarely passive and often exhibit pro-social behaviour during crisis situations. This behaviour is reflected (most of the time) in both organisations and communities and is indicative of the level of work people are willing to do, especially when new technologies (such as those of COSMIC) are to be introduced.
- Societal dynamics is largely dependent on the time it takes for a crisis situation to develop and on the magnitude of this crisis, but not on the type of crisis. Consequently, for individual, organisational and societal dynamics it makes no real difference whether society is confronted by, for example, a flood or a storm. Although, certain crisis types such as earthquakes often occur without a warning period and their dynamics is similar to the so-called flash crises, this conclusion provides valuable insights for the (possible) use of new technologies such as those of COSMIC.
- The role of government in the immediate aftermath of a crisis is often limited. Emergency management agencies are either not present or otherwise occupied with a limited number of citizens, or even unable to mount an effective response. It is the aspiration of COSMIC to show that this gap can be filled to some extent by citizens deploying new technologies, for the benefit of the whole society under duress.

Chapter 1: Introduction

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Understanding the contribution of social media to crisis management requires a preliminary investigation of the typical crises that European Member States are exposed to. This report will contribute to the consortium's efforts in understanding how different types of crises affect the security of the citizen. This report consists of fundamental preparatory work to enable COSMIC to be able to fulfil its objective of exploring how new and emerging communication technologies and applications can be most effectively utilised to promote the safety and security of citizens in crisis situations.

Furthermore, this report contributes to COSMIC's aim of determining the relevant criteria required to define, characterise and categorise different types of crises. It is important to conduct this examination as it is essential that COSMIC assesses the use of information communication technologies by those managing and responding to a crisis that Europeans have been affected by, rather than those that Europe has little experience of. This knowledge will provide an essential backdrop for supporting subsequent work efforts in COSMIC to ensure that its focus on understanding the contribution of new and emerging communication technologies is maintained (for instance in WP2 where we select case studies to examine the use of new media in crisis situations) in context to those types of crises that matter to Europe.

Accordingly, in this first supporting task, partners will define and characterise typical crisis situations, which will go some way in assisting the consortium with meeting its objective of developing a typology of crisis situations involving the security of citizens. Once these typical crisis situations have been mapped, partners will re-examine them, to determine which types of "typical" crisis situations have a high social impact in relation to the role of groups within society and society as a whole to determine how the security of the citizen is guaranteed. In order to complete this we must first understand key terms associated with this investigation, including; what we mean by the term "crises", how we define "physical impact", "societal impact" and lastly, what we mean by the phrase "security of the citizen".

1.1. KEY TERMS

This report contains several concepts that are in need of further clarification to ease the readers understanding and to ensure that partners are following a unified approach to the analysis involved in this task and the subsequent work packages. Accordingly, within this section the terms "crises", "physical impact", "high and low societal impact" and "security of the citizen" will be outlined.

1.1.1. Crises

Typically, the term "crisis" has been defined by the Oxford English Dictionary as "a time of severe difficulty or danger".¹ When discussing the term "crisis" in relation to ensuring citizens' security, it is commonly attributed and discussed interchangeably with the term "disaster", as seen for instance, in the 2010 "EU Internal Security Strategy in Action: Five steps towards a more secure Europe".² Within this report, as operationalised elsewhere, the term "crisis" will also be associated with the term "disaster". In addition, COSMIC is also interested in crises will associated with political disruption that affect the security of the citizen as experienced in Greece, Spain and Turkey.

¹ Soanes, Catherine, ed., *Paperback Oxford English Dictionary*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2002, p. 193.

² European Commission, *The EU Internal Security Strategy in Action: Five Steps Towards a More Secure Europe*, COM(2010) 673 final, Brussels, 22.11.201.

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2010:0673:FIN:EN:PDF#page=2>.

Although, as often found when defining terms, there is no “agreed upon” definition of the term “disaster”, there has been, as outlined by Perry, some consensus.³ A disaster is a “social phenomena”; a storm for instance, is not a disaster, it is the social effects of the storm on the social system that causes it to be classified and understood as a disaster. For instance an event might be classified as a disaster according to the number of systems damaged, citizens injured or displaced.⁴ Importantly, a disaster is also a reflection of the “social structure and reflects the process of social change”, in that as society evolves so too does the ways in which society is vulnerable to different types of disaster. This is reflected in the United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (UNISDR) who define a disaster as; “A serious disruption of the functioning of a community or a society involving widespread human, material, economic or environmental losses and impacts, which exceeds the ability of the affected community or society to cope using its own resources.”⁵

Within this report, as will be seen in chapter two, a central component of this work is to map European crises. For this endeavour, partners will utilise a well-recognised global database, OFDA/CRED International Disaster Database (EM-DAT).⁶ It is therefore worth noting that EM-DAT defines a disaster as:

Situation or event, which overwhelms local capacity, necessitating a request to national or international level for external assistance (definition considered in EM-DAT); An unforeseen and often sudden event that causes great damage, destruction and human suffering. Though often caused by nature, disasters can have human origins.⁷

In its criteria of what constitutes a “disaster”, EM-DAT use the following guidelines: Ten or more people reported killed, a hundred or more people reported affected, a declaration of a state of emergency or a call for international assistance.⁸ Within this definition, as with the definition posed by UNISDR emphasis is placed on the need of an area to need external help as a result of damage, destruction and human suffering and therefore both are associate the term disaster with its effect on society. Importantly, a crisis can be a result of a natural event, or a result of human activities, otherwise referred to in this report as a man-made disaster (e.g., an industrial accident or an intentional act of terrorism). As understood by Coleman, man-made disasters are by no means rare events, but are events that have grown immensely; “...largely due to an increase in traditional hazards such as fires and explosions, rather than from new technologies. Although the number of incidents has grown, this has been offset by a decline in fatalities per incident”.⁹

Accordingly, in addition to utilising the EM-DAT database, partners will also be seeking to understand the frequency (through the use of the Global Terrorism Database (GTD)¹⁰) with

³ Perry, Ronald W., “What Is a Disaster?”, in Havidan Rodriguez, Enrico L. Quarantelli, and Russell R. Dynes (eds.), *Handbook of Disaster Research*, Springer, New York, 2007, pp. 1–15.

⁴ Ibid., p. 12.

⁵ UNISDR, *2009 UNISDR Terminology on Disaster Risk*, UNISDR, Geneva, Switzerland, 2009.

⁶ EM-DAT: *The OFDA/CRED International Disaster Database*, Université catholique de Louvain, Brussels, Belgium, 2013. www.emdat.be.

⁷ EM-DAT, *Glossary*, Université catholique de Louvain, Brussels, Belgium, 2013. <http://www.emdat.be/glossary/9#letterd>

⁸ EM-DAT, *Criteria and Definition*, Université catholique de Louvain, Brussels, Belgium, 2013. <http://www.emdat.be/criteria-and-definition>

⁹ Coleman, Les, “Frequency of Man-Made Disasters in the 20th Century”, *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, Vol. 14, No. 1, 2006, pp. 3–11.

¹⁰ National Consortium for the Study of Terrorism and Responses to Terrorism (START), *Global Terrorism Database [Data file]*, 2012. <http://www.start.umd.edu/gtd>

which European Member States are exposed to deliberate man-made crises in the form of acts of terrorism.¹¹ It is thus important to understand how the term “terrorism” is defined.

Although a contested term¹², the term terrorism, as understood by the GTD in their recording of incidents, refers to: “intentional act of violence or threat of violence by a non-state actor”.¹³ In their recording of events, the incident would also have to meet two of the three criteria:¹⁴

- The violent act was aimed at attaining a political, economic, religious, or social goal;
- The violent act included evidence of an intention to coerce, intimidate, or convey some other message to a larger audience (or audiences) other than the immediate victims; and
- The violent act was outside the precepts of International Humanitarian Law.

Accordingly, within this report, partners will use a comprehensive approach to understanding and identifying different types of crises that Europe has been exposed to in the past. This will enable partners to understand (in future work packages), how to optimise the use of social media to respond to a crisis.

1.1.2. Physical impact

As identified by Lindell and Prater the physical impact of a natural disaster includes the number of casualties (deaths and injuries), property damage and loss of structures.¹⁵ Physical impact can also be linked to environmental factors such as damage to cropland or woodlands.¹⁶ The physical impact of a crisis can be difficult to measure, particularly with regard to casualty estimates and damage. For instance, following some events, such as a Tsunami, it can be difficult to determine the precise number of casualties due to some individuals missing as a result of the nature of the crisis.

Within the present report, as will be seen in Chapter 2, the physical impact of a crisis will be measured according to the number of individuals killed by a crisis, as well as the number of people affected by a crisis. In this sense, the term “affected” is associated with those that required immediate assistance to meet their basic survival needs, including; food, water, shelter, sanitation and immediate medical assistance.¹⁷

It is important to note that the physical impact of a crisis differs depending on the scale of the crisis, as well as the vulnerabilities of the affected community, and thus the societal impact of a disaster is an important consideration for attempting to determine the extent of the damage caused by a crisis.

1.1.3. Societal impact

Understanding the social impact of a crisis is fundamental to understanding the wider impact of a crisis on society, and thus what ultimately makes the situation a crisis. This will be

¹¹ An additional database is required for the endeavour as acts of “terror” are not included in the EM-DAT database.

¹² Frank Furedi, *Invitation to Terror: The Expanding Empire of the Unknown*, London, Continuum Books, 2007.

¹³ It is worth noting that some countries, for example the USA, also define terrorism in relation to acts committed by the state. <http://www.state.gov/j/ct/list/c14151.htm>

¹⁴ National Consortium for the Study of Terrorism and Responses to Terrorism (START), “Data collection and definition of terrorism”, 2012. <http://www.start.umd.edu/gtd/using-gtd/>

¹⁵ Lindell, M., and C. Prater, “Assessing Community Impacts of Natural Disasters”, *Natural Hazards Review*, Vol. 4, No. 4, 2003, pp. 176–185.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 7.

¹⁷ EM-DAT, *Glossary*, Université catholique de Louvain, Brussels, Belgium, 2013. <http://www.emdat.be/glossary/>

further explored in Chapter 3 where partners will examine the various groups that are affected by different types of crises, and crucially, how they are impacted.

Physical and social impacts share a close relationship, for physical impacts cause social impacts and are essentially linked to the vulnerability of society, as well as the resilience of a society and their capacity to respond to a crisis. Lindell and Prater categorise social impacts in relation to; psychosocial, sociodemographic, socioeconomic and sociopolitical impacts – all of which can have both short and long term impacts. The following table provides further elaboration on the differences between these types of social impacts:

Table 1: Social impact¹⁸

Social impact	Explanation & example
Psychosocial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fatigue, gastrointestinal upset, ○ Cognitive effects (e.g., confusion, attention deficit) ○ Emotional effects (e.g., anxiety, depression and grief), post-traumatic stress disorder ○ Behavioural effects (e.g., sleep and appetite changes, ritualistic behaviour, substance abuse). ○ Need for mental health treatment ○ Changes in risk perception ○ Increased hazard intrusiveness
Sociodemographic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Destruction of household dwelling ○ Socio-economic status can cause a crisis to have a higher social impact
Socioeconomic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Economic loss (e.g., through damage to property) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Impact on businesses ○ Impact on citizens ○ Impact of economic loss on local government ○ Need for replacement of assets (e.g., food and clothing) ○ Need for financial recovery assistance (e.g., unemployment benefits, loans)
Sociopolitical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Social activism ○ Conflict (e.g., within the community) ○ Decrease in quality of life ○ Change to civil governance

Elsewhere, partners in the MICRODIS project have identified other factors that can result in sociodemographic impacts, including: class, race, gender, age, literacy and marital status.¹⁹ Accordingly when considering the social impact of different types of crises in subsequent chapters, there are many factors to take into consideration.

1.1.4. Security of the citizen

The “security of the citizen” implies that a crisis has the ability to destabilise citizens’ daily routines which is largely a result of the combined impact of both the physical and social impacts of a crisis. For instance, following a crisis, a citizen could be emotionally or physically harmed and thus the “security” of that citizen may have been affected. Within this report, the concept ensuring the “security of the citizen” involves partners assessing how different types of crises affect the security of the citizen, and furthermore the various roles of different groups within society in ensuring that citizens are less vulnerable to a crisis. Implicit

¹⁸ Ibid., pp. 178-181.

¹⁹ MICRODIS project, “Preliminary conceptual model of social components that describe extreme event impact”, Deliverable 1.2.3 of the MICRODIS project, no date.
<http://www.microdis-eu.be/sites/default/files/D1.2.3%20-%20Preliminary%20conceptual%20model%20of%20social%20components%20that%20describe%20extreme%20event%20impact.doc.pdf>

in this examination of guaranteeing security, is the need to assess societal dynamics to determine how different segments of society are required to respond to a crisis.

Thus, in order for this report to succeed in accomplishing its goal of mapping security crises, it is necessary for partners to identify typical crises that European Member States have been exposed to, their impacts on society and how different groups within society must respond in order to ensure the security of European citizens.

1.2. STRUCTURE OF THE REPORT

In total, this report contains six chapters and will proceed in the following manner: Chapter two of this report “Mapping European Crises” is pivotal for subsequent chapters. In this chapter, partners will present the findings of a quantitative study of mapping European crises. Partners will use the EM-DAT database to identify what crises European Member States have been exposed to in the last 10 years (2003 to 2013). In addition, partners will access the GTD to identify what types of terrorist incidents European Member States have been exposed to between 2003 and 2011.²⁰ Findings from this chapter will be used in subsequent chapters to further analyse the impact of “typical” crises on the security of the citizen in chapters three, four and five.

In chapter three of this report “Crises and group impacts”, partners will use the findings from chapter two to identify “who” in society (e.g., governments, citizens, business etc.) is impacted by different types of crises by using case studies of typical crises for its analysis. Furthermore, the chapter will outline how these different groups are impacted by different types of crises.

Chapter four of this report “Crises and the security of citizens” will utilise the findings of chapter two, particularly crises that are categorised as being “typical” to identify how “typical” crises affect the security of the citizen. Partners will do so by focusing on six “typical” crises, and will illustrate, with the use of examples, their findings. Furthermore, in the second part of this chapter, partners will examine how groups in society (e.g., policy makers, authorities, humanitarian organisations etc.) guarantee citizens security at the level of field relief and rescue operations and at the level of policy and legislation.

Chapter five of this report “crises and societal dynamics” will outline how different groups appear to organise themselves to respond to crises and furthermore, what impact crises have on the organisation of groups. Chapter five will be split into three sections so as to conduct this analysis in relation to individual, organisation and society dynamics.

This report will conclude in chapter six, where partners will provide a summary of key findings from the previous chapters.

²⁰ The timing is different here as a result of the database only currently storing data up to 2011.

Chapter 2: Mapping European Crises

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2 MAPPING EUROPEAN CRISES

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Different types of crises occur throughout the world. Since the beginning of 2013 there have been numerous instances of widely publicised crises ranging from natural disasters including floods, tornadoes and storms, to those crises which are directly linked to human activities, including; the collapsing of buildings, acts of terrorism, mass protests and chemical explosions. In order to understand what types of crises affect the security of citizens in Europe, and therefore what contribution new and emerging information communication technologies can make to managing and responding to crises, it is necessary for COSMIC to understand what types of crises European Member states have been exposed to.

Accordingly, this chapter presents findings of a mapping task that sought to understand what types of crises European Member States have been exposed to in the last 10 years. The chapter will first describe the methodology used for this task. It will then outline the types of crises experienced in European Member States, thereby enabling partners to identify "typical" (reoccurring) crises. The chapter will then proceed to outline types of crises that have had a low and high impact, and will lastly, identify crises that were cross-border in nature. This chapter will conclude by identifying the types of crises that will serve as the foundation for subsequent analyses in the remaining chapters of this report.

2.1. METHODOLOGY

This mapping sub-task of Task 1.1 in COSMIC involved partners collating data relating to recorded crises that European Member States have encountered in the last ten years. Within this sub-section, partners will discuss the process of data collection used for this analysis as well as any known limitations with the data.

2.1.1. Data Collection

In order to map crises that European Member States have been exposed to, this sub-task involved the use of two crisis related databases: OFDA/CRED International Disaster Database (EM-DAT)²¹ and the Global Terrorism Database (GTD).²² Both databases are well known and respected within the field of crisis research. EM-DAT has a longstanding partnership with several International organisations including (for instance); the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC), Secretariat for the International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (UNISDR), U.S. Agency for International Development (USAID), Asian Disaster Reduction Center (ADRC), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the World Bank (World Bank).²³ The GTD is also celebrated and is commonly used by researchers and academics alike (see for instance; Henderson²⁴, and

²¹ EM-DAT: *The OFDA/CRED International Disaster Database*, Université catholique de Louvain, Brussels, Belgium, 2013. www.emdat.be.

²² National Consortium for the Study of Terrorism and Responses to Terrorism (START), *Global Terrorism Database [Data file]*, 2012. <http://www.start.umd.edu/gtd>

²³ EM-DAT, "Collaborations & Partnerships", Université catholique de Louvain, Brussels, Belgium, 2013. <http://www.emdat.be/collaborations-partnerships>

²⁴ Henderson, Harry, *Global Terrorism: The Complete Reference Guide*. Jaico Publishing House, 2005.

Dolnik²⁵). In both instances, due to their open data policies, both EM-DAT and the GTD provide a rich resource enabling partners to conduct this mapping exercise.²⁶ The data within EM-DAT is compiled by means of accessing a variety of sources, examples include: UN agencies, non-governmental organisations, insurance companies, research institutes and press agencies.²⁷

Elsewhere, the GTD understands terrorism to be an: “intentional act of violence or threat of violence by a non-state actor”. In their recording of events, as with the use of strict criteria by those responsible for the EM-DAT database, for GTD, the incident would also have to meet two of the three criteria.²⁸

- The violent act was aimed at attaining a political, economic, religious, or social goal;
- The violent act included evidence of an intention to coerce, intimidate, or convey some other message to a larger audience (or audiences) other than the immediate victims; and
- The violent act was outside the precepts of International Humanitarian Law.

As with EM-DAT, the GTD is compiled and further verified using a range of sources, examples include: electronic news archives, existing data sets, secondary source materials such as books and journals and legal documents.²⁹ Within the present report, the following criteria was used for the inclusion of data in the mapping of crises experienced by European Member States:

Table 2: Criteria for use of data in COSMIC Task 1.1

EM-DAT search 09/05/2013	Criteria
Country	Current EU Member States ³⁰
Years	2003-2013
Disaster types ³¹	Complex Disasters; Drought; Earthquake (seismic activity); Epidemic; Extreme temperature; Flood; Industrial Accident; Insect infestation; Mass movement dry; Mass movement wet; Miscellaneous accident; Storm; Transport Accident; Volcano; Wildfire;
Number of results	491
GTD search 09/05/2013	Criteria
Countries	Current EU Member States
Years	2003 – 2011 ³²
Number of results	693

It is important to note that the data used for this initial mapping exercise in COSMIC is restricted to those events included within the databases used within the analysis. The inclusion

²⁵ Dolnik, Adam, “Die and Let Die: Exploring Links Between Suicide Terrorism and Terrorist Use of Chemical, Biological, Radiological, and Nuclear Weapons.” *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, Vol 26, No. 1, 2003, pp. 17–35.

²⁶ EM-DAT’s criteria of what constitutes a “disaster” has been referred to in Chapter 1; Section 1.1.1.

²⁷ EM-DAT, *Frequently asked questions*, Université catholique de Louvain, Brussels, Belgium, 2013. <http://www.emdat.be/frequently-asked-questions>

²⁸ National Consortium for the Study of Terrorism and Responses to Terrorism (START), *Data collection and definition of terrorism*, 2012. <http://www.start.umd.edu/gtd/using-gtd/>

²⁹ National Consortium for the Study of Terrorism and Responses to Terrorism (START), *Data collection methodology*, 2012. <http://www.start.umd.edu/gtd/using-gtd/>

³⁰ As of 9th May 2013.

³¹ Note: This selection of “disaster types” includes all of those “types” available under the search criteria.

³² Note: For the GTD search, data was only available up until 2011.

of events is therefore limited to those classified as such by the two sources respectively. Within the data collected, both EM-DAT and GTD, contain some missing values (due to information being unavailable) which are either left blank within the database or labelled as “unknown”. These missing values thus cause a weakness in the data collected and used for this analysis – particularly with regard to the “impact” of the crisis.

2.2. CRISES EXPERIENCED BY EUROPEAN MEMBER STATES

As identified by EM-DAT, between 2003 and 2013 24 European Member States have experienced at least two disasters. Some European Member States have experienced more crises than others, for instance Italy (51 crises), Romania (45 crises), Austria and France (44 crises each) and Germany (42 crises) have experienced a greater number of crises than those residing in Cyprus and Latvia (5 crises each), Denmark, Estonia and Ireland (4 crises each), Sweden (3 crises), Finland and Luxembourg (2 crises each). Further information can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 1: Number of disasters in European Member States 2003-2013

Types of crises that European Member States experienced included 11 different types:

1. Flood
2. Extreme temperature
3. Storm
4. Transport accident
5. Wildfire
6. Miscellaneous accident
7. Earthquake (seismic activity)
8. Industrial accident
9. Epidemic
10. Drought
11. Mass movement wet³³

³³ A mass movement concerns the downslope movement of sediment, soil, and rock material. In relation to a (wet) mass movement, a hydrological hazard, this can be in the form of: subsidences, rockfalls, avalanches and landslides. (International federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, “Hydrological hazards”, 2013. <http://www.ifrc.org/en/what-we-do/disaster-management/about-disasters/definition-of-hazard/mass-movement-wet/>)

Further information relating to the number of disasters (by type) experienced by European Member States can be found in the figure below.

Figure 2: Number of disasters in European Member States by type 2003-2013

More typical crises included floods (132 occurrences), extreme temperatures (106 occurrences), storms (93 incidences), transport accidents (87 occurrences) and wildfires (20 occurrences). Less typical crises included earthquakes (12 occurrences), epidemics (7 occurrences), drought (4 occurrences) and mass movement (wet) (2 occurrences). Through the use of the database, partners were also able to identify a number of types of crises that occurred infrequently in European Member States as there was no evidence to suggest that any significant harm was caused or that any outside help was required, types included; complex disasters (those events that have multiple causes e.g., drought, famine), insect infestations, mass movement (dry) and volcanic eruptions.

In addition to understanding typical crises between 2003 and 2013, partners have also been able to identify the various types of crises and how they have changed in occurrence over time (between 2003 and 2012). As can be seen in the following figure, there are those types of crises, including extreme temperature, floods, miscellaneous accidents, storms and transport accidents which have occurred on an annual basis. When considering the frequency of these reoccurring crises over time, there is evidence of irregularity between the numbers of occurrences each year, with no discernable pattern of increase or decrease in the number of crises defined as such by EM-DAT. Alternatively, there are those crises such as drought, industrial accidents, mass movement wet and wildfires that do not occur every year; these too appear to be irregular in their patterns over time.

Figure 3: Mapping crises in European Member States over time

When considering the sub-type of the crises experience by European Member States, partners found higher occurrences related to: general floods (113 occurrences), cold wave (56 occurrences), water related transport accidents (36 occurrences), heat waves (32 occurrences) and local storms (31 occurrences). Less typical crises included: gas leaks (1 instance), landslides (2 instances) and chemical spills (2 instances).

Figure 4: Number of disasters in European Member States by sub-type 2003-2013

In addition to some man-made crises, including water, road, rail and air related incidents, collapses and chemical spills, there are also those forms of man-made crises that are deliberate; acts of terrorism. As identified in the figure below, the results from the GTD search revealed that European Member States have also experienced incidences of “terrorism”. Those in Greece (291 incidents), Spain (171 incidents) and Italy (47 incidents) were more likely to experience higher numbers of incidents than those in Denmark and Hungary (3 incidents each), Cyprus, Finland and Portugal (2 incidents each), Estonia, Latvia and Romania (1 incident each). Those in Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Poland, Slovak

Republic and Slovenia did not experience any incidences of “terrorism” between 2003 and 2011.

Figure 5: Number of terror related incidents in EU Member States

Crucially, whilst there were over 600 terror incidents recorded, not all incidences resulted in the loss of life or injuries. Of those terror related incidences that were recorded, attacks that resulted in a physical impact, with over 10 injures or any fatalities included attacks that took place in: Belgium, Italy, Spain, France, Great Britain, Greece, Finland, Czech Republic and the Netherlands. Further information about these attacks can be seen in the table below:

Table 3: Terror incidences with a physical "human" impact

Date	Country	# of fatalities	# of injuries	Perpetrator	Type of attack
04/06/2003	Belgium	0	20	Unknown	Unarmed assault
19/11/2003	Italy	0	50	Unknown	Unarmed assault
11/03/2004	Spain	73	450	Abu Hafs al-Masri Brigades	Bombing/explosion
11/03/2004	Spain	62	450	Abu Hafs al-Masri Brigades	Bombing/explosion
11/03/2004	Spain	37	450	Abu Hafs al-Masri Brigades	Bombing/explosion
11/03/2004	Spain	19	450	Abu Hafs al-Masri Brigades	Bombing/explosion
08/10/2004	France	0	10	French Armed Islamic Front	Facility/Infrastructure Attack
09/02/2005	Spain	0	43	Basque Fatherland and Freedom (ETA)	Bombing/explosion
25/05/2005	Spain	0	34	Basque Fatherland and Freedom (ETA)	Bombing/explosion
07/07/2005	Great Britain	27	340	Secret Organisation of al-Qaâida in Europe	Bombing/explosion
07/07/2005	Great Britain	8	171	Secret Organisation of al-Qaâida in	Bombing/explosion

				Europe	
07/07/2005	Great Britain	7	163	Secret Organisation of al-Qaâida in Europe	Bombing/explosion
07/07/2005	Great Britain	14	110	Secret Organisation of al-Qaâida in Europe	Bombing/explosion
30/12/2006	Spain	2	12	Basque Fatherland and Freedom (ETA)	Bombing/explosion
28/08/2007	Greece	63	Unknown	Unknown	Facility/Infrastructure Attack
07/11/2007	Finland	9	Unknown	Individual	Facility/Infrastructure Attack
28/06/2008	Czech Republic	0	20	Unknown	Bombing/explosion
21/09/2008	Spain	0	11	Basque Fatherland and Freedom (ETA)	Bombing/explosion
21/09/2008	Spain	0	10	Basque Fatherland and Freedom (ETA)	Bombing/explosion
30/10/2008	Spain	0	17	Basque Fatherland and Freedom (ETA)	Basque Fatherland and Freedom (ETA)
20/03/2009	France	0	10	Unknown	Armed assault
01/05/2009	Netherlands	7	12	Unknown	Assassination
29/07/2009	Spain	0	46	Basque Fatherland and Freedom (ETA)	Bombing/explosion

Thus, in relation to terrorism, between 2003 and 2011, 16 instances of acts of terror can be identified in European Member States. Accordingly, partners have found that in contrast to other types of crises, terrorism is not “typical”, in that there are other types of crises that are more common. However, that is not to say (as will be seen in Section 2.4) that terrorism is not a high impact crises worthy of further attention.

2.3. HIGH IMPACT CRISES

In order to identify types of crises that are considered to be of a “high impact”, partners have identified crises with a substantial physical impact³⁴; over 2000 citizens affected (in this sense “affected” includes those that required immediate assistance to meet their basic survival

³⁴ Following a lack of literature on what constitutes a “high impact” crisis, within this report, high impact boundaries were identified by partners based on an overview of the EM-DAT data surrounding European exposure to crises and the average number of fatalities, number of individuals affected and the economic impact of the crisis.

needs, including; food, water, shelter, sanitation and immediate medical assistance³⁵). In addition, crises with a high impact also contain a high economic cost, which goes some way to suggesting that the crises would have had a socio-economic impact (as determined by Lindell and Prater’s definition of social impact in Chapter 1); costing over \$150 million.

Accordingly, the analysis of crises using the EM-DAT database has revealed, that of those types of crises that have occurred in the last 10 years, there are five types of crises that have resulted in a high physical impact, and six crises with a high economic cost. The figure below summarises the number of times each of the following crises resulted in a “high physical impact”: flood, earthquake (seismic activity), storm, wildfire, industrial accident and extreme temperature.

Figure 6: Types of crises with a "high physical impact"

More specifically, the following table summarises the economic impact of and the size of the population affected by the top 10 crises with a “high physical impact” that occurred in European Member States between 2003 and 2013:

Table 4: Top 10 crises resulting in a high physical impact³⁶

Start	End	Country	Type	Killed	Tot. Affected	Est. Damage (US\$ Million)
28/02/2010	02/03/2010	France	Storm	53	500079	4230
20/07/2007	24/07/2007	United Kingdom	Flood	7	340000	4000
00/01/2003	00/09/2003	Portugal	Wildfire	14	150000	1730
17/05/2010	26/05/2010	Poland	Flood	16	100000	3080
06/04/2009	06/04/2009	Italy	Earthquake (seismic	295	56000	2500

³⁵ EM-DAT, *Glossary*, 2013.

³⁶ Please note, a “dash” in the table indicates a missing value. As this data was not able to be recorded by EM-DAT.

			activity)			
01/02/2012	06/02/2012	Bulgaria	Flood	5	37950	4.4
28/03/2006	09/05/2006	Hungary	Flood	-	32000	-
21/09/2005	23/09/2005	Romania	Flood	10	30800	-
25/06/2007	03/07/2007	United Kingdom	Flood	6	30000	4000
02/12/2003	03/12/2003	France	Flood	9	27000	1500

Whereas Figure 6 and Table 4 summarise the details of crises with high physical impacts, the following figure provides further information as to what types of crises have been found to have resulted in a high socio-economic impact (costing more than \$150 million): flood, storm, extreme temperature, wildfire, earthquake (seismic activity) and drought.

Figure 7: Types of crises with a "high social impact"

In addition, the following table provides further information relating to the top 10 crises between 2003 and 2013 with a high economic cost:

Table 5: Top 10 crises resulting in a high socio-economic impact

Start	End	Country	Type	Killed	Tot. Affected	Est. Damage (US\$ Million)
20/05/2012	20/05/2012	Italy	Earthquake (seismic activity)	7	11050	15800
18/01/2007	18/01/2007	Germany	Storm	11	130	5500
01/08/2003	20/08/2003	France	Extreme temperature	19490	-	4400
16/07/2003	15/08/2003	Italy	Extreme temperature	20089	-	4400
28/02/2010	02/03/2010	France	Storm	53	500079	4230
20/07/2007	24/07/2007	United Kingdom	Flood	7	340000	4000
25/06/2007	03/07/2007	United Kingdom	Flood	6	30000	4000
23/01/2009	26/01/2009	France	Storm	11	-	3200
17/05/2010	26/05/2010	Poland	Flood	16	100000	3080
07/01/2005	09/01/2005	Sweden	Storm	7	-	2800

Of those countries included in the table above, several have experienced multiple instances of crises with substantial social costs; France (x3), Italy (x2) and the United Kingdom (x2).

Notably, there are two incidents, in the form of “industrial accidents” resulting in a high impact. The first in 2004, an explosion at a fireworks factory in Denmark, resulted in 2072 people being affected and one person being killed. The second incident in 2010, a toxic spill in Hungary, resulted in 7270 people being affected, nine people killed and costs of up to \$103 million.

In addition to the types of crises identified above, the consortium has chosen to include acts of terror, a deliberate man-made disaster, within its assessment of crises experienced by European Member States. As seen by the GTD database, some European Member States have experienced vast numbers of terror related incidents in the last ten years, some of which has resulted in a substantial physical impact. Although not easy to identify, the cost of an act of terrorism has in some instances been substantial. For instance, the 2004 attacks in Madrid on the transportation network was identified by Buesa et al. as costing approximately € 2,176,875 (these costs relate to the valuation of the costs of the services of rescue and first aid attention for the victims of the attacks of 3/11).³⁷ Accordingly, terrorism is regarded within COSMIC as a “high impact” crisis as a result of its high physical impact, and in some situations, high costs and thus requires further attention within the COSMIC project, particularly with regard to the wider social impact of terrorism (as will be discussed in Chapter 3 and 4 of this report).

This initial identification of types of crises with a high impact, will assist the consortium in further understanding the wider societal impact of crises as experienced by European Member States, as will be discussed in Chapter 3 and 4 where it will be possible to see who was impacted by different types of crises, and importantly, how they were impacted (e.g., through damage to property, damage to business, health related problems etc.).

2.4. LOW IMPACT CRISES

As with our identification of types of crises with a high impact, the assessment of crises within this chapter is also interested in identifying crises that have had a low impact. In this sense, a crisis with a low impact is likely to have affected less than 2000 individuals, and to have cost less than \$150 million.³⁸ Accordingly, the following figure summarises the number of times crises with low physical impact were experienced between 2003 and 2013:

³⁷ Buesa, Mikel, Aurelia Valiño, Joost Heijs, Thomas Baumert, and Javier González Gómez., “The Economic Cost of March 11: Measuring the Direct Economic Cost of the Terrorist Attack on March 11, 2004 in Madrid.” *Terrorism and Political Violence*, Vol. 19, No. 4, 2007, pp. 489–509.

³⁸ As with the problem of classifying what a “high impact” crisis is considered to be, there was also a lack of literature on what constitutes a “low impact” crisis. Accordingly, within this report, low impact boundaries were identified by partners based on an overview of the EM-DAT data surrounding European exposure to crises and the average number of fatalities, number of individuals affected and the economic impact of the crisis.

Figure 8: Types of crises with a "low physical impact"

Additionally, the following crises have a low socio-economic impact, in that they have a reported cost of less than \$150 million: storm, flood, wildfire, earthquake (seismic activity), extreme temperature, industrial accident and drought.

Figure 9: Types of crises with a "low social impact"

Crucially, findings from this analysis of past-crises experienced by European Member States has shown that similar types of crises can have both a high and low impact, and thus it is not necessarily the “type” of crisis that influences the impact, but the scale of the crisis.

2.5. CROSS-BORDER CRISES

When assessing the data for this mapping exercise, it has been possible for partners to identify eight crises that were of a cross-border nature. Understanding that some types of crises may be cross-border in nature is important for COSMIC, as it is necessary for partners to understand that when considering the impact of different types of crises, their impacts can, in some cases, go beyond a single European Member State, which may then have consequences for managing and responding to the crisis. Assessing whether crises are cross-border in nature

will also complement partners' activities in developing a typology of different types of crises situations (WP1). Those crises were typically in the form of either a storm or in one instance, an epidemic.

Storm

An assessment of the data set revealed seven different storms that resulted in crises in different European Member States. For instance, in January 2003 an extratropical cyclone (storm) resulted in deaths in both Germany and France. More specifically, the following table provides further information relating to these cross-border crises:

Table 6: Cross-border storms in European Member States

Start	End	Country	Type	Name	Killed	Tot. Affected	Est. Damage (US\$ Million)
02/01/2003	02/01/2003	Germany	Storm	Calvann	5	- ³⁹	300
02/01/2003	03/01/2003	France	Storm	Calvann	1	-	0.05
29/02/2008	02/03/2008	Germany	Storm	Emma	5	-	1200
29/02/2008	02/03/2008	Austria	Storm	Emma	4	-	500
01/03/2008	01/03/2008	Poland	Storm	Emma	2	1060	50
29/02/2008	02/03/2008	Czech Rep	Storm	Emma	2	-	50
29/02/2008	02/03/2008	Romania	Storm	Emma	-	90	-
29/02/2008	01/03/2008	Belgium	Storm	Emma	-	-	-
29/02/2008	02/03/2008	Netherlands	Storm	Emma	-	-	-
07/01/2005	09/01/2005	Sweden	Storm	Erwin	7	-	2800
07/01/2005	09/01/2005	Denmark	Storm	Erwin	4	-	1300
07/01/2005	08/01/2005	United Kingdom	Storm	Erwin	3	3000	650
08/01/2005	09/01/2005	Latvia	Storm	Erwin	-	-	325
08/01/2005	08/01/2005	Germany	Storm	Erwin	2	2	270
07/01/2005	08/01/2005	Estonia	Storm	Erwin	-	100	130
08/01/2005	09/01/2005	Lithuania	Storm	Erwin	-	-	30
08/01/2005	08/01/2005	Netherlands	Storm	Erwin	-	1	-
07/01/2005	08/01/2005	Ireland	Storm	Erwin	-	-	-
07/01/2005	08/01/2005	Poland	Storm	Erwin	-	-	-
10/03/2008	10/03/2008	France	Storm	Johanna	2	-	-
10/03/2008	10/03/2008	United Kingdom	Storm	Johanna	-	-	-
23/01/2009	26/01/2009	France	Storm	Klaus	11	-	3200
23/01/2009	24/01/2009	Spain	Storm	Klaus	14	-	1900
24/01/2009	25/01/2009	Italy	Storm	Klaus	3	-	-
18/01/2007	18/01/2007	Germany	Storm	Kyrill	11	130	5500
18/01/2007	18/01/2007	United Kingdom	Storm	Kyrill	13	-	1200
18/01/2007	18/01/2007	Netherlands	Storm	Kyrill	7	-	550
18/01/2007	18/01/2007	Belgium	Storm	Kyrill	2	2	450
17/01/2007	18/01/2007	Austria	Storm	Kyrill	-	-	400

³⁹ Please note, a “dash” in the table indicates a missing value. As this data was not able to be recorded by EM-DAT. Importantly, the inclusion of the countries within the table do demonstrate that the storm did pass through them, although the extent of destruction is unknown.

18/01/2007	18/01/2007	France	Storm	Kyrill	3	-	250
18/01/2007	18/01/2007	Czech Rep	Storm	Kyrill	4	-	150
17/01/2007	19/01/2007	Denmark	Storm	Kyrill	-	-	100
18/01/2007	18/01/2007	Poland	Storm	Kyrill	6	-	100
17/01/2007	18/01/2007	Slovenia	Storm	Kyrill	-	-	100
28/02/2010	02/03/2010	France	Storm	Xynthia	53	500079	4230
28/02/2010	28/02/2010	Germany	Storm	Xynthia	4	-	1000
27/02/2010	28/02/2010	Spain	Storm	Xynthia	3	-	340
27/02/2010	27/02/2010	Portugal	Storm	Xynthia	3	-	270
28/02/2010	28/02/2010	Belgium	Storm	Xynthia	1	-	160
28/02/2010	28/02/2010	Luxembourg	Storm	Xynthia	-	-	31
28/02/2010	28/02/2010	Netherlands	Storm	Xynthia	-	-	28
28/02/2010	28/02/2010	United Kingdom	Storm	Xynthia	-	-	0.5

Due to the number of missing values in the data set, it is not possible to provide an in-depth analysis of the impact of these different storms. Based on the information that is available, it is possible to see that in some instances, these storms led to a greater impact in some countries than others. For instance, following the 2010 extratropical cyclone “Xynthia”, in some countries, such as France, there was a greater impact in terms of physical and social implications compared to others, such as Portugal and Belgium. Thus a cross-border crisis may differ in scale across different European Member States and will not necessarily result in equal destruction.

Epidemic

In 2003, the global epidemic, acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), was also present in European Member States, notably; Romania, Spain, Italy, the United Kingdom, France, Germany and Sweden. As can be seen in the following figure, although the data relating to the SARS epidemic is somewhat incomplete due to the lack of available information, it is possible to see that, for those countries where information is present, the epidemic had a considerably low impact.

Table 7: 2003 SARS Epidemic⁴⁰

Start	End	Country	Killed	Tot. Affected	Est. Damage (US\$ Million)
19/03/2003	19/03/2003	Romania	-	1	-
26/03/2003	26/03/2003	Spain	-	1	-
12/03/2003	20/04/2003	Italy	-	4	-
01/03/2003	01/04/2003	United Kingdom	-	4	-
21/03/2003	03/06/2003	France	1	6	-
09/03/2003	06/05/2003	Germany	-	9	-
28/03/2003	23/04/2003	Sweden	-	-	-

⁴⁰ Ibid.

2.6. CONCLUSION: SELECTION OF CRISES FOR FURTHER ANALYSIS

The purpose of this initial mapping task using two databases has been to develop a wider understanding of the “typical” types of crises that European Member States have been exposed to in the last 10 years (2003 to 2013). In addition to its primary mapping task of identifying “typical” crises, partners have been able to identify a series of crises that were cross-border; particularly storms. Partners have also been able to identify which types of crises, as experienced by European Member States are commonly found to have had a high physical and high societal impact. Furthermore, this chapter has demonstrated that there are also crises which have a low impact (both in terms of its physical impact and cost) on European Member States.

This mapping exercise have proved to be pivotal for directing partners attention within the COSMIC project to ensure that their selection of case studies in particular tasks, is focused on those types of crises that matter to European Member States. As part of the work involved in the COSMIC project, partners will utilise case studies of European crises in a number of tasks, including for instance, the remainder of the present report, as well as further efforts in WP1; Task 1.2 which involves partners using European and International crises to understand the search and rescue activities in different types of crises, which will go some way to informing partners of information and communication needs in different types of crises.

Accordingly, the following table provides further information as to the types of crises which are both typical and have had a high impact:

Table 8: Typical crises with a high impact

Type of crises	Typical	High physical impact	High social impact
Flood	x	x	x
Extreme temperature	x	x	x
Storm	x	x	x
Wildfire	x	x	x
Earthquake		x	x
Man-made		x	x

Thus subsequent chapters in this report will focus their analyses on case studies stemming from 6 types of crises: floods, extreme temperature, storms, wildfires, earthquakes and man-made.

Chapter 3: Group Impacts

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3 CRISES AND GROUP IMPACTS

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Understanding “who” is impacted by different types of crises is essential to the wider approach to investigating how different types of crises affect the security of the citizen within WP1 of COSMIC. Understanding how crises affect the security of citizens is crucial for COSMIC to be able to fulfil its objective of exploring how new and emerging communication technologies and applications can be most effectively utilised to promote the safety and security of citizens in crisis situations.

Since different types of crises may impact different groups within society, this chapter endeavours to understand not only “who” is impacted by different types of crises, but “how” they are impacted, particularly with regard to the wider social impact of a crisis. It will do so by examining incident data (e.g., from EM-DAT), official reports, journal articles and news items relating to selected case studies of the typical crises identified in Chapter 2. By doing so this chapter will map the types of impacts that different types of crises have.

In order to proceed with this analysis, this chapter will start by looking at the six types of “typical” and “high impact” crises identified in the mapping of European crises in Chapter 2; flood, extreme temperature, storm, wildfire, earthquake (seismic activity) and lastly, man-made. In order to direct its analysis, partners will make use of European based case studies of these types of crises to guide its analysis. These case studies have been selected through the use of examining the EM-DAT data set assessed in Chapter 2 of this report. Selection criteria included: whether a specific crisis was typical/high impact and the availability of documentation surrounding the crisis to enable the analysis. It is important to note that this approach will provide an overview of the various groups within society and how they are impacted by different types of crises.

It is important to note that whilst this chapter will reveal the types of groups impacted by different types of crises, this identification is based on a series of case studies and is therefore not wholly representative of all crisis situations. The analysis is limited in its identification of the extent of the impact as a result of the limitation of the availability of secondary data and documents. This analysis is by no means a comprehensive analysis, to do so would involve partners investing greater amounts of time and resources that would be beyond the means of the present project. Rather it supplies an introductory notion of “who” is impacted by different types of crises.

3.2 FLOOD

In the summer of 2007, parts of the United Kingdom (UK) fell victim to severe flooding in the form of a “general flood”. The UK’s Met Office measured that 414.1mm of rain fell between May and July in England and Wales; “more than at any time since it began compiling rainfall figures in 1766”.⁴¹ This unprecedented rainfall caused widespread floods, resulting in a high societal impact; as measured by EM-DAT, in addition to the 14 fatalities, 370,200 individuals were affected and the financial impact of the flood was approximately

⁴¹ “The Summer Floods: What Happened”, *BBC*, 25 June 2008. <http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/uk/7446721.stm>

\$8,448,000.00. The following table provides further information as to the breakdown of this crisis:⁴²

Table 9: UK Flood - Summer 2007

Date	Location	# of fatalities	# affected	Est. damage (US \$ million)
15-21 June, 2007	Yorkshire, Leeds, Wakefield...	1	200	448
25 June – 03 July, 2007	Yorkshire, Lincolnshire...	6	30,000	4000
20-24 July, 2007	Gloucestershire, Worcestershire...	7	340,000	4000

As seen in the table (above), the floods caused significant physical and socio-economic damage. A review of news articles and incident related reports, notably the independent review of the crisis by Michael Pitt⁴³, reveals that there were four groups that were directly impacted by the floods, which provides further evidence as to the wider social impact of the floods: citizens, critical infrastructure, business and government.

Citizens: As indicated by the data recorded by EM-DAT, citizens were both fatally injured and severely affected by the summer floods of 2007, with approximately 48,000 homes reported as being damaged.⁴⁴ Many citizens had not previously experienced floods of this magnitude and were unprepared for responding to them.⁴⁵ Furthermore, citizens physical health was affected as a result of the damp conditions that people were forced to live with. Reported conditions included; diarrhoea, asthma, sore throats, cold sores and bad chests.⁴⁶

The floods had affected not only the physical health of citizens, but also their mental health, with citizens feeling afraid and helpless as a result of the damage caused to critical infrastructure, which had secondary effects on citizens (e.g., lack of access to water and power supplies).⁴⁷ The lack of water went so far as to cause tension between some communities, providing evidence that the floods did not just affect individuals, but in some instances, the functioning of communities.⁴⁸ The impact of the floods on mental health was still noticeable in September 2008 with some individuals reporting high levels of stress and anxiety due to on-going arguments with insurance companies and rogue builders.⁴⁹

Critical infrastructure: The European Commission directive on the protection of critical infrastructures defines “critical infrastructure” as:⁵⁰

...an asset, system or part thereof located in Member States which is essential for the maintenance of vital societal functions, health, safety, security, economic or social well-being

⁴² EM-DAT, 2013.

⁴³ Pitt, Michael, *The Pitt Review: Learning Lessons from the 2007 Floods*, 2008.

<http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20080906001345/cabinetoffice.gov.uk/thepittreview.aspx>.

⁴⁴ BBC, 2008.

⁴⁵ Pitt, 2008, p. 7.

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 8.

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*

⁴⁸ *Ibid.*

⁴⁹ “Flood Victims ‘Still Traumatised’”, *BBC*, 23 September 2008.

<http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/england/humber/7632166.stm>

⁵⁰ European Commission, COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2008/114/EC of 8 December 2008 on the Identification and Designation of European Critical Infrastructures and the Assessment of the Need to Improve Their Protection”. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:345:0075:0082:EN:PDF>.

of people, and the disruption or destruction of which would have a significant impact in a Member State as a result of the failure to maintain those functions.

The impact of crises on critical infrastructure is therefore crucial to our understanding of how crises affects different groups within society. In relation to the 2007 floods a number of systems were affected; transportation, power, agriculture and authorities (e.g., fire services).⁵¹ This effect of one incident impacting other crucial services is known as a “cascading effect”; a chain of events within a system, much like a “domino effect”, with one event triggering other impacts on part of the system.

Transportation: The floods caused widespread disruption to transportation in the affected parts of the UK. For instance, as reported by the BBC, parts of the M1 Northbound and Southbound (motorway) were closed due to the risk posed by the Ulley dam, leaving citizens stranded in their cars. Elsewhere, train services run by companies including Virgin Trains, Midland Mainline and Arriva Trains were cancelled.⁵² As outlined by Pitt, further disruption was caused to both car transportation and rail networks following the rainfall in July; “around 10,000 people were left stranded on the M5 and surrounding roads as drivers were forced to abandon cars, and 500 people were stranded at Gloucester railway station as the railway network failed”.⁵³

Power: A crucial consequence of the floods concerns its effect on the provision of power to the affected areas, thereby further complicating and undermining the capacities of individuals and authorities to co-ordinate and respond to the crisis. As reported by Pitt, following the floods in June, in Sheffield, the Neepsend electricity substation was forced to shut down, causing 40,000 people to lose power. Following further rainfall in July, Castle Meads electricity substation was also forced to close, causing 42,000 people to lose power in Gloucester for 24 hours. The actions of authorities, armed forces and the Environmental Agency prevented further disruption at Walham electricity station.⁵⁴ Not restricted to impacting the provision of electricity, the BBC also reported the bursting of a gas main in Shropshire as a result of a collapsed bridge; affecting both transportation and the provision of energy.⁵⁵

Water: Water supplies were also affected as a result of the floods. In Tewkesbury, for instance, Severn Trent Water’s Mythe water treatment works flooded, leaving 350,000 people without access to water for two weeks.⁵⁶

Agriculture: Agriculture was also affected by the floods; affecting the provision of fresh crop produce as well as affecting the livelihood of those involved in farming in the affected areas (between 2600 and 5000 farms), costing approximately £11.2 million.⁵⁷ Dairy and livestock were also affected through drowning, water contamination and the added cost of having to purchase feed due to the floods affecting grazing land.⁵⁸

⁵¹ Pitt, 2008.

⁵² “Floods Force Thousands from Homes”, *BBC*, 26 June 2007. <http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/uk/6239828.stm>

⁵³ Pitt, 2008, p. 7.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵⁵ *BBC*, 2007.

⁵⁶ Pitt, 2008, p. 7.

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 9.

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

Authorities: A range of authorities were involved in having to respond to the unfolding floods. Noticeably, as reported by the BBC, in Humberside in June, fire crews received 1500 emergency calls in a 12-hour period, placing a strain on their capacities to respond.⁵⁹ Additionally, following the floods, under the European Solidarity Fund, the European Commission paid £31 million to local authorities, police authorities, fire and rescue services to offset costs sustained in dealing with the floods and the subsequent knock on effects.⁶⁰

Business: In addition to affecting citizens, agriculture and transportation providers, other local businesses were also affected. As reported by the BBC, the cost of flooding to local businesses “averaged between £75,000 and £112,000 (further information can be seen in the Figure, right).⁶¹

FLOODED PROPERTIES AND BUSINESSES			
Summer 2007			
Region	Households	Businesses	Total
East Midlands	4,581	290	4,871
London	1,108	302	1,410
South East	5,896	129	6,025
South West	4,915	1,000	5,915
Wales	32	4	36
West Midlands	8,450	1,453	9,903
Yorks/ Humberside	23,479	3,718	27,197
Total	48,461	6,896	55,357

Source: Environment Agency

Figure 10: Flooding to homes and businesses

As identified by Pitt, the floods caused damage to local heritage sites including for instance; Fountains Abbey, Blenheim Palace and many listed properties. Furthermore, businesses and heritage sites alike were affected by the reduction in tourism during this period.⁶² Insurance companies were also severely affected by the floods, with costs of approximately £3 billion.⁶³

Government: Both local and national government were affected by the floods, particularly in relation to their budgets. In the short term, the Department for Children Schools and Families (DCSF) had to allocate £10 million to cover the short term costs of getting children back into affected schools, additional funding was pledged at a later date.⁶⁴ Elsewhere, as revealed by the BBC, in order to improve flood defences, the British government pledged approximately £1 billion over a three-year period.⁶⁵ Thus the floods had a financial impact on both national and local government.

The floods in the UK in 2007 affected different groups within society. The following table summarises these (charted) affects:

Table 10: Group impacts of the 2007 UK floods

Citizens	Critical infrastructure	Business	Government
Physically	Transportation	Local business	Local
Psychologically	Power	Heritage	National
Sense of community	Water	Tourism	
Citizens' property	Agriculture	Insurance companies	
	Authorities		

⁵⁹ BBC, 2007.

⁶⁰ Pitt, 2008, p. 9.

⁶¹ “Cost of 2007 Floods Put at £3.2bn”, BBC, 18 January 2010. <http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/uk/8464717.stm>

⁶² Pitt, 2008, p. 9.

⁶³ Ibid., p. xxi.

⁶⁴ Ibid., p. 11.

⁶⁵ BBC, 2010.

The extent to which these groups were impacted is largely dependent on the scale of the floods that the UK experienced in 2007.

3.2 EXTREME TEMPERATURE

Between July and August 2003, some European Member States experienced extreme temperatures in the form of a “heat wave”, with temperatures consistently above 40 Celsius⁶⁶ in some European Member States, resulting in large numbers of individuals being killed and in some countries, sizeable financial implications.⁶⁷ As argued by the Earth Policy Institute (EPI), although crises relating to extreme temperatures are not given as much attention as other types of crises, “heat waves are a silent killer, mostly affecting the elderly, the very young, or the chronically ill”.⁶⁸ The following table provides further information as to the extent of the impact of the crisis:⁶⁹

Table 11: European “heat wave” 2003

Start	End	Country	Killed	Est. Damage (US\$ Million)
00/07/2003	00/08/2003	Austria	345	280
01/08/2003	15/08/2003	Belgium	1175	-
00/07/2003	00/07/2003	Croatia	788	-
00/07/2003	00/07/2003	Czech Rep	418	-
01/08/2003	20/08/2003	France	19490	4400
00/08/2003	00/08/2003	Germany	9355	1650
16/07/2003	15/08/2003	Italy	20089	4400
00/07/2003	00/07/2003	Luxembourg	170	-
31/07/2003	13/08/2003	Netherlands	965	-
00/08/2003	00/08/2003	Portugal	2696	-
00/07/2003	00/08/2003	Slovakia	-	150
00/07/2003	00/08/2003	Slovenia	289	80
01/08/2003	11/08/2003	Spain	15090	880
00/07/2003	00/07/2003	Switzerland	1039	280
00/07/2003	00/07/2003	United Kingdom	301	-

The extreme temperatures caused significant physical and socio-economic damage. A review of news articles and incident related reports, reveals that there were four groups that were directly impacted by the heat wave: citizens, critical infrastructure, business and government.

Citizens: As identified in the table (above), in numerous European Member States citizens were killed by the extreme temperatures. As revealed by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) report in 2004, the heat wave resulted in more than 30,000 people being

⁶⁶ “French Heat Toll Almost 15,000”, *BBC*, 25 September 2003.

<http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/world/europe/3139694.stm>

⁶⁷ Note: The number of “affected” individuals is unknown to EM-DAT.

⁶⁸ Bhattacharya, Shaoni, “European Heatwave Caused 35,000 Deaths”, *New Scientist*, 10 October 2003.

<http://www.newscientist.com/article/dn4259-european-heatwave-caused-35000-deaths.html>

⁶⁹ EM-DAT, 2013.

killed, making the crisis “one of the ten deadliest natural disasters in Europe for the last 100 years and the worst in the last 50 years”.⁷⁰

From a socio-demographic perspective, the elderly were most severely affected.⁷¹ Furthermore, women, were more likely than men to be affected (70% of women compared to 40% of men).⁷² In France, it was believed that the lack of communication, and the lack of doctors due to the crisis occurring during the summer vacation period contributed to the number of deaths. As outlined in a case study of the event by the UK Met Office, the effect of the heat wave on citizens included; heat stroke, dehydration, sunburn, air pollution and in some instances, drowning (as people tried to use rivers and lakes to cool off).⁷³

As revealed by a study for the European Commission looking into the number of fatalities caused by the crisis, Robine et al. utilised past statistics on death rates in 13 European Member States to determine whether or not there was a notable increase in the death rate as a result of the crisis.⁷⁴ Their findings revealed that the death rate had risen by a substantial number.⁷⁵

In comparison with the 1998-2002 period, more than 80,000 additional deaths were recorded in 2003 in the twelve countries concerned by excess mortality. Whereas 70,000 of these additional deaths occurred during the summer, over 7,000 took place afterwards. Nearly 45,000 additional deaths were recorded in August alone, as well as more than 11,000 in June, more than 10,000 in July and nearly 5,000 in September.

Business: The extreme temperatures that affected European Member States in 2003 also had an impact on business. The heat wave particularly affected those whose livelihoods may have been impacted by the cascading crisis resulting from the heat wave; forest fires, which impacted some businesses (this will be further discussed below).⁷⁶ Elsewhere however, in the UK, the extreme temperature had a positive effect on business, particularly with regard to encouraging tourism within the UK, as a result of its unusually high temperatures.⁷⁷

Critical infrastructure: As with other crises assessed in this chapter, the European heat wave in 2003 resulted in failures to several different types of critical infrastructure, including; agriculture, water, energy and transportation.

Agriculture: As highlighted by the 2004 UNEP report, the heat wave severely affected agriculture, costing European farming approximately €13.1 billion.⁷⁸ Both crops and livestock were affected, predominantly a result of the dry conditions.⁷⁹

⁷⁰ *Impacts of Summer 2003 Heat Wave in Europe*, United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), March 2004, p. 2. http://www.unisdr.org/files/1145_ewheatwave.en.pdf.

⁷¹ Ibid.

⁷² BBC, 25 September 2003.

⁷³ “The Heatwave of 2003”, *Met Office Education*, no date. <http://www.metoffice.gov.uk/education/teens/case-studies/heatwave>

⁷⁴ Robine, JM, SL Cheung, S Le Roy, H Van Oyen, and FR Herrmann, *Report on Excess Mortality in Europe During Summer 2003*, EU Community Action Programme for Public Health, Grant Agreement 2005114, *2003 Heat Wave Project*, 28 February 2007.

http://ec.europa.eu/health/ph_projects/2005/action1/docs/action1_2005_a2_15_en.pdf

⁷⁵ Ibid., p. 12.

⁷⁶ Walton, Doreen, “Europe Counts Cost of Scorching Summer”, *BBC*, 6 August 2003. <http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/business/3128597.stm>

⁷⁷ Met Office Education, no date.

⁷⁸ Ibid.

Water: The heat wave, also resulted in water shortages which served to further contribute to the devastation experienced by farmers in the affected areas.⁸⁰ In the UK, some individuals were affected by drinking water shortages, as well as the introduction of a hosepipe ban.⁸¹

Power: The heat wave also caused complications for the provision of energy in some European Member States. In Germany for instance, two nuclear power plants were forced to close as a result of the lack of water to cool the generators.⁸² This was similarly experienced in France, which concurrently faced an increase in demand for energy.⁸³

Transportation: Lastly, the case study report by the UK’s Met Office claimed that public transport (in the UK) was also affected in that addition to the London Underground being unbearable, some railway lines were affected as the tracks buckled due to the heat. There were also reports of damage cause to road surfaces (melting), as well as low river levels preventing some movements for sailboats.⁸⁴

Government: Both local and national government were affected by the heat wave, and as with the flood case study, the impact was financial. Not only did governments have to respond to the financial costs involved in responding to the heat wave, but also, in some European Member States, wildfires were a cascading effect of the crisis. As identified by the 2004 UNEP report:

“More than 25000 fires were recorded in Portugal, Spain, Italy, France, Austria, Finland, Denmark and Ireland. The estimation of forest areas destroyed reached 647 069 hectares. Portugal was the worst hit with 390146 ha burned, destroying around 5.6 % of its forest area. Spain came second with 127525 ha burned. The agricultural area burned reached 44 123 ha plus 8,973 ha of unoccupied land, and 1700 ha of inhabited areas. This was by far the worst forest fire season that Portugal had faced in the last 23 years. In October 2003, the financial impact estimated by Portugal exceeded 1 billion euros”⁸⁵.

Thus, some countries experienced further damages leading to a greater financial burden for national and local governments to bear.

This review of documents related to the 2003 extreme temperatures experienced by some European Member States suggests that the heat wave did indeed have an impact:

Table 12: Group impacts of the 2003 Europe heat wave

Citizens	Critical infrastructure	Business	Government
Physically	Transportation	Local business	Local
	Power (supply declined, demand increased)	Tourism (positive and negative depending on location)	National

⁷⁹ *Impacts of Summer 2003 Heat Wave in Europe*, 2004.

⁸⁰ Walton, Doreen, “Europe Counts Cost of Scorching Summer”, *BBC*, 6 August 2003. <http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/business/3128597.stm>

⁸¹ Met Office Education, no date.

⁸² *Ibid.*

⁸³ *Impacts of Summer 2003 Heat Wave in Europe*, 2004.

⁸⁴ Met Office Education, no date.

⁸⁵ *Impacts of Summer 2003 Heat Wave in Europe*, 2004, p. 4.

	Water		
	Agriculture		

3.3 STORM

Between the 27 February and 1 March 2010 parts of Western Europe were affected by the windstorm cyclone, Xynthia. Cyclone Xynthia led to gusts of wind up to 93mph (miles per hour) in France, as well as 26-foot wave leading to inland flooding.⁸⁶ As recorded by EM-DAT, this cross-border cyclone affected several European countries, including; France, Germany, Spain, Portugal, Belgium, Luxembourg, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom.⁸⁷

As reported in the table below, the storm had a physical impact on the security of citizens in the form of loss of life (e.g., some individuals in France drowned⁸⁸) and, notably, in France, a vast number of individuals were affected (e.g., injured, damage caused to their home etc.). Furthermore, the table also indicates the estimated damage caused by the storm, lending some understanding towards one aspect of the financial impact of the storm.⁸⁹

Table 13: The physical and societal impact of cyclone Xynthia

Country	Number of fatalities	Number affected	Est. Damage (US\$ Million)
France	54	500079	4230
Germany	4	- ⁹⁰	1000
Spain	3	-	340
Portugal	3	-	270
Belgium	1	-	160
Luxembourg	-	-	31
Netherlands	-	-	28
United Kingdom	-	-	0.5

A review of news articles and incident related reports reveals that there were three identifiable groups that were affected by the storm: citizens, critical infrastructure and government.

Citizens: Members of the public at the scene of a crisis were commonly found to be affected by the cyclone. Following Cyclone Xynthia there were multiple reports of children having been killed. For instance, as revealed by a news report by the International news provider, CNN (Cable News Network), in Spain two children were killed in a car accident as a result of the storm. Elsewhere, in Germany, a two year old drowned having been swept into a river. Elsewhere, in Portugal a child was killed as a result of a falling tree. In Belgium, a man was also killed by a falling tree.⁹¹

Citizens were not solely affected in the form of fatalities. For example, in France, homes of

⁸⁶ “More Than 50 Dead as Violent Storm Hits Europe”, *Telegra* <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/europe/france/734/Europe.html>

⁸⁷ *EM-DAT: The OFDA/CRED International Disaster Database* Belgium, 2013. www.emdat.be.

⁸⁸ “At Least 58 Dead as Storm Sweeps Across Western Europe” <http://edition.cnn.com/2010/WORLD/europe/03/01/europe.storm> EM-DAT, 2013.

⁸⁹ Note: A “-” indicates missing data.

⁹¹ CNN.com, March 2010.

In pictures: Storm batters western Europe

citizens and residents in the affected areas were damaged, leaving some homeless; and many other citizens experienced significant losses of personal possessions (*see figure - right*⁹²) (e.g., vehicles, clothes, jewellery etc.).

As with the case study of the floods, a cascading effect is also present in this instance. Cyclone Xynthia affected the daily working of the system, society, by disrupting communities, transportation and energy provision. Crucially, some cascading effects led to some individuals being affected as a result of other groups being affected. For instance, following the storm, the French energy provider, Electricite de France (EDF) was impacted causing a loss of energy being supplied to households – members of these households would have been affected as a result.⁹³ Other service providers were also impacted, such as transportation, which may have impacted some citizens.⁹⁴ Thus it is important to consider the dependencies between different groups when considering the overall impact of crises on the security of citizens.

Figure 11: BBC - In pictures: storm batters Western Europe

Critical infrastructure: As with the case study on floods, cyclone Xynthia also had an impact on some aspects of society’s critical infrastructure: transportation, the provision of energy and the functioning of some authorities.

Transportation: Damage from cyclone Xynthia was seen in relation to the provision of transportation, notably the rail network in several affected European Member States, and air transport in Paris. As reported in the news, the storm affected train services in Germany, North Rhine-Westfalia, Baden-Wuerttemberg, and Hesse, resulting in “massive disruptions and a partial shutdown of services”.⁹⁵ Elsewhere the BBC reported that rail services were “severely affected” in Northern Spain, as well as delays in Western France due to flooded tracks.⁹⁶ In Paris, the Paris-Charles de Gaulle International Airport was also affected with approximately 100 flights being cancelled as a result of the “blustery conditions”.⁹⁷ By impacting some forms of transportation, not only are transport providers affected, but so too were those individuals that used the transport network, including citizens in the form of both residents and travellers.

Power: In France, severely affected by the storm, the energy provider EDF was unable to provide power to over 500,000 households. Power outages were also reported in Portugal and Eastern Belgium, where they had “problems with fallen trees, roofs blown off and electricity cables not working”.⁹⁸

Authorities: In France, the storm also affected the ordinary running of emergency services, with military personnel and firefighters having to be mobilised to assist in the aftermath of the crisis.⁹⁹

⁹² “In Pictures: Storm Batters Western Europe”, *BBC*, 1 March 2010.

http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/in_pictures/8541808.stm.

⁹³ CNN.com, March 2010.

⁹⁴ Ibid.

⁹⁵ Ibid.

⁹⁶ “At Least 50 Die in Europe Storms”, *BBC*, 28 February 2010.

<http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/world/europe/8540762.stm>.

⁹⁷ CNN.com, March 2010.

⁹⁸ *BBC*, 2010.

⁹⁹ *CNN.com*, 2013.

Government: As reported by CNN, due to the scale of the crisis, in France, the government were also impacted due to the need to deploy financial aid and support to the affected areas; “President Sarkozy said he was making €3 million (\$4 million) of emergency funds available for the victims”¹⁰⁰.

This review of documents related to Cyclone Xynthia in 2010 suggest that three main groups were affected; citizens, critical infrastructure and the government. Not explicit in the news reports and other documentation regarding this event, was the impact of the storm on business related groups, including; tourists, travellers, businesses and service providers. As has been identified through the consideration of the impact of the cyclone on transportation providers and damage to households, there may have also been tourists and travellers that were affected as a result of the storm. In addition, just as households were affected, the storm could have also impacted local businesses and other forms of critical infrastructure (e.g., health care, telecommunications, agriculture etc.).

Table 14: Group impacts of Cyclone Xynthia

Citizens	Critical infrastructure	Business	Government
Physically	Transportation	Reliable data about impact on business not available	National
Citizens' property	Power		
	Authorities		

3.4 WILDFIRE

In the summer of 2007, wildfires spread across parts of Greece, particularly Peloponnese; this crisis peaked between the 24th and 30th August 2007. As recorded by EM-DAT, the fires resulted in both a physical and socio-economic impact, with 67 people killed (with some other reports claiming that 87 people were killed¹⁰¹), 5392 individuals affected and a financial cost of approximately \$1750 billion.¹⁰² The damage caused by the fires was extensive; approximately 670,000 acres of forest and farmland were burnt.¹⁰³ Whilst some of the fires were a result of extremely hot and dry weather conditions, along with strong winds¹⁰⁴, there were also reports of some fires having been intentionally set, with a 26 year old farmer arrested and prosecuted for arson related offences.¹⁰⁵

An investigation of news articles, incident related journal articles and reports have revealed that four groups were affected by the wildfires: citizens, critical infrastructure, business and the government.

Citizens: As revealed by the data recorded in EM-DAT, the physical impact of the wildfires in Greece during the summer of 2007 was devastating for citizens. A report in the *Economist* identified additional details regarding this physical impact, claiming that 100 villages had

¹⁰⁰ Ibid.

¹⁰¹ Rosenfeld, Everett, “Top 10 Devastating Wildfires”, *Time*, 8 June 2011.

http://www.time.com/time/specials/packages/article/0,28804,2076476_2076484_2076504,00.html

¹⁰² EM-DAT, 2013.

¹⁰³ Rosenfeld, 2011.

¹⁰⁴ “Greece Forest Fires - Summer 2007”, *European Commission: Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection*, December 1, 2011. http://ec.europa.eu/echo/civil_protection/civil/forestfires_el_2007.htm.

¹⁰⁵ Rosenfeld, 2011.

been “guttled”.¹⁰⁶ Elsewhere, the *Guardian* reported damage to other citizens’ vehicles.¹⁰⁷ Thus citizens were not only affected in terms of their physical wellbeing, but also their property and for some (as will be seen in subsequent points of reference) their way of life was severely affected by destruction to critical infrastructure, farming and businesses.

The wildfires also had a perceived impact on the environment, which could serve to survey affect the security of citizens. Hamashige, writing for National Geographic, emphasised the importance of understanding the potential impact of the wildfires on the environment, including its devastation to forests which provide a central protective measure for society in its ability to combat air pollution, reduce (in-part) high temperature peaks, and crucially provides a source of oxygen. Furthermore, the wildfires severely damaged seven Natura 2000 sites, a protective area aimed at halting the loss of biodiversity in Europe. Furthermore, the damage to these areas also served to affect the security of different animal species, including endangered species such as the golden jackal, red deer as well as lizard and turtle species.¹⁰⁸ Crucially, following the fires, further concern was voiced by environmentalists as to the protection of Greek forests from future hazards and whether preventive action was not taken by the Greek government.¹⁰⁹

Critical infrastructure: In comparison to other types of crises assessed in this chapter, critical infrastructure does not appear to be as affected as severely. Rather, the analysis of the 2007 Greece wildfires illustrated that critical infrastructure that was particularly affected by the fires was agriculture and fire services.

Agriculture: As revealed by Rosenfeld, approximately 670,000 acres of forest and farmland were burnt.¹¹⁰ The damage to livestock was extensive, as was that damage to the olive crop. In addition, there was also evidence to destruction to 731 stables – further impacting agriculture as well as other potential business ventures.¹¹¹

Authorities: From the perspective of firefighters, not only did the emergency services suffer loss of life, with the deaths of three firefighters as a result of the wildfires, but in addition, some firefighters were over-burdened by the scale of the crisis, causing them to suffer from exhaustion, as well as having their own personal losses to deal with (e.g., damage to their own property).¹¹² A study of 102 male firefighters, published by the *Lancet*, revealed that some firefighters were having to deal with other forms of social harm relating to their experiences, particularly, psychological distress and in some instances post-traumatic stress disorder (19 of the firefighters, 12 of which were seasonally employed).¹¹³

Business: Reports stemming from the wildfires suggest that business was noticeably affected by the fires. As identified in their report, Psarros et al. argued that 30 office buildings had

¹⁰⁶ “Burning Forests: Fighting Greek Fire”, *The Economist*, 29 August 2007.

“Greek Wildfires Rage On”, *The Guardian*, 28 August 2007.

8/helenasmith.international.

ery Could Take Decades”, *National Geographic*, 3 October 2007.

749428903.html.

, Sophia Martinaki, and Ioanna-Despoina Bergiannaki, “Traumatic Recurrence”, *The Lancet*, Vol. 371, No. 9609, January 2008, p. 301.

Figure 12: Photograph by Petros/Giannakouris/AP

been damaged and in some instances, some warehouses were destroyed. This devastation would have affected the everyday operations of some businesses and therefore, also the livelihood of some citizens that were either directly or indirectly involved with them (e.g., owners, employees and customers for instance).¹¹⁴

In addition to businesses being affected, the wildfires also affected local heritage, including the destruction of 12 churches, as well as presenting a danger to Ancient Olympia (as indicated in the photograph – left¹¹⁵) as well as numerous other historically important sites.¹¹⁶ Accordingly, the wildfires also impacted tourism, which would serve to further affect the economic wellbeing of those involved in the tourist business.

Government: The wildfires in Greece in 2007 affected national government as well as EU Member States. The fires led to the pressing need for financial assistance for numerous communities, and as reported by the *Economist*, the Greek government, in the lead up to national elections in September, were “quick” to pass out assistance to those in need, providing funds of up to 13,000 to those villagers affected by the fire.¹¹⁷

In addition to facing the financial consequences of the fires, the government were also faced with a great amount of criticism, thus putting them under political pressure prior to the impending election. Some went so far as to label those in charge as “incompetent”, with public protests in Athens.¹¹⁸

Having declared a state of emergency, the Greek government were forced to ask for help from EU Member States via the Monitoring and Information Centre (MIC). Over the course of the summer, Greek officials requested assistance on four occasions (27th June, 5 July, 18 July and 24 August).¹¹⁹ This request for assistance was in the form of Canadairs (water-bombing aircrafts), heavy duty helicopters, specialists and additional fire crew.

Assistance deployed through the Community Civil Protection Mechanism

A number of European Member States responded to these calls for assistance, a sign of what was referred to as “European Solidarity”, of which further information can be seen in the figure left:¹²⁰

¹¹⁵ Hamashige, 2007.

¹¹⁶ Psarros et al., 2008.

¹¹⁷ *The Economist*, 29 August 2007.

¹¹⁸ Attewill, Fred, “Anger at Greek Government’s Wildfire Response”, *The Guardian*, 28 August 2007. <http://www.guardian.co.uk/world/2007/aug/28/naturaldisasters.features11>.

¹¹⁹ *European Commission: Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection*, 2011.

¹²⁰ *Ibid.*

Figure 13: 2007 Greece wildfires - EU response European Commission: Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection, 2011.

The examination of documentation surrounding the 2007 Greece wildfires has revealed that they affected a number of groups:

Table 15: Group impact of the 2007 Greece wildfires

Citizens	Critical infrastructure	Business	Government
Physically	Agriculture	Local business	Local
	Authorities	Heritage	National
		Tourism	European Union

3.5 EARTHQUAKE

In May 2012, Northern Italy faced two significant earthquakes in a single month, both of which resulted in a physical and social impact. The first earthquake, which will be the focus of this case study, took place on the 20th May 2012 between Finale Emilia (province of Modena) and Sant'Agostino (province of Ferrara). The earthquake killed seven people, affected 11,050 individuals and cost approximately \$15,800 million.¹²¹ The second earthquake in the same area took place nine days later, killing a further 17 people and affecting 14,350 people.

As with the other types of crises analysed in this chapter, an investigation of news articles, incident related journal articles and reports have revealed that four distinguishable groups were affected by the earthquake: citizens, critical infrastructure, business and the government.

Citizens: The earthquake in Italy on the 20th May impacted citizens. Not only did the earthquake result in loss of life, but in addition, some members of the public were affected by the earthquake as a result of damage to their property as well as damage to their businesses. Officials claimed that up to 3000 people were not able to return to their homes and would have to stay in temporary shelter.¹²² However, even though not all residential structures were damaged, in total up to 7000 individuals remained homeless either through not being able to return to their homes, or in some instances, avoiding their homes due to fear of further after-shocks and the potential danger they could face – illustrating that the earthquake also has a psychological impact.¹²³

¹²¹ EM-DAT, 2013.

¹²² Jewkes, Stephen, “Italy Quake Kills at Least Six, Damages Historic Buildings”, *Reuters*, 20 May 2012. <http://www.reuters.com/article/2012/05/20/us-quake-italy-idUSBRE84J01K20120520>

¹²³ Rossetto, Tiziana, David Alexander, Enrica Verrucci, Ioanna Ioannou, Randolph Borg, Jose’ Melo, Bryan Cahill, and Indranil Kongar, *The 20th May 2012 Emilia Romagna Earthquake: EPICentre Field Observation Report*, UCL EPICentre Department of Civil, Environmental and Geomatic Engineering, University College London, 1 June 2012. http://www.ucl.ac.uk/~ucestor/research-earthquake/EPICentre_Report_EPI-FO-200512-v2.pdf

Critical infrastructure: The earthquake in Italy impacted multiple forms of critical infrastructure, including: agriculture, schools, power/energy, water and transportation. The extent of damage to these different infrastructures differed in intensity.

Agriculture: The region affected was known for its production and selling of parmesan cheese, the earthquake significantly affected the production and distribution of this produce, as a result of the damage suffered, with approximately 300,000 cheeses damaged, resulting in a loss of approximately €250 million (*as seen in the image – right*).¹²⁴ Further agricultural loss was suffered in Northern Italy as a result of damage caused to agricultural buildings.¹²⁵

Figure 14: Agricultural & financial loss (Telegraph, 2012)

Schools: Following an investigation in the affected areas, a team from EPICentre (Department of Civil, Environmental and Geomatic Engineering) University College London (UCL) reported damage suffered by a local elementary school in San Carlo.¹²⁶

Power: In addition to schools and agriculture being affected, the team from UCL also confirmed that local residents had reported that the earthquake had damaged gas pipes, as well as damage to electricity. It was believed that the loss of electricity was minor, in that it had only been unavailable for four hours, whilst repairing the gas pipes could have taken up to a week to repair.¹²⁷

Water: The observations from those representing UCL also suggested that water towers had been affected by the earthquake, with the team reporting cracks in the interior forced core (as seen in their image (below)).¹²⁸

Figure 15: Cracks to a water tower al Churches and Castles”, *Telegraph.co.uk*, 21 May 2012, sec. picturegalleries. <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/picturegalleries/worldnews/9280177/Earthquake-in-northern-Italy-damages-medieval-churches-and-castles.html>

¹²⁵ “Five Killed in Northern Italy Earthquake”, *The Independent*, 20 May 2012. <http://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/europe/five-killed-in-northern-italy-earthquake-7769382.html>

¹²⁶ Rosetto et al., 2012, p. 37.

¹²⁷ Ibid.

¹²⁸ Ibid., p. 36.

¹²⁹ Ibid., p. 37.

Transportation: As a final point, the UCL group also reported cracks in road surfaces, however, they did point out that many of the roads already had damage prior to the earthquake, and that the earthquake had simply “exacerbated” them.¹²⁹

Business: In addition to affecting citizens and several types of critical infrastructure, the earthquake in Northern Italy also severely affected business. Whilst there was evidence of local businesses being affected by the quake, for instance significant damage to warehouses (e.g.,

a ceramics factor)¹³⁰, there were also reports of damages to banks and other local businesses.¹³¹

Figure 16: Damage to local heritage

Crucially local *heritage* was also significantly affected, which not only impacts upon the tourist business but also the everyday lives of local citizens. The earthquake, combined with several after-shocks significantly damaged local heritage including a clock tower (left¹³²), churches, the town hall and Estense Castle.¹³³ As reported by Reuters news agency: “The tremors seriously damaged many historic churches and other buildings, adding up to the greatest loss to Italy's artistic heritage since an earthquake in 1997 ravaged the Basilica of St Francis in Assisi, where

the ceiling collapsed”.¹³⁴

Government: As with other crises assessed in this report, the earthquake in Italy, also impacted both local and national government, with the need for support and resources to be coordinated to assist those requiring assistance.¹³⁵

This review of documents related to the 2012 earthquake in Northern Italy show that four main groups were affected; citizens, critical infrastructure, business and the government:

Table 16: Group impact of the 2012 Italy earthquake

Citizens	Critical infrastructure	Business	Government
Physically	Transportation	Local business	Local
Psychologically	Power	Heritage	National
Citizens' property	Water		
	Agriculture		
	Schools		

3.6 MAN-MADE

At 08:50 BST on 7th July 2005, the city of London’s transportation network was intentionally attacked by four individuals. The first attack occurred on the London Underground on the Circle line between Aldgate and Liverpool Street, the second at Edgware Road station, and the third on the Piccadilly line between Russell Square and King’s Cross. The fourth attack

¹³⁰ Telegraph, 2012.
¹³¹ Rosetto et al., 2012.
¹³² Telegraph, 2012.
¹³³ Rosetto et al., 2012.
¹³⁴ Reuters, 2012.
¹³⁵ Rosetto et al., 2012.

occurred an hour later, targeting a London bus service at Tavistock Place. These attacks caused 52 fatalities and 770 injuries.¹³⁶

A review of news articles, incident related reports and journal articles revealed that the impact of the attacks went beyond those initially, they also affected; citizens, critical infrastructure, business and national and local government.

Citizens: The attacks resulted in citizens that were directly affected by the attacks by either being injured or in some instances, killed. There were also those members of the public at the scene of the attacks who were not directly injured, but were exposed to the attacks and thus may have experienced some form of psychological trauma. By its very nature, as identified by Nacos an act of terror is designed to instil fear in the community at large¹³⁷, by expanding its reach through publicity¹³⁸, and thus there were many citizens that were also indirectly affected by the attacks; both those within the local community as well as further afield. For instance a telephone survey of Londoner's by Sheppard et al., shortly following the attacks revealed that for some individuals there were substantial levels of stress following the attacks.¹³⁹ In addition, following the attacks, there was widespread concern over backlash against the Muslim community, where reports of hate crimes had taken place, for instance, a school boy had been attacked in the West Country.¹⁴⁰

Critical infrastructure: The attacks on London in July 2005 affected several forms of infrastructure, including: transportation, authorities, communications and in some instances, schools.

Transportation: The attacks on London in 2005 involved direct action against the public transportation network affecting local buses, trains, roads and in some cases, airports. The effects of the attack was not necessarily a long-term effect, but a short-term one, causing further distress and disturbance to citizens in the surrounding areas affected.¹⁴¹

Authorities: The attacks on London also affected the functional capacities of emergency services, including the police, fire service and the ambulance service in the affected areas. Due to the increased demand for assistance, the London ambulance service for instance, were only able to send ambulances to patients with life-threatening illnesses or injuries, and asked that “until further notice, only be sending ambulances to

Figure 17: Impact of the London attacks on transportation (Guardian, 7 July 2005)

¹³⁶ “7 July bombings: What happened?”, *BBC*, no date.

http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/shared/spl/hi/uk/05/london_blasts/what_happened/html/default.stm

¹³⁷ Nacos, Brigitte Lebens, *Mass-mediated Terrorism the Central Role of the Media in Terrorism and Counterterrorism*, Rowman & Littlefield, Lanham, Md., 2007.

¹³⁸ Watson, Hayley, “Dependent Citizen Journalism and the Publicity of Terror”, *Terrorism and Political Violence*, Vol. 24, No. 3, 2012, pp. 465–482.

¹³⁹ Sheppard, Ben, G James Rubin, Jamie K Wardman, and Simon Wessely, “Terrorism and Dispelling the Myth of a Panic Prone Public”, *Journal of Public Health Policy*, Vol. 27, No. 3, 2006, pp. 219–245; discussion 246–249.

¹⁴⁰ Dodd, Vikram, “Calls for calm as fear of severe backlash grows” *The Guardian*, 13 July 2005. <http://www.guardian.co.uk/uk/2005/jul/13/otherparties.society>

¹⁴¹ McIntosh, Neil, “Bomb Blasts Plunge London into Chaos”, *The Guardian*, 7 July 2005. <http://www.guardian.co.uk/news/blog/2005/jul/07/explosionsplun>

patients across the capital with life-threatening illnesses or injuries. This will enable us to focus on treating the large numbers of casualties at the scene". In addition, ambulance staff were supported by ambulance teams from surrounding Home Counties including Bedfordshire, Hertfordshire, Surrey, Kent and Essex, as well as from voluntary groups such as the British Red Cross and St John's Ambulance.¹⁴² The attacks also placed pressure on hospitals in the affected areas; in many London hospitals staff were called in from their annual leave to help with the crisis.¹⁴³

Communications: In the immediate aftermath of the attacks, the UK's mobile telephone networks were also impacted by the attacks, with some networks running close to capacity. This led to some networks, such as Vodafone (see right¹⁴⁴), asking its customers to not making any "unnecessary or lengthy calls", if required by the emergency services, the network would also be able to "free up capacity on its network by blocking other customers".¹⁴⁵

Figure 18: The attacks impacted the Vodafone UK network.

In addition to mobile networks being affected, some Internet sites were also running slow due to the high traffic demand as seen following the attacks in the USA on the 11th September 2001.¹⁴⁶

Schools: As a result of the attacks (on the Thursday morning) affecting the public transportation network, schools in two London boroughs (Westminster City and Camden) were shut due to concerns over levels of public transport.¹⁴⁷

Business: A study by the London Chamber of Commerce and Business, revealed that following the attacks, in July 2005 there was a reduction in the number of people visiting the West End which would have impacted on businesses within the West End (20 to 30% reduction), this was further compounded by the subsequent attempted attacks on the 21st July 2005. There was also evidence to suggest that the attacks had caused concern for people working in the affected areas and some employers, not wanting to add to the stress of their employees, being forced to take alternative, more costly measures to operate.¹⁴⁸ An example can be seen here:

An export trading firm based outside central London reported that it had changed from getting its staff to deliver important shipping documents to the City and have instead begun using couriers. A senior manager with the company said: "We did not want to expose any employee to the stress of going into the City so soon after the bombings, so sent the documents by motor cycle courier. This is a regular requirement, and for the next few weeks we will be using a

¹⁴² Andalo, Debbie, "Ambulance Service Reports 'Large Number' of Casualties", *The Guardian*, 7 July 2005. <http://www.guardian.co.uk/society/2005/jul/07/terrorism.attackonlondon3>.

¹⁴³ "Hospitals Treat Hundreds of Blast Casualties", *The Guardian*, 7 July 2005. <http://www.guardian.co.uk/society/2005/jul/07/hospitals.terrorism>

¹⁴⁴ Vodafone logo, 2010. <http://www.dearcustomerrelations.com/wp-content/uploads/2010/05/vodafone-logo.gif>

¹⁴⁵ "Internet Takes Strain as World Wakes up to London Blast News", *The Guardian*, 7 July 2005. <http://www.guardian.co.uk/technology/2005/jul/07/media.pressandpublishing>

¹⁴⁶ Ibid.

¹⁴⁷ Ford, Liz, "Schools to Close Friday", *The Guardian*, 7 July 2005. <http://www.guardian.co.uk/education/2005/jul/07/schools.uk>

¹⁴⁸ The Economic Effects of Terrorism on London – Experiences of Firms in London's Business Community, *The London Chamber of Commerce*, August 2005. <http://www.londonchamber.co.uk/docimages/754.pdf>

courier for our documents. Obviously, this will increase our costs.” These costs must be met either by the employer or employee.¹⁴⁹

In addition, other businesses including transport operators (e.g., British airways) and shops also saw a short-term impact on their businesses. For instance, Harrods, observed decreases in the number of visitors to its stores from outside London.¹⁵⁰

Government: Not only did the British government, including local and national government have to respond to the financial implications of the attacks, including costs of the emergency services, but in addition there were also those costs stemming from victim compensation. As of July 2010, five years after the attacks, compensation payments had reached £11 million.¹⁵¹ There were also financial implications relating to the costs of a coroner’s inquest which has cost approximately £4.6 million.¹⁵²

Not restricted to having an economic impact, the 2005 attacks also had an impact on the British political system. As highlighted by Haverig, following the attacks the British government placed greater emphasis on “community cohesion”.¹⁵³ Community cohesion is associated with “elements of a shared sense of belonging, unity and respect for liberal democratic values”.¹⁵⁴ This community cohesion strategy was also supported by the governments’ counter terrorism strategy, which focused on preventing extremism within the UK. Thus, the London attacks had important social implications in terms of its political impact within the UK.

Furthermore, the attacks in London also saw the development of legal approaches to countering terrorism, with the introduction of the 2006 UK Anti-Terrorism Act. As reported by some, rather than tackling terror in the UK, for some, the political discourse surrounding the war on terror has led Muslims to be labelled as the “enemy within”, and are therefore the focus of the UK’s security agenda, and are a “suspect community”. This may result in the security agenda being undermined, rather than strengthened.¹⁵⁵ This example of increasing legislation and its effect on a community serves to demonstrate that a man-made crisis such as an act of terror can have long-term social impacts.

This review of documents related to the 7th July 2005 terror attacks in London suggest that four groups were affected; citizens, critical infrastructure, business and the government. Different to the other crises assessed in this chapter is the notion of intent, where the attacks in London served to further affect citizens than those directly caught up in the crisis.

Table 17: Group impacts of the 2005 terror attacks in the UK

¹⁴⁹ Ibid., p. 14.

¹⁵⁰ Ibid., p. 19.

¹⁵¹ “£11m Compensation for 7/7 Victims”, *BBC*, 2 July 2010. <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/10491295>.

¹⁵² “Inquest Into 7/7 Cost £4.6 Million”, *The Huffington Post UK*, 19 January 2012.

http://www.huffingtonpost.co.uk/2012/01/19/77-bombings-inquest-into-london-attacks-cost-46-million_n_1216344.html.

¹⁵³ Haverig, Anika, “Managing Integration: German and British Policy Responses to the ‘Threat from Within’ Post-2001”, *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, Vol. 14, No. 2, 2013, pp. 345–362.

¹⁵⁴ Ibid., p. 350.

¹⁵⁵ Pantazis, Christina, and Simon Pemberton, “From the ‘Old’ to the ‘New’ Suspect Community Examining the Impacts of Recent UK Counter-Terrorist Legislation”, *British Journal of Criminology*, Vol. 49, No. 5, September 1, 2009, pp. 646–666.

Citizens	Critical infrastructure	Business	Government
Physically	Transportation	Local business	Local
Psychologically	Authorities	Tourism	National
Sense of community	Communication		
	Schools		

3.7 CONCLUSION

The purpose of this chapter has been to identify “who” is impacted by typical, high-impact crises, including: floods, extreme temperature, storms, wildfires, earthquakes and man-made. This analysis of “who” was impacted has shed some light on the social impact of different types of crises. Partners assessed “who” was impacted by different types of crises by considering a European case study for each form of typical crisis identified in Chapter 2 of this report. Each of the six case studies were selected based on them having a high impact as identified during the mapping exercise in Chapter 2.

In each of the six case studies that were assessed, similar findings were found with regard to the different groups that were impacted. In all six case studies citizens, critical infrastructure and the government were affected in the immediate aftermath of the crisis. In addition, in five out of the six crises (Flood, extreme temperature, wildfire, earthquake and man-made) there was evidence to suggest that different types of business had also been affected. This was not found with regard to the case study used to assess storms. However, it is highly unlikely that the amount of damage suffered by Cyclone Xynthia did not result in some form of physical or social impact upon businesses as was experienced by citizens and critical infrastructure.

When considering whether different types of disasters (socially) affect different groups, evidence suggests that in typical crises facing Europe, those groups that are affected are likely to be similar, the primary difference is the extent of the impact on different groups, which is highly dependent on the scale of the crisis.

In addition, as revealed in several of the case studies, notably floods, extreme temperatures and storms, it is important to note that the impact of the different types of crises on different groups should not be regarded in isolation, rather the potential impact of a crisis on one group can also impact other groups (e.g., the impact on loss of power, not only affects the critical infrastructure of a society, but in addition has the capacity to affect other groups including citizens, business and government). Thus, it is important to consider the inter-dependencies between different groups when faced with a crisis.

The following table provides further information as to the similarities and differences across the different types of crises (based on the case studies assessed in this chapter) and their impacts on groups, illustrating, that whilst the crises assessed in this chapter have similar impacts at the macro level, the impact of the crisis on the group at the micro-level differs across different types of crises:

Table 18: Groups impacts of typical crises based on selected case studies

Citizens			
Physically	Psychologically	Citizens’ property	Sense of community
Flood	Flood	Flood	Flood
Extreme temperature	Earthquake	Storm	Man-made

Storm	Man-made	Earthquake				
Wildfire						
Earthquake						
Man-made						
Critical infrastructure						
Transport	Power	Water	Agriculture	Authorities	Schools	Communication
Flood	Flood	Flood	Flood	Flood	Earthquake	Man-made
Extreme temperature	Extreme temperature	Extreme temperature	Extreme temperature	Storm	Man-made	
Storm	Storm	Earthquake	Wildfire	Wildfire		
Earthquake	Earthquake		Earthquake	Man-made		
Man-made						
Business						
Local business		Heritage		Tourism		Insurance companies
Flood		Flood		Flood		Flood
Extreme temperature		Wildfire		Extreme temperature*		
Wildfire		Earthquake		Wildfire		
Earthquake				Man-made		
Man-made						
Government						
Local		National			European Union	
Flood		Flood			Wildfire	
Extreme temperature		Extreme temperature			Man-made	
Storm		Wildfire				
Wildfire		Earthquake				
Earthquake		Man-made				
Man-made						

(* Positive effect)

It is important to note that whilst this chapter has, to an extent, revealed the types of groups impacted by different types of crises, it is limited in its identification of the extent of the impact as a result of the limitation of the availability of some documents as well as the case studies assessed. The results, do however, provide a useful guide for understanding the different stakeholders impacted by different types of crises, and therefore enables the COSMIC consortium to consider the various groups that may have communication needs in a crisis.

Chapter 4: Crises and the security of the citizen

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4 CRISES AND THE SECURITY OF THE CITIZEN

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Crises affect the security of the citizen in multiple ways, which are in most cases hard to separate with regard to a causal link of the type: *crisis* → *effects*. It is widely accepted that almost all the societal impact effects summarised in Table 1 of Chapter 1 can be attributed to one of the main types of crises examined in chapter 2, i.e. flood, extreme temperature, storm, wildfire, earthquake and man-made disaster. The higher the scale of the crisis, the wider the implications and the more likely it is for the effects described in Table 1 to be experienced by the society. This is exemplified in cases of cascading effects (described in Chapter 3) of crises, where one type may create another. Typical cases are extreme temperatures resulting in forest fires and these leading to floods in a later rainy season.

Although COSMIC does not concentrate on climate change as such, we cannot oversee the fact that a widely accepted causal chain of disasters owes its origin in it. In fact Objective 5 of the EU Internal Security Strategy¹⁵⁶ states that “the EU is exposed to an array of potential crises and disasters, such as those associated with climate change and those caused by ...”, thus endorsing climate change as a cause of crises. The resulting storms, floods, droughts, heat waves (induced forest fires) and cold waves ultimately affect humans and animals with diseases and loss of life. The social cost of this change can be significant. A recent Communication by the Commission (2013)¹⁵⁷ states that if no adaptation measures are taken, an additional 26000 deaths/year from heat are expected by 2020 and this will rise to 89000 by 2050. It is remarkable that although the World Health Organisation (WHO) suggests that initiatives and actions¹⁵⁸ should be taken to address the health consequences of climate change, the UN Convention relating to the Status of Refugees (CRSR) does not recognise those who became so due to such a cause.

As COSMIC concerns social media use during crises, it is important to examine the behaviour of the citizens-users during such events. This is determined by the effects crises have on citizens and the ways these effects are treated by organised forms of society, themselves also potential users of social media. To this end, in this chapter we examine typical crises from the point of view of their effects on citizens, using illustrative cases. Subsequently, we refer to the mechanisms of the organised society in protecting citizens from crises both at the level of field relief and rescue operations and at the level of policy and legislation.

4.2 TYPICAL CRISES AND THE SECURITY OF THE CITIZEN

In what follows we shall illustrate these points with examples showing the effects of typical types of crisis on the security of citizens.

¹⁵⁶ European Commission, Brussels, “The EU Internal Security Strategy in Action: Five steps towards a more secure Europe”, COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND THE COUNCIL, COM(2010) 673 final, Brussels 22.11.2010

¹⁵⁷ European Commission, Brussels, “An EU Strategy on adaptation to climate change”, COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS, Brussels, 16.4.2013

¹⁵⁸ World Health Organisation, Europe, “Improving Public Health Responses To Extreme Weather/Heat-Waves, EuroHEAT”, Meeting Report, Bonn, Germany, March, 2007

4.2.1 Flood

Catastrophic floods endanger lives and cause human and financial losses. In addition to economic and social damage, severe environmental consequences, ranging from toxic chemicals being released, when installations are inundated, to wetland areas being destroyed are possible. Aided by climate change, a higher flood risk is predicted in Europe, as remarked in the accompanying annex of a recent Communication by the Commission (2013)¹⁵⁹. The same source states that “...of all types of natural disasters, flooding and storm events result in the greatest economic losses compared with other types of disasters in the EU (25% by flooding and 32% by storms). The most significant flooding events in terms of economic losses were in the UK in the summer of 2007 (4 billion), in Switzerland, Austria and Germany in 2005 (2.8 billion) and in France in December 2003 (1.6 billion).”

Already in the past 20 years, 953 disasters killed nearly 88,671 people in Europe, affected more than 29 million others and caused a total of 250 EUR billion of economic losses. The Communication warns that the existing estimates of loss linked to natural hazards are to be considered low estimates because many impacts, such as loss of human lives, cultural heritage, and ecosystem services, are difficult to value and monetise, and thus are either omitted or only poorly reflected in loss estimates.

Between 1998 and 2009, Europe suffered over 213 major damaging floods¹⁶⁰, including the catastrophic events along the Danube and Elbe rivers (summer 2002). Severe floods in 2005 further reinforced the need for concerted action. Between 1998 and 2009, floods in Europe have caused the displacement of about half a million people and at least €52 billion in insured economic losses¹⁶¹. People’s security is directly affected by loss of life, property, home base and the possible destruction of societal structures. A characteristic narrative from the effects of floods in Southern Pakistan is quoted below.

Floods in Sindh, Southern Pakistan, 2011¹⁶²

A survey by the Economic Ministry (2011) after the 2011 floods illustrated that the damage to crops, livestock, poultry and fisheries was to the tune of US\$1,840.3 million. Sindh suffered the brunt of this loss with 94 per cent of the total damage. In the flood-affected villages where I did fieldwork, it was obvious that families and communities were still reeling from the loss of livelihoods and food consumption. In two or three villages, community members also showed me areas where even one year after the floods, fields were still flooded and planting a new crop was not possible. At the same time, however, all interviewees acknowledged that they were able to maintain a level of subsistence; during their time in the relief camps (whether government or CSO/NGO-run) they received regular supplies of food and rations. However, since coming back to their homes regular food supply seemed to be more of a concern.

4.2.2 Extreme temperature

According to the European Environment Agency¹⁶¹ the average temperature over land in Europe in the last decade was 1.3 °C warmer than the pre-industrial level; this makes it the

¹⁵⁹ European Commission, Brussels, “An EU Strategy on adaptation to climate change”, COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS, Impact Assessment - Part 2, Brussels, 16.4.2013

¹⁶⁰ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/water/flood_risk/index.htm

¹⁶¹ European Environment Agency (EEA), <http://www.eea.europa.eu/highlights/natural-hazards-and-technological-accidents>

¹⁶² Siddiqi A., “The Emerging Social Contract: State–Citizen Interaction after the Floods of 2010 and 2011 in Southern Sindh, Pakistan”, IDS Bulletin, Vol. 44, No. 3, May 2013.

warmest decade on record. Exceptional melting in the Greenland ice sheet was recorded in the summer of 2012 and the Arctic sea ice extent and volume have been decreasing much faster than projected.

As remarked by EuroHEAT¹⁶³, a DG SANCO co-funded project, the health impacts of hot weather and heat-waves depend upon the level of exposure (frequency, intensity and duration) to heat; the size of the exposed population; the characteristics of the population (susceptibility); and the prevention measures in place. Geographical and temporal variations of the relationship between daily temperature and the effects on health have been well-documented. As mentioned in the same report, the Assessment and Prevention of Acute Health Effects of Weather Conditions in Europe (PHEWE) project, by using the same methodology across 15 European cities, estimated that for every 1°C increase in apparent temperature above a threshold for a given location/population, the increase in mortality would be about 2% (95% Confidence Interval: 0.06-3.64) in northern continental cities and about 3% (95% CI: 0.60-5.72) in the Mediterranean cities. As will be discussed in section 4.3.3.2, the thresholds are typically population and location specific. The strength of the relationship between daily outdoor temperature and health outcomes differs between countries, between cities, and even in the same location from one year to the next. For example, the estimated increase in mortality per 1 °C increase in apparent temperature was 1.5% in Barcelona and more than 5% increase in Athens and Rome.

The following graph is indicative of the situation. The vertical lines show the percentage increase in mortality during different characteristics of heat waves, namely long duration (orange), long duration and high intensity (black) and an average of all heat waves (green). For example, the graph shows that the increase in mortality in Athens due to all heat waves is between an estimated 18-26%, while the increase in Milan for all heat waves is between 28-38%.

Figure 19: Effect of heat-waves with different characteristics on total mortality among people aged 65+.¹⁶³

¹⁶³ World Health Organisation, “Improving Public Health Responses to Extreme Weather/Heat-Waves – EuroHEAT”, Meeting Report, Bonn, Germany, March 2007

As the most recent Communication by the EC states¹⁵⁹ “...the impact of heat waves is particularly strong in cities and towns because of the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect¹⁶⁴. Cities in northern Europe are potentially as much exposed to the human health effects of heat waves as are cities in southern Europe, given the different heat thresholds and levels of acclimatisation of local populations. Long heat waves (more than 5 days) have an impact 1.5 to 5 times greater than shorter events. The reduction of ability to work, resulting in a lower productivity e.g. shortening/delaying delivery of products and services will impact European economy. 86.000 net extra deaths per year are projected for EU Member States (high-emissions scenario) with a global mean temperature increase of 3 °C in 2071–2100 relative to 1961–1990.”

The Communication by the Commission (2013) goes further by pointing out that more intense and frequent heat waves will result in decreasing CARNOT efficiency for thermal industrial plants, including electricity production, along with decreasing cooling water supply. These effects will be combined with a need for increased air-conditioning, thus resulting in societal repercussions of unknown magnitude: “...Threats to the energy system might increase regional disparities with the EU with southern countries suffering from i) high electricity import dependency and thus relying on yet non-resilient transmission infrastructure and ii) projected impacts from gradual temperature increase, heat wave and drought frequency further threats to domestic supply aggravating import dependency. Meanwhile, northern countries show a more complex and uncertain picture of potential gains and losses for energy supply and security.”

4.2.2.1 Projections

Recent projections by the EEA¹⁶⁵ show that due to climatic change heat waves will likely be more frequent and intense, resulting in a marked increase in heat-attributable deaths, also due to synergistic effects with air pollution, which tends to increase under these conditions (PM₁₀ and ozone). Another side effect is also forest fires, which also have severe health impacts (see section 4.2.4 for details).

The PESETA and PESETA II projects¹⁶⁶ estimate that heat-related mortality in Europe in the 2080s will increase by between 60000 and 165000 (without adaptation and physiological acclimatisation, compared to the present baseline). Cold-related mortality is projected to decrease by between 60 000 and 250 000, which is about the same magnitude as the increase from heat-related mortality^{167, 168}. In the absence of adaptation, these changes would lead to a reduction in human lifespan of up to 3–4 months in 2070–2100.

The CLIMATECOST project¹⁶⁹ estimated an additional 26000 deaths per year from heat by the 2020s, rising to 127 000 deaths per year by the 2080s under a medium to high emission (A1B) scenario, assuming no adaptation. While heat-related mortality is projected to increase

¹⁶⁴ “Closed isotherms indicating an area of the surface that is relatively warm; most commonly associated with areas of human disturbance such as towns and cities.”, definition from the Meteorological Glossary of the American Meteorological Society, at http://glossary.ametsoc.org/wiki/Urban_heat_island

¹⁶⁵ <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/heat-and-health-1/assessment>

¹⁶⁶ <http://peseta.jrc.ec.europa.eu>

¹⁶⁷ Ciscar J., C., et al., “Physical and economic consequences of climate change in Europe”, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 108, Nr. 7 (January 31, 2011): 2678–2683, doi:10.1073/pnas.1011612108

¹⁶⁸ Huang C. et al., “Projecting future heat-related mortality under climate change scenarios: A systematic review”, *Environmental Health Perspectives* 119, Nr. 12 (August 4, 2011): 16811690, doi:10.1289/ehp.1103456.

¹⁶⁹ http://cordis.europa.eu/search/index.cfm?fuseaction=proj.document&PJ_RCIN=10373758

across Europe, impacts would be highest in southern Europe. Under an E1 scenario, broadly equivalent with stabilising global mean temperature increase at 2 °C above pre-industrial levels, impacts are reduced significantly, with an estimated 69000 deaths per year by the 2080s. With acclimatisation, the estimated number of heat-related deaths declines substantially to 13000 per year in the 2020s, and 40000 per year in the 2080s under the A1B scenario; for the E1 scenario it is down to 18000 per year in the 2080s. Both projects (PESETA II and CLIMATECOST) note that these figures are subject to considerable uncertainties.

4.2.2.2 Two cases in Europe

The summer of 2003 was probably the hottest in Europe among the previous 500 years with unusually large numbers of heat-related deaths reported in France, Germany and Italy. According to the Nature journal it is very likely that the heat wave was human induced by greenhouse gases. In Eastern Europe the summer of 2010 was exceptionally hot, with an amplitude and spatial extent that exceeded the previous 2003 heat wave¹⁷⁰. These two heat waves broke the seasonal temperature records over approximately half of Europe.

Summer 2003 in Europe¹⁷¹

*“... Maintained by a succession of stationary weather systems over the Northern Atlantic and Central Europe, conditions of excessive heat and drought would persist for almost eight months. By summer’s end, the heat wave had reduced ancient rivers to non-navigable streams, consumed in fire an area larger than some European nations, and claimed more lives than the United States lost in a decade of warfare in Vietnam. **The EU estimated that more than 70000 citizens of 12 countries died from heat-induced illnesses over a four-month period in the summer of 2003. This number represents more fatalities than have resulted from any EU or American conflict since World War II.**”*

“... In the months following the heat wave, post-event assessments would document massive social, economic, and environmental impacts. By the end of the summer, more than 25,000 fires had consumed a total of 647,069 hectares across Portugal, Spain, France, Italy, Austria, Finland, Denmark, and Ireland, an area roughly equivalent to that of Luxembourg. Portugal alone would lose an estimated 10% of its total forestland. Agricultural losses were unprecedented. The excessive heat and drought reduced fodder harvests in France by an estimated 60% and by at least 30% in neighboring countries. One of the most productive agricultural regions in Italy reported a 40 to 50% drop in olive production and a 40 to 100% reduction of the peach, apricot, and grape yields, with the costs of produce on the shelf in Britain rising by 40%. The limited evidence available suggests the impact of the heat on livestock was substantial; it was reported that 80,000 chickens perished on a single farm in England. Overall, economic losses from the heat wave across Europe were estimated to be about \$13 billion, a figure that is certain to underestimate the true costs.”

Summer of 2010¹⁷⁰

“...During the summer 2010, mean temperatures were between 4 and 8°C above normal during July and the two first weeks of August in Western Russia and Eastern Europe. It was the most extreme heat wave in the instrumental record of 1880-present for that region. The extreme heat and the absence of rain led to the worst drought conditions in more than 100 years and also to the worst wildfires in decades. Munich Re estimated 56,000 people died from the effects of this heat wave. This heat wave also led indirectly to an increase in the price of staple goods like pasta and bread all over Europe because Russia’s wheat crops failed.”

¹⁷⁰ European Commission, Brussels, “An EU Strategy on adaptation to climate change”, COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS, Impact Assessment - Part 2, Brussels, 16.4.2013

¹⁷¹ Stone B., Jr., “The City and the Coming Climate”, Cambridge University Press, 2012

4.2.3 Storm

Severe weather conditions causing storms (hurricanes, typhoons, tropical cyclones etc.) can have a devastating effect on communities. Hurricanes may last as long as a month and although they travel very slowly wind speeds can reach over 120 km/h (75 mph). The intense winds of tropical storms can destroy whole communities, buildings and communication networks. As well as their own destructive energy, the winds generate abnormally high waves and tidal surges. Sometimes the most destructive elements of a storm are the subsequent high seas and flooding. The result is societal disruption manifested as evacuation, loss of life for those in the affected vicinity, destruction of property, homelessness, subsequent diseases due to unhygienic conditions and hard to obtain medical help, as well as social tensions and poor economic conditions due to the scarcity of goods such as petrol (transport) and food.

Figure 20: The devastating tropical storm that hit Northern Mindanao in the Philippines in December 2011 affected some 600,000 people in 13 provinces, damaging bridges, roads and destroying houses. (Credit: UNICEF/J. Maitem)

The following case is indicative of the societal effects of storms, both in the short and in the long term, and the efforts to mitigate them.

Hurricane Katrina (2005)¹⁷²

Katrina was a category 4 storm, with surges reaching over 6m in height. New Orleans was one of the worst affected areas. Being below sea level, the protective levee defences were unable to cope with the strength of Katrina and water flooded into the city. Despite an evacuation order, many of the poorest people remained and sought refuge in the Superdome stadium. Conditions became unhygienic with a shortage of food and water. Looting was commonplace throughout the city. Tension was high and many felt vulnerable and unsafe. 1 million people were made homeless and about 1200 were drowned in the floods. Oil facilities were damaged and as a result petrol prices rose throughout the US.

There was much criticism of the authorities for their handling of the disaster. Although many were evacuated, the process was slow and the poorest and most vulnerable were left behind. \$50 billion in aid was given by the government. The National Guard was mobilised to restore and maintain law and order in what became a hostile and unsafe living environment.

4.2.4 Wildfire

Wildfires or forest fires release pollutant biomass smoke in the atmosphere, with obvious effects on human health. Effects range from small eye, nose or throat irritation to persistent cardio-pulmonary conditions or even premature death in rare cases. Smoke thus produced can

¹⁷² http://www.bbc.co.uk/schools/gcsebitesize/geography/weather_climate/weather_human_activity_rev4.shtml

enter the body via inhalation, ingestion and dermal absorption. A recent study¹⁷³ in which the authors investigated the short-term effects of forest fires on non-accidental mortality in the population of Athens, Greece, during 1998-2004 shows an immediate effect on mortality, especially if the fire occurs near a densely populated area. In particular, "... small fires do not have an effect on mortality. Medium sized fires are associated with an increase of 4.9% (95% CI 0.3% to 9.6%) in the daily total number of deaths, 6.0% (95% CI -0.3% to 12.6%) in the number of cardiovascular deaths and 16.2% (95% CI 1.3% to 33.4%) in the number of respiratory deaths. Cardiovascular effects are larger in those aged under 75 years, while respiratory effects are larger in older people. The corresponding effects of the one large fire are: 49.7% (95% CI 37.2% to 63.4%), 60.6% (95% CI 43.1% to 80.3%) and 92.0% (95% CI 47.5% to 150.0%). These effects cannot be completely explained by an increase in ambient particle concentrations."

Disturbance of the ecosystem in the neighbouring areas has negative effects on animals, plantation and crops by affecting the fertility of the soil. Water bodies can also be affected by the growth of bacteria and pathogens. Indirect effects can be caused by the reduced visibility in nearby areas and roads due to smoke rising, frequently resulting in traffic accidents.

As a consequence of the above, the security of the citizen is affected either directly, if close to the fire, where health effects, loss of property and loss of life are possible consequences, or indirectly by the subsequent degradation of his wider living environment.

The following description, taken from the civil protection site of the European Commission, illustrates the functioning of the Community Mechanism for Civil Protection and its [Monitoring and Information Centre \(MIC\)](#) (also see description under section 4.2).

Forest fires in Greece (2007)¹⁷⁴

In 2007 Greece experienced the worst year on record for forest fires. Extremely hot and dry weather conditions, combined with strong winds led to a disastrous upsurge of forest fires and wildfires. This year Greece requested assistance 4 times through the Mechanism's Information Centre (MIC) to face during the months of June, July and August. The total burnt area in 2007 amounts to 268 834 hectares, of which 180 000 burnt between the 24 and 30 August 2007. The first request for assistance to the [Monitoring and Information Centre \(MIC\)](#) came on the 27 June 2007. By then, there were already some 120 fires in the country, the most affected areas being the Regions of Thessaly, Sterea, Attica and the Peloponnese. By 2 July 2007 the forest fires were brought under control and the request for assistance was closed.

Later fires affected the environs of Parnitha and Pilion Mountains, prompting a second request for assistance on 5 July. These fires had been totally extinguished by 7 July.

The MIC received the third request for assistance from Greece on 18 July 2007 with fires burning away in Korinthos, Patras and Mani (in the Peloponnese) as well as Kithira Island and Kefalonia Island. On 1 August 2007, Greece informed the MIC that no further European assistance is required and closed the emergency. The European Commission's [Joint Research Centre \(JRC\)](#) reported that the total burned area mapped in Greece until the 31 July 2007 was 80 970 hectares. From this area 11 753 hectares were on NATURA 2000 sites. However, Greece had yet to come through its fourth request for assistance, which was the most dramatic one to date in terms of loss of human lives and damage. Greece requested assistance on 24 August 2007, when more than a 100 forest fires. Weather conditions fanned the fires to a reported maximum of 124. Some 64 people died, including 6 seasonal fire-fighters. The fires affected large areas of Greece, ranging from the island of Evia north of Athens to the Peloponnese in the south. Greece also declared a state of emergency.

¹⁷³ Analitis A., Georgiadis I., Katsouyanni K., "Forest Fires Are Associated with Elevated Mortality in a Dense Urban Setting", *Occupational and Environmental Medicine* 69, Nr. 3 (January 3, 2012): 158–162, doi:10.1136/oem.2010.064238

¹⁷⁴ From the reporting of the European Civil Protection, http://ec.europa.eu/echo/civil_protection/civil/forestfires_el_2007.htm

4.2.5 Earthquake

According to European Commission report¹⁷⁵, earthquakes are by far the most deadly natural disasters in the world having killed 340000 people since 1975. Since the beginning of this century, earthquakes have caused about 20000 deaths per year. A third of the world's population continue to live in areas considered to be "at risk". In the European Union, almost 5000 people have died as a result of earthquakes. In 1980, an earthquake in southern Italy, killed more than 4000 people and left 250000 homeless. More recently, in 1995, earthquakes in the Greek region of Grevena (1995) and in Assisi (1997) caused extensive damage. Most recently, the L'Aquila earthquake in Italy lead to 295 fatalities and considerable physical damage (for details see, Chapter 2, Table 4). The European Commission's report indicates that damage from earthquakes seems greater today than it used to be in the past for two reasons: "First of all, countries are more densely populated, including those at risk. Secondly, there is new industrial infrastructure that may be vulnerable in the event of an earthquake: gas and oil pipelines, dams, chemical factories and so on."

As the US Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA)¹⁷⁶ reports, harm or losses likely to result from exposure to earthquakes are usually measured in terms of expected casualties (fatalities and injuries), direct economic losses (repair and replacement costs), and indirect economic losses (income lost during downtime resulting from damage to private property or public infrastructure). Other measures include effects such as probable volumes and durations of utility outages and displaced households, and amounts of debris likely to be generated. Earthquake casualties are not limited by the number of people present in stricken areas; cascade effects may be present. The radioactive contamination from Fukushima, for example, is likely to affect a much larger population, as the spill may reach the Pacific Ocean¹⁷⁷. Losses are constrained by the quantity and value of buildings, infrastructure, and other property in the affected areas. Seismic risk increases as earthquake-prone regions become more densely populated and urbanised.

Factors influencing the effects of an earthquake depend on its location (epicentre), its severity, the level of development of the affected area (richer areas are more likely to have resources and more resilient infrastructure), the density of the population, the skill and means of the rescue teams and the timing of the event (referring to time-of-day and time-of-year, affecting the location of people and the weather conditions correspondingly).

Apart from the immediate effects on humans, such as loss of life and destruction of infrastructure, longer term impacts are of a serious nature, depending on the severity and pattern of the shock and the aftershocks. The following table summarises the short and long term impacts of earthquakes.

Table 19. Impacts of earthquakes on human life (reproduced from a BBC geography course¹⁷⁸)

	Social impacts	Economic impacts	Environmental impacts
Short-term (immediate) impacts	People may be killed or injured. Homes may be destroyed. Transport and	Shops and business may be destroyed. Looting may take place. The damage to	The built landscape may be destroyed. Fires can spread due to gas pipe explosions. Fires can

¹⁷⁵ <http://ec.europa.eu/research/leaflets/disasters/en/earthqu.html>

¹⁷⁶ <http://www.fema.gov/earthquake/your-earthquake-risk>

¹⁷⁷ International Business Times, 11/07/2013, <http://www.ibtimes.com/fukushima-plant-probably-leaking-contaminated-water-pacific-ocean-japans-nuclear-regulator-1341367>

¹⁷⁸ http://www.bbc.co.uk/schools/gcsebitesize/geography/natural_hazards/earthquakes_rev3.shtml

	Social impacts	Economic impacts	Environmental impacts
	communication links may be disrupted. Water pipes may burst and water supplies may be contaminated.	transport and communication links can make trade difficult.	damage areas of woodland. Landslides may occur. Tsunamis may cause flooding in coastal areas.
Long-term impacts	Disease may spread. People may have to be re-housed, sometimes in refugee camps.	The cost of rebuilding a settlement is high. Investment in the area may be focused only on repairing the damage caused by the earthquake. Income could be lost.	Important natural and human landmarks may be lost.

The following is a short factual description of the effects of the earthquake which hit Japan on 11 March 2011, with devastating effects even leading to a nuclear accident.

<p>The impact of Japan earthquake of 11 March 2011¹⁷⁹</p> <p><i>DEATH TOLL: A total of 12431 people were confirmed dead by Japan's National Police Agency, while 15153 were missing.</i></p> <p><i>NUMBER OF PEOPLE EVACUATED: More than 163000 people were in shelters around the country following evacuation, according to the National Police Agency. The government has set up an evacuation area around Tokyo Electric Power Co's quake-stricken nuclear plant in Fukushima 150 miles north of Tokyo, with a 12-mile radius.</i></p> <p><i>HOUSEHOLDS WITHOUT ELECTRICITY: A total of 164059 households in the north were without electricity, according to Tohoku Electric Power Co and at least 170000 households in eight prefectures were without running water, according to the Health Ministry.</i></p> <p><i>NUMBER OF BUILDINGS DAMAGED: At least 46,027 buildings were destroyed, washed away or burnt down, according to the National Police Agency of Japan.</i></p> <p><i>IMPACT ON ECONOMY: The government estimated damage from the earthquake and tsunami at 16-25 trillion ye, making it the world's costliest natural disaster.</i></p> <p><i>NUMBER OF COUNTRIES OFFERING AID: According to the Foreign Ministry, 134 countries and 39 international organisations have offered assistance.</i></p>

4.2.6 Man-made disasters

Humans and their activities can be causes of disasters. These range from hazardous materials emergencies such as chemical spills leading to groundwater contamination, to common workplace fires potentially leading to significant property damage and loss of life.

Communities are also vulnerable to threats posed by terrorist groups who use violence against both people and property. High-risk targets include military and civilian government facilities, international airports, large cities and high-profile landmarks. Another form, cyber-terrorism involves attacks against computers and networks done to intimidate or coerce a government or its people for political or social objectives.

4.2.6.1 Technological and accidental hazards

The effects of this category of man-made (potential) disasters are summarised by the US Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA)¹⁸⁰ under the following categories.

¹⁷⁹ The Telegraph, 06 April 2011, <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/asia/japan/8431209/Japan-earthquake-and-tsunami-list-of-impacts-of-disaster.html>

¹⁸⁰ <http://www.ready.gov/technological-accidental-hazards>

- ◆ **Blackout** (power outage) – a condition which can happen anywhere without warning (in many cases due to bad weather) and, if extensive in time or affected area, can cause loss of life, property or both. This is because vital support equipment at home or other installations depend on electrical power (heating, cooling, lighting). In many cases, impact on citizens is caused by consequential criminal action by organised gangs who take advantage of those vulnerable. The biggest Blackout in U.S. history occurred on August 14, 2003, leaving roughly 50 million people without power.
- ◆ **Hazardous material incidents** – caused by the widely spread and improper use of chemical substances. Hazardous materials in various forms can cause death, serious injury, long-lasting health effects and damage to buildings, homes and other property. Many products containing hazardous chemicals are shipped (via road, railway, waterways and pipelines), used and stored in homes routinely. They come in the form of explosives, flammable and combustible substances, poisons and radioactive materials, which most often happen to be improperly released as a result of transportation accidents or chemical accidents in plants. The infamous Bhopal disaster at the Union Carbide India Limited (UCIL) pesticide plant in Bhopal, is widely considered as being the world's worst industrial disaster, with an official immediate death toll of 2259 many more later on. A government affidavit in 2006 stated the leak caused over 500000 injuries including approximately 3900 severely and permanently disabling injuries.
- ◆ **Nuclear power plants** – are closely monitored facilities all over the world but accidents have happened. The potential danger from such an accident is exposure to radiation from released radioactive material into the environment, usually characterised by a plume (cloud-like formation) of radioactive gases and particles. Major hazards to humans in the vicinity of the plume are radiation exposure to the body from the cloud and particles deposited on the ground, and inhalation and/or ingestion of radioactive materials. The longer a person is exposed to radiation, the greater the effect, leading to serious illness, immediate death or to terminal illnesses (usually cancer) a few years after the exposure incident.

The Seveso disaster, Italy 1976^{181, 182}

Around midday on Saturday 10 July 1976, an explosion occurred in a TCP (2,4,5-trichlorophenol) reactor of the ICMESA chemical plant on the outskirts of Meda, a small town about 20 kilometres north of Milan, Italy. A toxic cloud containing TCDD (2,3,7,8-tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin), then widely believed to be one of the most toxic man-made chemicals, was accidentally released into the atmosphere. The dioxin cloud contaminated a densely populated area about six kilometres long and one kilometre wide, lying downwind from the site. This event became internationally known as the Seveso disaster, after the name of a neighbouring municipality that was most severely affected. Eleven communities in the rolling countryside between Milan and Lake Como were directly involved in the toxic release and its aftermath.

Despite their exposure to high levels of dioxin, it was a few days before people began to feel the effects: nausea, blurred vision, skin lesions and the development of severe chloracne, particularly among children. As a result of the slow development of symptoms, the area around Seveso was not immediately evacuated. Research into the long-term health effects of the Seveso disaster is ongoing. One study from 2008 found that babies born to women living in the contaminated area at the time of the accident were about six times more likely to have altered thyroid function than other babies. Additionally, a 2009 report found an increase in breast and lymphatic cancers in the area.

The Seveso disaster had a particularly traumatic effect on exposed local populations because its seriousness was recognized only gradually. The community was divided by rancorous conflicts. People in other countries also experienced much heightened concern about industrial risks and the need for tighter regulation of hazardous chemical installations. In these respects Seveso resembled Bhopal (1984) and Chernobyl (1986), which have both come to be regarded as international symbols of industrial pathology.

¹⁸¹ UN University, <http://archive.unu.edu/unupress/unupbooks/uu211e/uu211e09.htm>

¹⁸² <http://greenliving.about.com/od/greenprograms/a/Seveso-TCDD.htm>

One consequence of the Seveso disaster was the impulse that it gave to the creation of the European Community's Seveso Directives, regulating industrial plants.

4.2.6.2 Terrorist acts

Following the categorisation by the US Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA)¹⁸³, we distinguish between six types of terrorist acts:

Explosions – The most common type of terrorist act. It is used to damage and destroy human life and damage financial, political, social, and religious institutions. Devastating acts, such as the terrorist attacks on the Oklahoma City US, the 09/11 World Trade Center attack, the London bombings of 2005 and many others are prominent examples.

Biological threats – Realised as deliberate releases of germs or other biological substances to harm humans and animals. Such agents can be dispersed by spraying them into the air, by infecting animals that carry the disease to humans, by contaminating food and water or via other infected persons for diseases such as smallpox, plague, and the Lassa viruses. Examples of such threats are abundant throughout history, for example during the 6th century BC¹⁸⁴, the Assyrians poisoned enemy wells with a fungus that would render them delirious.

Chemical threats – Can be released by bombs or sprayed from aircraft, boats and vehicles. They can have an immediate effect (a few seconds to a few minutes) or a delayed effect (2 to 48 hours). While potentially lethal, chemical agents are difficult to deliver in lethal concentrations. Outdoors, the agents often dissipate rapidly. In addition, chemical agents also are difficult to produce.

Cyber attacks – A cyber-attack can be defined as a deliberate action to exploit a computer system (including networks).¹⁸⁵ The spectrum of cyber risks is wide; threats, some more serious and sophisticated than others, can have wide-ranging effects, from identity theft to system infiltration or breach of access, on the individual, communal, organisational, and national level. These risks include national security risks, disruption of transportation, power, and other services via large scale cyber incidents, compromised networks of organisations, and loss of personal information due to attacks on personal computing devices.

Nuclear blasts – They are possible even via a small portable nuclear device transported by an individual. All nuclear devices cause deadly effects when exploded, including blinding light, intense heat (thermal radiation), initial nuclear radiation, blast, fires started by the heat pulse and secondary fires caused by the destruction.

Radiological Dispersion Devices (RDD) – Often called “dirty nuke” or “dirty bomb” combine a conventional explosive device with radioactive material. Such material can be easily obtained as it can be widely used in medicine, agriculture, industry and research. The size of the affected area and the level of destruction caused by an RDD would depend on the sophistication and size of the conventional bomb, the type of radioactive material used, the quality and quantity of the radioactive material, and the local meteorological conditions - primarily wind and precipitation. The primary purpose of such attacks is to cause psychological fear and economic disruption, while some devices could cause fatalities from exposure to radioactive materials. Depending on the speed at which the area of the RDD detonation is evacuated or how successful people are at finding local shelter, the number of deaths and injuries from an RDD might not be substantially greater than from a conventional explosion. The area affected could be placed off-limits to the public for several months during cleanup efforts.

¹⁸³ <http://www.ready.gov/technological-accidental-hazards>

¹⁸⁴ Mayor A., “Greek Fire, Poison Arrows & Scorpion Bombs: Biological and Chemical Warfare in the Ancient World”, Woodstock, N.Y.: Overlook Duckworth, 2003, ISBN 978-1-58567-348-3

¹⁸⁵ <http://www.techopedia.com/definition/24748/cyberattack>

4.3 GUARANTEEING THE SECURITY OF THE CITIZEN

Emergency situations and crises caused by such situations often create a need for organised action to deliver essential services to the affected population and to reduce the likelihood of increased morbidity, mortality, outbreaks and other ill effects, thereby enhancing the security of the citizen. There are three major actors¹⁸⁶ involved in such societal and civil protection responses: bilateral organisations (governments of individual countries, including their armed forces), multilateral organisations (e.g. UN and European Union agencies involved in relief work) and civil society or non-governmental organisations (CSOs/NGOs).

Besides the three organised forms of societal action mentioned above, which concern us in this section, for reasons of completeness we should also include a “fourth” form of social organisation, usually called “emergent response groups”. These are defined in chapter 5 as “collectives of individuals who use non-routine resources and activities to apply to nonroutine domains and tasks, using non-routine organisational arrangements”. Due to their nature they have no specifically a-priori set mandate, but their contribution can be decisive under crisis conditions. We refer to chapter 5 for a characterisation of their dynamics.

Bilateral organisations are found in every country ranging from security forces such as police and army to purpose-led emergency services such as rescue agencies, medical teams, fire fighting bodies and others. These bodies are regulated by emergency legislation referring to their mandates, their authorisation hierarchy and their means of intervention for the benefit of distressed citizens.

A study¹⁸⁷ made on behalf of the European Commission observes that “... Member States generally appear to have developed quite effective and well-coordinated mechanisms for crisis management (response and recovery), also in regard to specific disaster types. Among other things, this reflects that crisis management and civil protection are areas with a long history and a strong national momentum.”

The study places emphasis on the demands stemming from EU legislation and other international commitments as drivers for an intensified effort and the development of new prevention approaches by the individual states. It also stresses that significant disasters with losses of lives and or economic values over the last decade became a strong impetus for prevention planning, with examples such as:

- ◆ Sweden, where the windstorms in 2003 were the reason for the implementation of new legislation on protection of accidents in 2004
- ◆ France, where the heat wave in 2003 was the driver of the drawing up of a national heat prevention plan
- ◆ Romania, where the implementation of the Water Directive was the driver of the development of risk maps and systematic use of GIS to establish a solid basis for decision-making in the field of both prevention and civil protection.

¹⁸⁶ Muriuki, D., “Contribution of NGOs in Complex Emergencies”, WHO Conference on the Health Aspects of the Tsunami Disaster in Asia, Phuket, Thailand, 4- 6 May 2005

¹⁸⁷ European Commission, DG Environment, “Member States' Approaches towards Prevention Policy - a Critical Analysis”, Final Report, March 2008

- ◆ Portugal, where the experience with forest fires, such as in 2003 and 2005 resulted in a strong focus to limit forest fires, especially when droughts are foreseen to become an increasing problem causing water shortage

Following on the observations of the above study, from the operational point of view, Member States follow a thematic or sectoral management structure for risk planning, usually under the responsibility of a given government department (ministry). Forest fires usually fall within the ministry of agriculture and forestry, flooding management usually belongs to the ministry of environment. The interesting observation here is that prevention planning occurs mainly as thematic initiatives, such as for example heat wave or forest fire prevention plans. As a result of the thematic focus, risk assessment at national level appears to be an isolated thematic exercise with little data sharing to other thematic areas and sectors, thus showing a lack of integration of information or action. A less fragmented and more integrated approach and the consequent efficiency gains would undoubtedly enhance the security of the citizen. This need can possibly be covered by regulation and action at Community level.

4.4 MULTILATERALS

Their trans-national nature makes them particularly suited to cross-border crises as well as crises of unpredictable timing and/or proportions. Their role is supportive to that of bilateral organisations but their contribution can be crucial especially when national resources become too strained to respond and the security of the citizen is adversely affected. In what follows, we examine the role of main such organisations at international level, such as the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs, the EU Community Mechanism for Civil Protection and the Red Cross/Red Crescent movement.

4.4.1 UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA)

OCHA (www.unocha.org) is the part of the United Nations Secretariat responsible for bringing together humanitarian actors to ensure a coherent response to emergencies. Its mission is stated as:

- ◆ to mobilise and coordinate effective and principled humanitarian action in partnership with national and international actors in order to alleviate human suffering in disasters and emergencies.
- ◆ to advocate the rights of people in need.
- ◆ to promote preparedness and prevention.
- ◆ to facilitate sustainable solutions

According to its claim, OCHA "... can quickly deploy specialised humanitarian personnel to support efforts on the ground, particularly in situations where local capacity is overwhelmed, in response to a new or escalating humanitarian crisis."

The functioning of OCHA is realised via supporting the United Nations Resident or Humanitarian Coordinator, who usually is the most senior UN official in the country. OCHA's core functions are coordination, policy, advocacy, information management and humanitarian financing with the aim to build:

- ◆ **Shared situational awareness** for the coordination analysis and communication of needs assessment

- ◆ **Common approaches** among key operational actors on policy dilemmas, such as how best to support vulnerable groups, or whether and how to coordinate with local or international military actors
- ◆ **Common strategy and implementation plans** for resource mobilisation and financing such as for example the "cluster approach" which groups agencies with a shared operational interest, e.g. health, water and sanitation.

The readiness level of OCHA assures deployment of response coordination specialists within hours:

- ◆ The [United Nations Disaster Assessment and Coordination \(UNDAC\) system](#), managed by OCHA, is a standby team of volunteer emergency managers with varied skills, from over 60 developed and developing countries, international agencies and NGOs. Self-contained and fully equipped UNDAC teams can deploy within 24-48 hours of a disaster anywhere in the world.
- ◆ During the search-and-rescue (SAR) phase, the key players are the international urban SAR teams that make up the [International Search and Rescue Advisory Group \(INSARAG\)](#). INSARAG develops and promotes internationally accepted procedures and systems for sustained cooperation between international urban SAR teams operating at a disaster site.

Figure 21: The UN On-Site Operations Coordination Centre (OSOCC) at the entrance to a transit camp near the Tunisia-Libya border. (Credit: OCHA/David Ohana)

At the time of preparation of this report (July 2013), OCHA is coordinating with local authorities and agencies to monitor the northern tip of Sumatra Island after a strong earthquake rocked Indonesia's Aceh province with 2 confirmed dead and some 150 injured¹⁸⁸. This follows the early 2013 roundtable meeting on building resilience to natural disasters and major economic crises¹⁸⁹ among Indonesia and the other members of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations ([ASEAN](#)), where the Deputy Secretary-General Jan Eliasson issued an urgent call to protect the poor and vulnerable during natural disasters and economic crises.

4.4.2 EU: the Community Mechanism for Civil Protection

¹⁸⁸ <http://www.un.org/apps/news/story.asp?NewsID=45326&Cr=Indonesia&Cr1=#.UdaKkdhDVSM>

¹⁸⁹ The impetus for the roundtable was the new study by the UN Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (ESCAP) which found that multiple shocks are occurring with increased frequency and are converging in new ways.

Established by the Council Decisions of [23 October 2001](#) and [18 November 2007](#), the Community Mechanism for Civil Protection facilitates co-operation in civil protection assistance interventions in major emergencies. In accordance with the principle of subsidiarity, it can provide added-value to European civil protection assistance by making support available on request by the affected country. The mission is protection primarily of people, but also of the natural and cultural environment as well as property.

The mechanism acts as a pool of the civil protection capabilities of the 28 Member States as well as four participant states (Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway and FYROM). Operation is supported by the following resources which facilitate adequate preparedness as well as effective response to disasters at a community level.

The [Monitoring and Information Centre \(MIC\)](#) is the operational heart of the Mechanism, managed by the Emergency Response Unit of the Directorate General for Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection (ECHO) of the European Commission and accessible on a 24-hour basis. The MIC is a one-stop-shop acting as a communications hub at headquarters level among participating states, the affected country and dispatched field experts. It not only provides useful and updated information on the actual status of an ongoing emergency, but also plays a co-ordination role by matching offers of assistance put forward by participating states to the needs of the disaster-stricken country. Any country inside or outside the Union affected by a major disaster can make an appeal for assistance through the MIC.

The [Common Emergency and Information System \(CECIS\)](#) is a reliable web-based alert and notification application to facilitate emergency communication among participating states. It provides an integrated platform to send and receive alerts and details of assistance required, to show offers of help and to view the development of the ongoing emergency as they happen in an online logbook.

A [training programme](#) on the co-ordination of civil protection assistance interventions is in place. It aims to achieve compatibility and complementarity among the intervention teams in participating states by enhancing the skills of experts involved and the sharing of best practice. The programme involves training courses, joint exercises and a system of exchange of experts among participating states.

Finally, a collection of critical facilities, personnel and equipment for emergency response has been specified and made available to the Mechanism from one or more Member States on a voluntary basis. Known under the name of "[Civil Protection Modules](#)", specialised emergency response units have been set up to respond more quickly to emergencies. They can be used for interventions both within and outside the EU, are available at short notice (max. 12 hours) and are able to work independently. Examples of European modules include high capacity pumping, advanced medical posts or urban search and rescue.

The policy mandates behind the creation of the modules were the European Council in the Conclusions of June 2005 and the European parliament in its Resolution of January 2005 on the 2004 tsunami disaster in South-Asia, calling for an EU rapid response capability. [Commission Decision 2008/73](#) and [Commission Decision 2010/481](#) lay down rules for the implementation of the modules concept under the Mechanism.

Table 20. Civil Protection Modules of the Community Mechanism

Civil Protection Module	Description	Deployment
1. High capacity pumping	Provision of mobile medium and high capacity pumps for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flooded areas, • firefighting by delivering water. 	Availability for departure in less than 12 hours after acceptance of the offer. Ability to be deployed for a period of up to 21 days.
2. Water purification	Provide drinkable water, from surface water sources. Perform water quality control at the outtake point of the purification equipment.	Availability for departure in less than 12 hours after acceptance of the offer. Ability to be deployed for a period of up to 12 weeks.
3. Medium urban search and rescue	Operate according to the INSARAG guidelines to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search for, locate and rescue victims located under debris, • Provide lifesaving first aid as required, until handover for further treatment 	Operational in the affected country within 32 hours.
4. Heavy urban search and rescue	As above	Operational in the affected country within 48 hours.
5. Aerial forest fire-fighting module using helicopters	Contribute to the extinction of large forest and vegetal fires by performing aerial fire-fighting	Availability for departure maximum 3 hours after acceptance of the offer
6. Aerial forest fire-fighting module using airplanes	As above	As above
7. Advanced medical post	Perform patient profiling (triage) on the site of the disaster. Stabilise the condition of and prepare the patient for transport to the most suitable health facility for final treatment.	Availability for departure in less than 12 hours after acceptance of the offer Operational 1 hour after arrival on site
8. Advanced medical post with surgery	As above, plus: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform damage control surgery 	As above
9. Field hospital	Provide initial and/or follow-up trauma and medical care, according to acknowledged international guidelines for foreign field hospital use, such as those of WHO or the Red Cross.	Availability for departure in less than 7 days after the request Operational 12 hours after arrival on the site. Ability to be operational for at least 15 days
10. Medical aerial evacuation of disaster victims	Transport disaster victims to health facilities for medical treatment.	Availability for departure in less than 12 hours after acceptance of the offer
11. Emergency temporary shelter	Provide emergency temporary shelter, and essential services, mainly in the initial stages of a disaster until handover to local authorities or humanitarian organisations. Train the relevant personnel during the handover process.	Availability for departure in less than 12 hours after acceptance of the offer. Generally, the mission should last at most 4 weeks, or a handover process would have begun where necessary.
12. Chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear detection and sampling (CBRN)	Carry out/confirm an initial assessment, Perform qualified sampling. Mark the contaminated area. Prediction of the situation, monitoring, dynamic assessment of the risks, including recommendations for warning and other measures. Support for immediate risk reduction.	Availability for departure in less than 12 hours after the acceptance of the offer. This process should, where possible, take account of the evidential requirements of the requesting state.
13. Search and rescue	Special search and rescue using protective	Availability for departure in less than

in CBRN conditions	suits.	12 hours after the acceptance of the offer
14. Ground forest fire-fighting	Contribute to the extinction of large forest and vegetal fires by using ground means.	Availability for departure in less than 6 hours after acceptance of the offer Ability to work continuously for 7 days
15. Ground forest fire-fighting using vehicles	Contribute to the extinction of large forest and vegetal fires by using vehicles.	As above plus Deployment by land or sea. Deployment by air is only an option in well justified cases.
16. Flood containment	Reinforce existing structures and build new barriers to prevent further flooding of rivers, basins, waterways with rising water levels.	Availability for departure in less than 12 hours after acceptance of the offer. Deployment by land or sea Deployment by air is only an option in well justified cases Ability to be operational for at least 10 days.
17. Flood rescue using boats	Water search and rescue and assist people trapped in a flooding situation by using boats. Provide lifesaving aid and deliver first necessities as required.	As above

Since its creation in 2001, the Mechanism has been activated for over 150 times, for very different types of disasters. Major disasters requested assistance including the Tsunami in South Asia (2004/2005); Hurricanes Katrina and Rita in the USA (2005); earthquakes in China (2008), Haiti (2010), Japan (2011); floods in the Balkans (2010); forest fires in Greece (2007, 2012); civil unrest in Libya (2011); and explosion at a naval base in Cyprus (2011).

A summary of the activations of the Mechanism can be found [here](#), also containing the following example quoted below.

The naval base explosion in Cyprus, 2011

The request for assistance was received on 13/07/2011 concerning technical experts in the field of damage assessment, safety, security and economic impact, along with large power generators. On 14/07 a Monitoring and Information Centre local officer was sent to start preparing the deployment of a civil protection team. Starting at 16/07 the team was deployed (AT, BG, DE, HU, IT, MT, PL and UK) and was reinforced on 23/07 by 3 specialised DLR¹⁹⁰ experts to perform a UAV aerial damage assessment. In total 14 experts in liaison with the EC Representation in Nicosia and Athens, the Greek and Cypriot Civil Protection services and the award of a 1 million transport grant to Greece to support 4 ships loaded with generators sent to Limassol.

4.4.3 The GMES Emergency response service

In the frame of the European GMES initiative (Global Monitoring for Environment and Security), the [GMES Emergency Response Service](#) provides a reactive cartographic service to the registered users involved in the management of humanitarian crises, natural disasters and man-made emergency situations with products derived from Space Observation. The service is based on two pillars:

- ◆ **The Emergency Response Service**, delivering to European civil protection and humanitarian actors
- ◆ **The Emergency Support Service**, which provides reference products and situation maps, dedicated to the preparedness and recovery phases of a crisis.

¹⁹⁰ Initials of the German Aerospace Centre, <http://www.dlr.de/dlr/en/desktopdefault.aspx/tabid-10002>

The services target decision makers; implementing partners, such as for example UN agencies or the CSOs/NGOs, which increasingly provide custom-made maps to their field officers; and field officers and experts.

Users' involvement is a key priority of the service, supported by actions such as:

- ◆ Validation and acceptance of the service definition
- ◆ Validation of the operational performance and training of users
- ◆ Validation of new developments

4.4.4 An EU civil protection exercise

An EU civil protection exercise, the [EU TARANIS 2013](#), was held in Salzburg, Austria, on the 29th of June 2013, with the cooperation among civil protection teams from Austria, Bulgaria, Romania, Croatia, the Czech Republic, the Netherlands and Germany. The exercise lasted for three days and the subject was the integration of response capacities from other Member States in a domestic major disaster. According to the scenario, Austria was hit by heavy rains and the consequent flooding greatly damaged the infrastructure. This triggered road, train and plane accidents, some of which involved chemical spills. The teams practiced urban search and rescue, search and rescue in chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear (CBRN) conditions, rescue in flood conditions, high capacity pumping, and water purification.

The exercise was the first EU co-financed civil protection exercise organised by, and with strong participation of the Red Cross (Austrian Red Cross).

Such operational trials are very important for the readiness and preparation of response teams, especially in cross-border cooperative missions such as those of the recent exercise. A clear programme of similar actions and initiatives covering all the basic categories of crises described in section 4.2, and planned on a systematic basis to cover all the Member States could prove invaluable for civil protection at pan-European level and for enhancing the security of European citizens.

Figure 22: Scene from the EU TARANIS 2013 exercise.

4.5 CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANISATIONS (CSOs)

CSOs or also frequently called Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) can be local or international and vary greatly in terms of financial, technical and operational capacities. Their action in protecting the security of citizens and victims has been manifested in many

situations of emergency and has frequently been praised. Critical aspects of their role in complex emergencies have been successfully analysed by Dr. Muriuki¹⁹¹ during a conference by the WHO; in what follows, we summarise the basic conclusions from that presentation.

Although international CSOs have the advantage of larger resources, local CSOs, despite limited resources can have as much or greater impact in terms of delivering services to distressed populations, due to their superior knowledge of the situation at hand. Strengths of CSOs, which make them ideal operatives in emergencies include:

- ◆ **Ability to respond fast;** due to established protocols of response to emergencies, readily available and able to mobilise resources, to the extent that they frequently are on site before other actors.
- ◆ **Flexibility;** most CSOs can adapt rapidly to changing environments, in contrast to other official actors who are bound by stringent security precautions, host government concerns and other factors.
- ◆ **Manoeuvrability;** CSOs can reach many hard to reach areas and populations; some of them using own air or sea transport capabilities.
- ◆ **Creation of public awareness;** being part of the civil society, CSOs traditionally have good links with the media, put to good effect for awareness-raising. This was evident at the initial stages after the 2004 tsunami when the full impact and destruction had not been fully comprehended by many people, including political leaders in the affected countries.
- ◆ **Health service delivery;** this is a very important and successful feature of CSOs, both in the short as well as in the long term. For example in both the Liberia and Rwanda crises, CSOs were not only the first on ground, but at some point were responsible for about 95% of the health care delivery. Ten years later, a considerable proportion of health services in both these countries were still provided by CSOs.

Despite the huge advantages and successes of CSOs, they also face challenges, such as:

- ◆ **Lack of the big picture;** a problem mainly affecting small CSOs, with no established connections with governments and multilaterals. This may mislead them into projects of low priority or low sustainability after their departure.
- ◆ **Poor coordination;** lack of a strong coordinating body in complex emergencies may lead to duplication of effort or to concentration of effort in one area while other affected populations do not receive sufficient resources or effort.
- ◆ **Being ignored;** host governments frequently deal with official actors and tend to ignore CSOs especially in decision-making. This often proves counterproductive as because of their presence and interaction with affected populations, CSOs especially local ones are in a better place to correctly identify the needs of the affected population.

Over 100 CSOs/NGOs were involved in the December 26, 2004 Asia Tsunami Disaster Response and Recovery Operations as of January 1, 2006¹⁹². Of those we quote a sample here:

1. [International Red Cross and Red Crescent \(IFRC\)](#). The International Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement is comprised of three interrelated components, namely the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), the Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies and the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC).
2. [Action Against Hunger | ACF International](#)
3. [Act!onAid International](#)

¹⁹¹ Muriuki, D., “Contribution of NGOs in Complex Emergencies”, WHO Conference on the Health Aspects of the Tsunami Disaster in Asia, Phuket, Thailand, 4- 6 May 2005

¹⁹² <http://libguides.tulane.edu/content.php?pid=73839&sid=565675>

4. [Action Medeor - German medical aid organisation](#)
5. [Adventist Development and Relief Agency \(ADRA\)](#)
6. [Agence d'Aide à la Coopération Technique Et au Développement \(ACTED\)](#)
7. [ALL INDIA DISASTER MITIGATION INSTITUTE](#)
8. [AmeriCares Disaster and Humanitarian Aid Organization](#)
9. [The Catholic Agency For Overseas Development \(CAFOD\)](#)
10. [CARE International \(CARE\)](#)
11. [Caritas Internationalis](#)
12. [Christian Aid - United Kingdom](#)
13. [Church World Service](#)
14. [Focus Humanitarian Assistance \(FOCUS\)](#)
15. [Health Partners International of Canada \(HPIC\)](#)
16. [HELP – Hilfe zur Selbsthilfe e.V](#)
17. [HelpAge International](#)
18. [IMA World Health | Health Care in Developing Countries \(Interchurch Medical Assistance, Inc.\)](#)
19. [International Medical Corps](#)
20. [International Rescue Corps - U.K.](#)
21. [Islamic Relief \(IR\)- United Kingdom](#)
22. [Latter-day Saint Charities - United States](#)
23. [Médecins Sans Frontières International](#)
24. [Muslim Aid - UK](#)
25. [Norwegian Church Aid is part of ACT International](#)
26. [Oxfam International.](#)
27. [Project HOPE \(Health Opportunities for People Everywhere\)](#)
28. [Swiss Foundation for Mine Action \(FSD\)](#)
29. [United States Fund for UNICEF.](#)
30. [World Concern](#)
31. [World Emergency Relief's \(WER\)](#)
32. [World Hope International \(WHI\)](#)
33. [World Relief](#)

4.6 REGULATIONS, GUIDELINES AND WARNING SYSTEMS

This section summarises the European regulatory framework that aims not only to protect citizens during a crisis, but also to provide prevention and warning measures, if at all possible. We have to note here that, due to the widely acknowledged climate change, a shift of the regulatory framework has occurred towards mitigating the effects of this change. This includes explicit reference to extreme weather crises, such as heat, floods and storms and frequent references to possible side effects such as wildfires. The net result is that recent regulations and guidelines at European level tend to view disaster mitigation measures within the causal envelope of the climatic change. Three policy examples below are indicative of this development.

As mentioned in the introduction to this chapter the EU Internal Security Strategy has recognised climate change as a cause of crises. This is followed by the European Commission's latest package to advance action on adaptation to climate change, announced in April 2013. The package also represents the most recent EU policy response to disasters. It explicitly talks about "strengthening Europe's preparedness against natural and man-made disasters"¹⁹³ and introduces an adaptation strategy. A Green Paper on the role of insurance in mitigating the effects of a disaster was also made available for public consultation until the end of June 2013. Further EC legislative and non-legislative will follow based on the responses received.

¹⁹³ http://ec.europa.eu/clima/news/articles/news_2013041601_en.htm

Along similar lines, a Communication¹⁹⁴ by the Commission identifies the need for preparing **guidelines on disaster prevention** within the framework of climate change adaptation. This follows the call of the Council Conclusions of November 2009 on a Community Framework on disaster prevention within the Union. Preparatory work has included collection and analysis of more than 400 examples of good practice from over 35 countries including all countries participating in the Civil Protection Mechanism plus Turkey, Australia, New Zealand, USA and Switzerland.

Intended to be voluntary in nature, the guidelines centred on multi-hazard or horizontal and cross-cutting themes that could be in line with the 4 prevention priorities under the 10-year UN [Hyogo Framework for Action](#) for building the resilience of nations and communities to disasters. Potential areas to be included in the guidelines are:

- ◆ Governance, that is cooperation and coordination at different levels and across different authorities and stakeholders, cross border cooperation, monitoring, evaluation and implementation of existing legislation, cooperation with the business sector and voluntary organisations, community resilience actions, coherence with other policies including climate change adaptation;
- ◆ Planning, including development and promotion of multi-hazard and cross sectoral risk assessments at national, regional and local level, which should be further integrated into risk management plans, recovery, capability and response planning as well as long-term sustainable development strategies and policies (e.g. land-use planning, infrastructure) and financial mechanisms;
- ◆ Disaster data, including recommendations and good practices on collection, analysis and sharing of data and its use for policy-making;
- ◆ Risk communication, information-sharing and awareness raising, including use of social media, mechanisms for effective exchange of information before, during and after a disaster, creation of one information portal on risks, vulnerabilities and preventative actions, tailored risk communication to target local and vulnerable population, education and awareness raising activities;
- ◆ Research and technology transfer – including use of new technologies for prevention and risk management, development of multi-hazard early warning systems, extract value out of research and implement into practice and underpin scientifically based decision-making;

Finally, the Communication above includes a list of existing related EU-level supplementary policies on which the guidelines can be based. These are existing policies related to human, animal and plant health such as the EU Health Programme 2007-2013, the EU Ambient Air quality and Cleaner Air Directive, the EU Animal Health Strategy (2007-2013), including the revision and consolidation of veterinary legislation by a New Animal Health Law, and the review of the EU plant health legislation. Existing institutions along these lines also include the European Centre for Disease prevention and control (ECDC).

Next, we will describe specific European regulatory frameworks which are more focused on specific types of disasters and aim to protect the security of citizens.

¹⁹⁴ European Commission, Brussels, “An EU Strategy on adaptation to climate change”, COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS, Impact Assessment - Part 2, Brussels, 16.4.2013

4.6.1 Floods

The EU Floods Directive¹⁹⁵, published in the Official Journal on 6 November 2007, aims to reduce and manage the risks that floods pose to human health, the environment, cultural heritage and economic activity. The Directive applies to inland waters as well as all coastal waters across the whole territory of the EU and foresees a phased implementation plan by Member States as follows:

- ◆ preliminary assessment by 2011 to identify the river basins and associated coastal areas at risk of flooding
- ◆ flood risk maps to be drawn for zones at risk by 2013
- ◆ flood risk management plans focused on prevention, protection and preparedness, drawn by 2015

These steps need to be reviewed every 6 years in a cycle coordinated and synchronised with the implementation cycle of the [Water Framework Directive](#) which shapes Community action in water policy. All assessments, maps and plans prepared shall be made available to the public.

To support the implementation, a [Common Implementation Strategy](#) has been drawn. Reporting, a requirement of the Directive, is via [WISE \(Water Information System for Europe\)](#).

Besides European level action, flood is in many cases a cross-border issue. Spain and Portugal have a bilateral agreement on flooding control. Another example is the cooperation between Germany, France, Holland, Belgium and Switzerland on flood management in the Rhine and the Meuse (Maas) river basin¹⁹⁶.

4.6.2 Extreme temperature

Recent extreme temperature events have in many occasions been attributed to climate warming. Main weapons against the effects of heat waves constitute early detection and warning systems, usually referred to as Heat Health Warning Systems (HHWS¹⁹⁷), and plans for emergency action once a heat wave has been detected.

A HHWS uses meteorological forecasts to initiate acute public health interventions designed to reduce heat-related impacts on human health during typically hot weather.

The EuroHEAT project¹⁹⁸ observes that as there are no standard definitions of the terms “heat event” or “heat-wave” HHWSs in Europe use different methods to define and to identify such situations. Most use air temperature and duration, but some systems use more complex methods to encircle heat situations such as synoptic approaches and heat balance approaches using parameters such as humidity, wind speed and cloud cover.

¹⁹⁵ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2007:288:0027:0034:EN:PDF>

¹⁹⁶ De Wit M., J., M. et al, “Floods in the Meuse basin: Event descriptions and an international view on ongoing measures”, Intl. J. River Basin Management, Vol. 5, No. 4 (2007), pp. 279–292, <http://www.cipm-icbm.be/files/files/jrbmmaas.pdf>

¹⁹⁷ Kovats, R. S., Kristie, L. E., “Heatwaves and public health in Europe”, European Journal of Public Health, Vol. 16, No. 6, 592–599, 2006

¹⁹⁸ World Health Organisation, Europe, “Improving Public Health Responses To Extreme Weather/Heat-Waves, EuroHEAT”, Meeting Report, Bonn, Germany, March, 2007

It should be noted that meteorological thresholds for action triggered by a HHWS must also be population specific so as to apply to the local population's adaptation ability. The majority of HHWSs implemented after 2003 have more than one level of response, based on the confidence in the heat wave forecast or the magnitude of the event. Cities in the US also have two-tiered or three-tiered warning procedures. Most cities in Europe include emergency planning, which can be deployed for extreme heat waves. For example, the Greek government implemented its Xenocrates emergency plan for natural disasters during severe heat waves in 1998 and 2002 and the system has been quite successful since. The highest level of the UK heat wave plan triggers a so-called “Major Incident” response.

It is of interest to note¹⁹⁸ that past experience has been utilised by civil authorities in many cases. At the time of the heat wave in Europe in 2003, only two cities in the WHO European region had operational HHWSs: the ICARO system in Lisbon and a heat health watch warning system in Rome. After 2004, France, Italy, Germany, Spain and the UK all developed and launched heat wave plans. However, for the moment, there is no specific legislation or regulation at the European level.

Finally, the effects of heat waves are closely dependent on the activity and the conditions the affected individuals are engaged in at the time they are happening. Most state authorities, in combination with HHWSs issue guidelines towards the population, such as plan the day so that you stay out of the heat; avoid strenuous outdoor activity; take cool showers or baths; drink regularly; check on older people living alone, etc.

Example: 2003 Heat wave in France (reproduced from ref 194)

In 2003, France suffered the hottest summer in 50 years. That year, an exceptionally severe heat wave claimed more than 15,000 lives. After this tragedy, the public authorities established the national heat emergency plan, which is activated every year from 1 June to 31 August, in order to reduce the risk of deaths from heat waves. The French Red Cross, in its role as auxiliary to the public authorities and with its 45,000 volunteers and 556 health and social facilities, was mobilized in a large-scale operation in the summer of 2003 (helping vulnerable people, distributing water, assisting health facilities and emergency services). Since then, it has played an active part in implementing the national plan. Based on its own heat emergency guide and plan, it prepares and implements a series of actions in coordination with the public authorities and in accordance with local resources and needs.

The national heat emergency plan established by the Ministry of Health provides for French Red Cross intervention at various levels. It plays a vital role in strengthening solidarity and dealing with the problem of isolated vulnerable people, particularly those most at risk from the effects of a heat wave. It also mobilizes its volunteers to carry out specific activities, targeting the most vulnerable sectors of the population including elderly and disabled people. In 2006 the French Red Cross mobilized its network to deal with the effects of extremely high temperatures (level 2 or 3), deploying over 3,500 volunteers. Efforts focused primarily on assisting homeless people and isolated elderly people, supporting establishments and services, such as homes for the elderly and hospital emergency services, and providing first-aid teams. On 17 July 2006, the public authorities in western France activated level 2 of the heat emergency plan, where the local Red Cross branch started on its rounds of elderly people living on their own. The most problematic cases were to be dealt with on the first day, focusing on the most vulnerable sectors of the population, including those who are completely on their own, those who are no longer in full possession of their faculties and those who have serious medical conditions. On recognizing the Red Cross uniform, an elderly lady opened her door quickly. In the dim interior of her pleasant, impeccably kept apartment, 87-year-old Suzanne invited the volunteers to sit down for a moment in her living room. “I’m so happy to know that someone is thinking of me. You can’t imagine how hard it is and how much my heart is warmed by what you do,” she said (Source Red Cross, 2009)

4.6.3 Wildfire

Forest fire is another hazard intensified by climatic changes. In fact “projected climate changes would increase the length and severity of the fire season, the area at risk and the

probability of large fires, possibly enhancing desertification.”¹⁹⁹. Warmer countries in Europe are obviously more affected, but their resources appear frequently limited to face the outbreak of accelerating fires and the peaks of demand in human and material resources such as trained personnel, airborne and land-based means etc.

Action at multilateral (European) level is among the most efficient way to face such threats and to protect the security of citizens. Chapter 3 (section 3.4) provides a recent example to the critical role that multilateral assistance played in fighting wildfires in Greece in 2007. More than 10 member states provided assistance in response to the four requests from the Greek government in 27th June, 5 July, 18 July and 24 August. In what follows we refer to policy measures at EU level, which promote multilateral action for the protection of citizens against wildfires.

Various DGs at the European Commission are involved in the development and monitoring of measures in the field of forest fires. Up to 2002 the legal framework for information, prevention, fire fighting and restoration of burned surfaces was provided by a 1992 [regulation](#). After 2002, this was replaced by the [Forest Focus](#), a monitoring scheme which, up to 2006, supported the implementation of forest fire prevention measures in the Member States. Activities have since continued under the [European Forest Fire Information System \(EFFIS\)](#), which is jointly managed by the Commission's Joint Research Centre and DG Environment.

Awareness-raising campaigns, providing information to the public, and training of forest fire prevention agents between 2007 and 2013 are financed under [LIFE+](#) instrument.

EU level support for the restoration of forests and fire prevention activities is legally based on the [Regulation on support for rural development \(1698/2005\)](#) by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) for the period 2007-2013. It lays the ground for a new rural development policy and obliges Member States to classify areas on their territory posing particular risks of fire in their forest protection plans. Articles 36 and 48 call for measures preventing fires and restoring damage from fire for forest areas classified as of high or medium risk.

Sources of funding for damaged areas can include the [EU Solidarity Fund](#). To qualify for assistance, the estimated cost of total direct damage must exceed €3 billion in 2002 prices or 0.6% of the gross national income of the State in question, whichever is the lower.

Finally, in response to forest fires in Greece and large-scale flooding in the United Kingdom in September 2007, the European Parliament adopted a [resolution on natural disasters](#) followed by another [resolution on stepping up the Union's disaster response capacity](#). This helped raise awareness and cooperation levels in Europe and also raise funding for increased capacity to combat disasters.

A [report on the causes and contributing factors of forest fires in Europe](#), published by DG Research in February 2008, showed that due to considerable rural depopulation, the Greek forest service was forced to acquire fire-fighting vehicles and hire seasonal fire-fighters.

¹⁹⁹ European Commission, Brussels, “An EU Strategy on adaptation to climate change”, COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS, Impact Assessment - Part 2, Brussels, 16.4.2013

Another example is Italy, which has Europe's largest fleet of aircraft and helicopters, and has on several occasions loaned out its planes to France and Spain. The high level of preparedness requires significant resources, but has shown good results: the year 2000 saw 6600 fires destroy 58000 hectares of forest, while almost the same number of fires in 2006 only destroyed 16,000 hectares (Swedish Commission on Climate and Vulnerability, 2007).

4.6.4 Earthquake

Protection of citizens from earthquakes is left to national civil protection authorities of the Member States, in addition, of course, to multilateral resources, such as the European Mechanism for Civil Protection or the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs.

From the legislative point of view, the main effort lies in protecting citizens via the quality and levels of safety offered by construction in Europe. To this end, the EN Eurocodes for construction products and engineering services are meant to lead to more uniform levels of safety and citizen protection in construction in Europe. The EN Eurocodes are European standards, currently at the national calibration stage. After publication of the [National Standard](#) transposing the Eurocodes and the National Annexes, all conflicting standards are expected to have been withdrawn already (by 2010). The EN Eurocodes prove compliance of building and civil engineering works with the essential requirements of the [Construction Products Directive](#) and cover standards such as:

- ◆ basis of structural design (EN 1990);
- ◆ actions on structures (EN 1991);
- ◆ the design of concrete (EN 1992), steel (EN 1993), composite steel and concrete (EN1994), (EN 1994), timber (EN 1995), masonry (EN 1996) and aluminium (EN 1999) structures, together with;
- ◆ geotechnical design (EN 1997); and
- ◆ the design, assessment and retrofitting of structures for earthquake resistance (EN 1998).

Scientific and technical organisations in the EU indirectly support the protection of citizens from earthquakes, by increasing the available knowledge about these phenomena and promoting appropriate action measures based on their findings. They include the [European Laboratory for Structural Assessment](#) (ELSA), part of the Institute for the Protection and Security of the Citizen (IPSC) of the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission and the [European-Mediterranean Seismological Centre](#) (EMSC).

The ELSA provides research, contributes to European standards harmonisation in construction, performs vulnerability assessment of buildings and civil infrastructures for risk mitigation and develops appropriate methodologies using experimental testing and numerical modelling in Structural Mechanics. One of its missions is also to identify the co-normative and pre-normative research needs for the development and maintenance of the Eurocodes.

The EMSC is an international, non-governmental, and non-profit association for the promotion of seismological research. It runs an Earthquake Alert System for potentially damaging earthquakes in the Euro-Med region which consists of the rapid determination of the epicentre and the dissemination of the seismic alert message within the hour following the occurrence of the earthquake. In 1987, the EMSC was charged by the Council of Europe (CoE) to provide the latter with seismic warnings in the framework of the Open Partial

Agreement (OPA) on the prevention of, protection against, and organisation of relief in major natural and technological disasters.

4.6.5 Man-made disasters

Man-made disasters threaten the security of the citizen on a par with natural disasters. These come both from deliberate acts of mass distraction, usually characterised as terrorism acts, and from accidents due to a variety of causes.

Terrorism threatens security and, especially after the infamous 9/11, all European countries have included extra pieces of legislation in their legal systems. A notable example is the transposition of the [Data Retention Directive](#) (2006) by the Member States, which also has been the object of studies regarding the adverse effects it may have on the security of the citizens. Although the main purpose of the Directive is to help in the investigation of crime, therefore to protect citizens from its consequences, there has been criticism on the inadequate measures contained therein regarding protecting citizens against abuse of their rights to privacy and data protection²⁰⁰.

At EU level, the [EU Counter-Terrorism Strategy](#), adopted in 2005, commits the Union to combating terrorism globally, while respecting human rights. The actions proposed are along four axes, namely PREVENT, PROTECT, PURSUE and RESPOND.

Border security has been strengthened with new systems still being developed such as the [second generation Schengen Information System](#) (SIS II) and the [Visa Information System](#) (VIS). Cyber security is dealt with in the framework decision on [attacks against information systems](#) and the [action plan to protect critical information infrastructure](#). To improve transport security, especially regarding civil aviation and maritime transport, a legislative framework has been established, under the cooperation of national administrations and the Commission²⁰¹.

On the matter of protecting infrastructure, a directive on [European critical infrastructures](#) was adopted in 2008 as a first step in creating an EU-wide approach. Other instruments relating to data gathering and exchanges have been adopted, such as the Data Retention Directive (see above), the decision on [stepping up cross-border cooperation](#) and the framework decisions on [simplifying the exchange of information between national law enforcement authorities](#) and on the [European evidence warrant](#). At the same time, improvements have been made to the functioning of [Europol](#) and to its cooperation with [Eurojust](#).

The financing of terrorism indirectly affects the security of the citizen by enabling subsequent activities. Legislation to counteract this is based on the Directive on [money laundering](#) adopted in 2005 and the regulation on [controls of cash entering or leaving the EU](#) (2005). There are also non-legislative measures to counter terrorist financing, such as the voluntary

²⁰⁰ Feiler L., “The Legality of the Data Retention Directive in Light of the Fundamental Rights to Privacy and Data Protection”, *European Journal of Law and Technology*, Vol 1, No 3 (2010), <http://ejlt.org/article/view/29/75>

²⁰¹ European Commission, Brussels, “COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT on Transport Security”, SWD(2012) 143 final, Brussels, 31.5.2012, <http://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/security/doc/2012-05-31-swd-transport-security.pdf>

guidelines to address the vulnerability of non-profit organisations to abuse for terrorist financing purposes.

Response and effective protection of citizens is entrusted to the [EU Civil Protection Mechanism](#) as well as the Crisis Coordination Arrangements (CCA) and the ARGUS system, which aim at coordinating responses to crises. Europol also supports coordinated responses to terrorist incidents through its information exchange mechanisms.

The [EU action plan on chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear security](#) was adopted in 2009, with a view to better prepare and respond to incidents in which terrorists would obtain such materials. The Commission also provides support to victims of terrorist attacks, including financial support.

4.6.6 Accidents

Accidents are not deliberate disasters and protection for citizens at legislative level is left to the general health and safety provisions existing in each Member State, usually implementing European Directives. These cover both general safety as well as related conditions at work as shown below. A wide variety of Community measures in the field of safety and health at work have been adopted on the basis of Article 153 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (ex Article 137 TEC). Important Directives in this area include:

- [The OSH Framework Directive](#)
- [Workplaces, equipment, signs, personal protective equipment](#)
- [Exposure to chemical agents and chemical safety](#)
- [Exposure to physical hazards](#)
- [Exposure to biological agents](#)
- [Provisions on workload, ergonomic and psychosocial risks](#)
- [Sector specific and worker related provisions](#)

To those, we should add the **Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemical substances regulations (REACH)**, (EC 1907/2006), which entered into force in 2007. The aim of REACH is to improve the protection of human health and the environment through the better and earlier identification of the intrinsic properties of chemical substances. The regulations are managed and monitored by the [European Chemicals Agency \(ECHA\)](#) in Helsinki.

Legislative protection from major chemical accidents in Europe is via the “Seveso Directive”, now in its third version ([Directive 2012/18/EU](#), adopted on 4th July 2012 and entered into force on 13th August 2012, with Member States obligations to transpose and implement it 1st June 2015). It applies to around 10,000 industrial establishments where dangerous substances are used or stored in large quantities, mainly in the chemicals, petrochemicals, storage, and metal refining sectors. The Directive obliges Member States to ensure that operators have a policy in place to prevent major accidents and the obligation to inform the public likely to be affected by an accident. Member States must ensure that emergency plans are in place for the surrounding areas and that mitigation actions are planned. Account must also be taken of these objectives in land-use planning.

There is a tiered approach to the level of controls: the larger the quantities of dangerous substances present within an establishment, the stricter the rules ('upper-tier' establishments have bigger quantities than 'lower-tier' establishments and are therefore subject to tighter

control). This is a risk-based protection for the citizen, in the sense that the greater the risk the stricter the prevention measures demanded by legislation.

4.7 CONCLUSION

Crises affect the security and well-being of the citizen in multiple ways which span bodily and psychological health, destruction of communities and supporting infrastructure, loss of personal property, loss of life and even possibly destruction of entire civilisations²⁰². As COSMIC concerns social media during crises, citizens are the potential users of such media; their behaviour is largely determined by the crisis itself and its evolution. This, in turn, is dependent on the response by organised forms of society charged with mitigating the effects.

Concerted societal action combating a crisis involves monitoring, prediction, preparation and intervention plans as well as dedicated organisations. Those are found at Member States in the form of security forces, purpose-led emergency services and rescue agencies, medical teams, fire fighting bodies and others. At EU level organisations such as the Community Mechanism for Civil Protection and the GMES Emergency Response Service offer cross-border assistance where it is needed, in response to calls by individual states both from the EU and elsewhere. At an even higher level, the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) has an extensive track record of intervention in distress situations all over the world. These efforts are supplemented by a variety of Civil Society (Non-Governmental) Organisations, which, thanks to their flexibility, can offer substantial support to communities in need.

Organised societies protect citizens not only via material means but also via sets of principles, expressed as policy and legislation frameworks. It is through such frameworks that any emerging crisis management methods, such as those treated by COSMIC, have to pass. To this end, it was necessary to offer a concise view of the legislative and regulatory activities undertaken both at national and European level (European Directives, guidelines and regulations).

What emerged in the course of drafting this chapter is the concern at policy level about the combined effects of climatic change, which are increasingly considered responsible for a multiplicity of crises such as heat waves, floods and storms. Effort at European Commission level uses the framework of climatic change as the starting point for a forthcoming set of guidelines on disaster prevention in collaboration with the participant states in the Community Mechanism for Civil Protection and countries such as Turkey, Australia, New Zealand, USA and Switzerland.

²⁰² Scholars have suggested that the eruption on the island of Thera (present-day Santorini about 100 km distant from Crete), among the largest volcanic explosions in the history of civilization, was instrumental in the destruction of the Minoan civilisation.

Chapter 5: Crises and societal dynamics

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5 CRISES AND SOCIETAL DYNAMICS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

An integral part of the COSMIC project is to understand the individual, organisational and societal dynamics in crisis situations. If the COSMIC consortium is to explore how new and emerging technologies, such as social media, are effectively utilised, we will need to understand the various social responses before, during and after crisis situations, particularly with regard to the typical crisis situations which have been identified in Chapter 2 of this report.

In this chapter we provide an outline of the individual, organisational and societal dynamics with respect to crisis situations.²⁰³ Dynamics refer to the behavioural responses of individuals, organisations and societies (communities) before, during and after crisis situations. Consequently, partners will identify how different individuals, organisations and societies appear to organise themselves to respond to different types of crises and will determine the impact of different types of crises on the interaction of individuals and organisations. For this purpose, partners will use illustrative examples of crisis situations from the EU and other countries. These examples are based on the selection of typical crisis situations, as identified in Chapter 2.

5.2 INDIVIDUAL DYNAMICS

Individual dynamics during crisis situations are dependent on (citizen) preparation, (early) warning, and interventions (or lack thereof) during the response and recovery phases of a crisis. This sub-section will describe these four phases to highlight the individual dynamics of citizens during crisis situations.

Prior to doing so, it is important to note that not all crisis types follow these four phases in the same manner. Crises such as extreme temperatures, storms and wildfires are typically preceded by an extended warning period. This allows citizens to prepare themselves, for example, by evacuating a certain area or seeking shelter. In the warning period, information about the physical characteristics of the event and recommendations regarding which protective actions to take are distributed via the mass media, social media and informal networks.²⁰⁴ Other crisis situations have a shorter warning period and necessitate a faster warning and response, such as a rapid-moving wildfire that changes direction due to the wind. Earthquakes and man-made disasters such as chemical spills, traffic accidents and terrorism can occur without warning and are therefore ‘sudden’ crises. These sudden crises are unexpected and are difficult to prepare for in a specific manner. The degree to which individuals are able to cope with these unexpected crises depends largely on the skills and knowledge they have developed, as well as the resources they have possessed over their life time.²⁰⁵

²⁰³ Because of this division there will be some necessary overlap between the paragraphs.

²⁰⁴ Sorensen, J. and B. Vogt (2006). Interactive emergency evacuation guidebook. Last accessed on 7-1-2013. Retrieved from: <http://orise.orau.gov/csepp/documents/planning/evacuation-guidebook/index.htm>.

²⁰⁵ Helsloot, I. and H. Ruitenbergh (2004). Citizen Response to Disasters: a Survey of Literature and Some Practical Implications. In: *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*. 12(3), pp. 98-111.

5.2.1 Preparation

Individuals only prepare for those crises that they perceive to present a significant and imminent threat to themselves or their relatives; in the absence of danger, individuals do not like to think about any possible negative consequences of a crisis situation.²⁰⁶ As argued by Thomas and Thomas; “If men define their situations as real they are real in their consequences”.²⁰⁷

Flood preparation and risk perception

In Western societies, few citizens perceive floods to be a significant threat. In a recent study in the Netherlands, which is a flood-prone country, only 13 per cent of the respondents regarded flooding as a likely event within the next ten years.²⁰⁸ In addition, very few respondents were found to express anxiety about their exposure to floods. Not surprisingly, hence, it is often found that residents living in flood-prone areas do not adequately prepare themselves for potential floods events.²⁰⁹

Risk perception

To gain a better understanding of the way individuals prepare themselves for crises, it is necessary to consider the insights obtained from scientific research on risk perception, which focuses on the way individuals assess safety and security risks.

The way safety and security risks are perceived by individuals has changed in recent decades.²¹⁰ This change is particularly visible in crisis situations with a large impact. For example, the 1953 flood in the Netherlands caused 1,835 deaths and was largely perceived as an “act of God” and therefore beyond the responsibility of the Dutch government. Alternatively, the 2007 forest fire in Greece, that destroyed 2,700 square kilometres of forest, olives groves and farmland and killed 84 people, was seen as unacceptable, a failure of government oversight, and as a case of terrible public miss-management.²¹¹ Nevertheless, it is striking to see that other (objectively larger) risks are often accepted, even when citizens are aware that the risk is larger. We must therefore question, what factors influence individuals’ perception of safety and security risks?

A considerable body of scientific research has shown that individuals look at more than just ‘probabilities’ or ‘effects’ of risks when they assess their safety and security. In fact, in the assessment of the acceptability of safety and security risks these measures play a minor role. Starr was one of the first researchers who studied the factors that influence individuals’ perception of safety and security risks.²¹² One of his conclusions was that the acceptability of voluntary risks (like driving a car, or smoking) is a thousand times higher than that of involuntarily risks.

²⁰⁶ Perry R. W. and M.K. Lindell (2003). Understanding Citizen Response to Disasters with Implications for Terrorism. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*. 11(2), pp. 51–52.

²⁰⁷ Thomas W. and D.S. Thomas (1928). *The Child in America*, New York.

²⁰⁸ Terpstra T. (2009). Flood Preparedness: Thoughts, Feelings and Intentions of the Dutch Public. Dissertation, University of Twente.

²⁰⁹ Bubeck, P., W.J.W. Botzen, H. Kreibich and J.C.J.H. Aerts (2013). Detailed insights into the influence of flood-coping appraisals on mitigation behaviour. *Global Environmental Change*.

²¹⁰ Helsloot and Ruitenbergh, 2004.

²¹¹ Attewill, Fred (2007). “Anger at Greek Government’s Wildfire Response”, *The Guardian*, 28 August 2007. <http://www.guardian.co.uk/world/2007/aug/28/naturaldisasters.features11>.

²¹² Starr, C. (1969). Social benefits versus technological risk, *Science*. 165(3899), pp. 1232–1238.

Building upon the work of Starr, Slovic et al.²¹³ in the USA and Vlek and Stallen²¹⁴ in the Netherlands concluded that a number of (sometimes combined) factors influence the perception of risks. These factors include:

- a) The ‘catastrophic potential’ or ‘perceived threat’;
- b) In-voluntarism understood as unfairness (who benefits, who bears the effects);
- c) In-voluntarism understood as a lack of personal influence (uncontrollability);
- d) New risks versus known risks (e.g. new technology);
- e) Hidden or long-term effects of the risk (e.g. cancer after long term exposure); and
- f) Lack of clarity of the societal effects of the risk-bearing activity. More recently, research has shown that confidence (or the lack of it) in the openness of responsible authorities and the attributability of the risks affects how risks are perceived by individuals.²¹⁵

Protection Motivation Theory

Research on risk perception shows that risks are social constructs, which cannot be completely objectified. For example, Dake explains that risk perception is an “interpersonal experience based in moral commitments to particular ways of life”²¹⁶. This means that ultimately risks are perceived in different ways among communities. This is a result of a multitude of factors relating to cultural biases, social relations and behavioural strategies, which may be present in one community, religious group or society, but not in others.

The degree to which individuals prepare themselves for a crisis is not only determined by the perception of a threat, but also, the perception of coping possibilities, that is the actions individuals can to protect themselves against a threat. Both of these elements are captured in the Protection Motivation Theory (PMT).²¹⁷ PMT is considered to be one of the foremost theoretical frameworks to predict and influence health-related behaviour. Although PMT was originally developed to understand protective health behaviour, it has been successfully applied in several other contexts, including technical and environmental risks, as well as natural hazards.^{218 219}

PMT presumes that individuals undergo two main cognitive processes when facing a specific threat, i.e., “threat appraisal” and “coping appraisal”. Threat appraisal consists of two components: “perceived vulnerability” (probability of the threat) and “perceived severity” (consequences of the threat). These two components describe how threatened individuals perceive a threat. Coping appraisal refers to the cognitive process that people undergo when they simulate possible responses to a threat as well as their ability to avert or avoid the threat.

²¹³ Slovic, P., B. Fischhoff and S. Lichtenstein (1979). Rating the Risks, *Environment*, 21(3), pp. 14-39.

²¹⁴ Vlek, C. and P.J. Stallen (1980), Rational and Personal Aspects of Risk, *ACTA Psychology* 45(1-3), pp. 273-300.

²¹⁵ Helsloot and Ruitenber, 2004.

²¹⁶ Dake, K. (1992). Myths of Nature: Culture and the Social construction of Risk. *Journal of Social Issues*, 48(4), pp. 21-37.

²¹⁷ Rogers, R.W. (1983). Cognitive and physiological processes in fear appeals and attitude change: A revised theory of protection motivation. In J. Cacioppo & R. Petty (Eds.), *Social Psychophysiology*. New York: Guilford Press.

²¹⁸ Bubeck et al., 2013.

²¹⁹ Grothmann, T. and F. Reusswig (2006). People at risk of flooding: why some residents take precautionary action while others do not. *Natural Hazards*. 38, pp. 101–120.

It encompasses three components: ‘response efficacy’, ‘self-efficacy’ and ‘response cost’.²²⁰ Response efficacy concerns the degree to which an individual believes a protective measure is effective for reducing a specific risk. Self-efficacy indicates whether an individual believes he or she is able to actually implement the protective measure and “response cost” describes the financial, time and emotional costs that an individual associates with implementing the protective measures.²²¹ According to Bubeck et al., these two appraisal processes influence an individual’s protection motivation, which can be regarded as an intervening variable that arouses, sustains and directs the activity of individuals to protect themselves to the threat, and results in a coping response that can be either protective or non-protective.²²² Bubeck et al. define protective measures as (all) those actions that are suitable to actually reduce the threat and are adopted if high-risk perceptions are accompanied by (positive) coping appraisals. In contrast, they define non-protective responses as situations in which high risk perceptions are accompanied by low coping appraisals.²²³

PMT can be seen as an extension of Azjen’s Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB).²²⁴ Azjen suggests with the TPB that only certain attitudes towards behaviour can be expected to predict that behaviour. Azjen argues that we consequently need to look not only at those attitudes, but at subjective norms and perceived behavioural control to explain any behavioural intent as well. An important addition of TPB is the inclusion of subjective norms in research on risk behaviour as these are equally important to determine citizen behaviour.

Variables that influence threat and coping appraisal

Nature of the threat: In the case of any future crisis, citizens often assess possible risks based on their sensory perception: risks which people can see, hear or smell are perceived as visible and finite. In the citizens’ understanding, preparing to respond to these kinds of crises makes sense. Thus, citizens may take preparatory action to threats that are highly perceptible, such as wildfires, floods and storms with warning periods and extreme temperatures especially when they are alarmed that the risk of exposure to the threat is rising.

The distinctive characteristic of many new risks, which result from technological innovations, is that their effects are mostly unknown. As a result, citizens often do not take preparatory actions. The fear of radiation is useful to illustrate this point; individuals perceive radiation to be catastrophic, irreversible and with long-lasting health effects. Factual information about radiation levels, exposure and its real dangers is often absent in the public debate. Individuals have been exposed to many discussions and information about the harmful effects of the radiation. For these reasons, whenever radiation comes into play, it is perceived as a threat of high-level radiation threatening with serious health problems or even death. Preparing for this kind of threat is quickly considered to be useless.

Experience with crises: The scientific literature suggests that personal experience with a certain type of crisis often results in a more accurate perception of the threat and better coping

²²⁰ Floyd, D.L., S. Prentice-Dunn and R.W. Rogers (2000). A meta-analysis of research on protection motivation theory. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*. 30, 407–429.

²²¹ Ibid.

²²² Bubeck et al., 2013.

²²³ Ibid.

²²⁴ Azjen, I. (1991). The Theory of Planned Behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*. 50(2), pp. 179-211.

behaviour, although that does not necessarily imply taking more extensive preparatory actions.

In addition, ethnographic investigations suggest that communities which have experienced a particular type of disaster on a number of occasions develop so-called “disaster cultures or subcultures”, in which the exchange of knowledge, exercise and other preparations to the particular threat plays a central role.²²⁵ Members of these cultures or subcultures have adapted to the constancy of risk by normalising a threat and have learnt to prepare and to respond more appropriately to any particular hazard.²²⁶ It should be noted however that subcultures are often directed at only one type of crisis and therefore the community may not be able to cope with other types of crises. This therefore negates the theory that when individuals are prepared for one type of crisis they are prepared for other crisis types as well.²²⁷

Flood preparation

Recent studies of floods show mixed empirical results for the relationship between experience and preparatory action. Takao et al. found that preparedness for floods in Japan depends primarily on ownership of a home, fear of flooding and the amount of damage from previous floods rather than on previous experience with floods.²²⁸ Yet such attitudes may be of fairly recent provenance as traditionally Japanese society has exhibited strong preparatory tendencies to hazards.²²⁹ Burningham et al. arrived at similar conclusions in their study of flood preparation in the UK, arguing that experience and prior knowledge of local flood risks does not necessarily prepare today’s citizens for flood.²³¹ Platt ascribes the symptomatic disregard for risk in democratic industrial societies to what he calls the “moral hazard” whereby the more governments invest in flood defences, the more citizens expose themselves to risk by living in areas liable to floods.²³² In contrast, Bubeck et al.²³³ shows, among others, that experiences with (flood) hazards has a powerful impact on the recognition of a risk and consequently (flood) mitigation behaviour.

Hurricane Kate and Elena

Sorensen and Vogt²³⁴ argue that in the case of hurricanes and other storms, experience sometimes deters response and in others it can improve response. The authors note that Hurricane Kate led to an evacuation of the Tampa Bay area about four months after Hurricane Elena had prompted an unnecessary evacuation of the same area. Evacuation rates in the Tampa Bay area for Hurricane Kate were similar to that for Elena, despite the earlier false alarm. Others

²²⁵ Tierney, 1989.

²²⁶ Bankoff, (2003). *Cultures of Disaster: Society and Natural Hazard in the Philippines*. London: Routledge.

²²⁷ Tierney, 1989.

²²⁸ Takao, K., Motoyoshi, T., Sato, T., Fukuzondo, T., Seo, K. and S. Ikeda (2004). Factors Determining Residents' Preparedness for Floods in Modern Megalopolises: The Case of the Tokai Flood Disaster in Japan. *Journal of Risk Research*. Vol. 7 (7) pp. 775 -787.

²²⁹ Clancey, G. (2006). *Earthquake Nation: The Cultural Politics of Japanese Seismicity, 1868-1930*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

²³⁰ Sand, J. and Steven Wills (2011). Governance, Arson, and Firefighting in Edo, 1600-1868, in: G. Bankoff, U. Luebken, J. Sand, Eds., *Flammable Cities: Urban Fire and the Making of the Modern World*. Madison: University of Wisconsin Press.

²³¹ Burningham, K., J. Fielding and D. Thrush (2008). It'll Never Happen to Me: Understanding Public Awareness of Local Flood Risk. *Disasters*. Vol. 32 (2), pp. 216-238.

²³² Platt, R. (1999). *Disasters and Democracy: The Politics of Extreme Natural Events*. Washington D.C.: Island Press.

²³³ Bubeck et al., 2013.

²³⁴ Sorensen, J. and B. Vogt (2006). Interactive emergency evacuation guidebook. Last accessed on 7-1-2013. Retrieved from: <http://orise.orau.gov/csepp/documents/planning/evacuation-guidebook/index.htm>.

(source) have suggested that long-term residents of coastal areas, who experienced minor hurricanes without severe damages, become complacent, and are less likely to evacuate in subsequent events.

Gender and socio-economic status: Perry and Mushkatel note that threat awareness and preparation can be related to socio-demographic characteristics (e.g., income, education, and ethnicity).²³⁵ According to the authors non-minorities and people of higher socio-economic status are better prepared for crises than others, since minorities experience greater difficulties than non-minorities because they have lower incomes and money reserves, are more likely to be unemployed, less likely to have relevant insurances and more likely to have problems communicating with institutional providers of information about risks and post-impact relief.²³⁶ It should be noted however that taking preparatory action is not actually the same as being prepared and vice versa.^{237 238}

Floods, gender and socio-economic status

Recent studies of floods reveal mixed empirical results for the connection between gender and socio-economic status and preparation to crises. Bubeck et al. found that gender and educational level of the respondents are poor predictors of flood precautionary behaviour.²³⁹ In contrast, Burningham et al. showed that lower social classes in the UK have significant lower levels of flood risk awareness, which according to the authors might be attributed to lower levels of education and inappropriate information provision or a lack of participation in awareness-raising activities.²⁴⁰ The authors suggest that the lack of risk awareness impedes taking sufficient preparatory action to flooding. In addition, Bubeck et al. found that an individual's income had a significant influence on the structural measures taken to prepare for a flood.²⁴¹ According to the author, this finding can be explained by the substantial financial costs associated with such measures. Moreover, research on hurricane Floyd in 1998 illustrated how social-economic factors influenced the way individuals took preparatory measures.

How socio-economics affected preparation of individuals to hurricane Floyd

A study in the social dynamics after hurricane Floyd in 1998, and in particular to the community resilience in the affected American state North Carolina, demonstrated that social-economic factors influenced the individual and community vulnerabilities. Usually poor people are more vulnerable, because their houses are built on the most dangerous places in cases of floods, hurricanes, earthquakes or volcano eruptions. After hurricane Floyd the local government protected the most urbanized (and richest) areas in North Carolina by the releasing of water from reservoirs, regardless of the consequences for the citizens living on lower grounds. Furthermore the availability of the right information for the Latino Hispanic community was insufficient. In addition, because the media did not publish information in Spanish, whilst many people were aware of the arrival of a storm, they did not necessarily understand the potential consequences.

Social environment: The behaviour of neighbours, friends and family of individuals greatly influences individuals' decision to prepare for crises.²⁴² The social environment affects the way risks are perceived as well as the degree to which preparatory action is regarded possible and cost-effective.

²³⁵ Perry and Mushkatel, 1986.

²³⁶ Tierney, 1989.

²³⁷ Helsloot and Ruitenbergh, 2004.

²³⁸ Ibid.

²³⁹ Bubeck et al., 2013.

²⁴⁰ Burningham, K., J. Fielding and D. Thrush (2008). It'll Never Happen to Me: Understanding Public Awareness of Local Flood Risk. *Disasters*. Vol. 32 (2), pp. 216-238.

²⁴¹ Bubeck et al., 2013.

²⁴² Ibid.

Floods and mitigation

In the context of flood mitigation behaviour, Bubeck et al. summarised evidence showing that if the majority of homeowners in the neighbourhood implemented a flood mitigation measure, it is likely that other individuals also want to follow suit. Moreover, the authors note that the decisions of neighbours can provide important information value for someone who is considering investing in a flood-proof house, since the cost-effectiveness of such investment is hard to assess. In such a situation, Bubeck et al. argue that the measures taken by a neighbourhood provides a useful indicator of the cost-effectiveness of different types of measures.

Personality: Personality factors such as locus of control (it is in the hands of others) or fatalism (what will happen will happen regardless of what I do) is presumed to affect the preparatory actions individuals undertake. According to Sorensen and Vogt, this presumption is supported by anecdotal evidence of people who refuse to evacuate and not by systematic empirical investigation.²⁴³ Some studies have concluded fatalism diminishes taking preparatory action for earthquakes and tornados (ibid). This may explain on a micro-level differences among the preparations ordinary citizens take.

5.2.2 Warning

Some crises such as floods, extreme temperature and wildfires are accompanied by an intermediate or longer-lasting warning phase.²⁴⁴ In this phase individuals receive many forms of information. Individuals listen to the radio advising them to close windows and doors, to avoid certain areas or to even be evacuated. Neighbours and family call each other with their own information about the emerging threat. Social media channels are scanned for the latest update.^{245 246} Individuals must decide whether or not the information is trustworthy and whether the advice given is relevant to them and make decisions about what to do. The degree to which an individual takes measures relies on his or her interpretation of the situation.²⁴⁷

The way individuals interpret the situation and take action has been described in several ways. Perry and Lindell²⁴⁸ characterize this process as a four stage decision-making process: 1) risk identification: does the threat really exist?; 2) risk assessment: is protection needed?; 3) risk reduction: is protection feasible?; 4) protective response: what action to take? Mileti and Sorensen (1988) use a slightly different model and identify six stages: 1) hearing the warning; 2) understanding the contents of the warning message; 3) believing the warning is credible and accurate; 4) personalizing the warning to oneself; 5) confirming that the warning is true and others are taking heed; and 6) responding by taking (a protective) action.

Both models point to the importance of threat perception. As Perry argues: “Unless the warning recipient believes that the threat is genuine, he or she is not likely to undertake any

²⁴³ Sorensen and Vogt, 2006.

²⁴⁴ Ibid.

²⁴⁵ Scanlon, J, I. Helsloot and J. Groenendaal (2013). Putting it all together: Integrating ordinary citizens into the emergency response. *International journal of Mass Emergencies and Disasters*.

²⁴⁶ Helsloot, I. G. Bankoff and J. Groenendaal (2013). Dealing with citizen response and evacuation during large scale flooding in industrial societies. *Handbook on Drowning*. Heidelberg: Springer.

²⁴⁷ Perry, R.W. (1985). *Comprehensive Emergency Management: Evacuating Threatened Populations*. Greenwich (USA): JAI Press.

²⁴⁸ Perry, R.W. and M.K. Lindell (2003). Understanding Citizen Response to Disasters with Implications for Terrorism. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*. 11(2), pp. 51–52.

protective action”.²⁴⁹ Different variables influence the interpretation of the warning, such as the perceived reliability of the sender and prior experience of the announced threat.²⁵⁰ When the warning is considered to be noteworthy, citizens will consider the consequences of the warning to themselves and relatives. Individuals who receive information they perceive as unreliable or uncertain, will, as in ordinary life, look for confirmation and verification. This is one of the (obvious) explanations for the heavy phone traffic during crises.²⁵¹ Consequently, whether preparatory actions are taken depends inter alia on three different factors: Time available to respond to the threat; strength of family ties, generally families with strong ties hesitate longer when not all members are safe or gathered together. In evacuation situations, families often respond together, not as a collection of individuals²⁵², and lastly, concrete knowledge on how to cope with the threat.²⁵³

Man-made disasters and the social environment

The social environment of an individual plays an important role during the warning phase. Studies in the Netherlands have shown that in the case of power outages most are first informed by their neighbours, friends and family.²⁵⁴ In deciding what to do, individuals frequently rely on the actions taken by others: the social environment reinforces group norms. In a study of the Three Mile Island nuclear power plant accident, Cutter and Barnes²⁵⁵ found that among citizens who evacuated, 74% reported that their neighbours also evacuated. Among those who did not evacuate, 50% reported that their neighbours also did not evacuate. The social environment has also been found to provide emotional support and access to resources during the warning and response phase of a crisis.²⁵⁶

Warning messages from multiple sources

According to Dynes and Quarantelli²⁵⁷, individuals typically get additional warnings from personal contacts outside of their own households, sometimes even in place of other warnings, far more often in addition to the initial warning. The authors point to Hurricane Camille (1969) and tornado situations where a warning was possible: these incidents “indicate that after the initial warning, people receive information on the threat from multiple other sources, especially kin members. 26 per cent got their first indication of possible danger in a flood from friends, neighbours or relatives. Put very simply, where it is possible, people generally learn danger through and/or with known others, especially family members.”

5.2.3 Response

Individuals decide to take action in a threatening situation by applying two cognitive processes: an intuitive and analytical process. The former is rapid, associative, affectionate, automatic, emotional and unconscious. The latter is based on deliberate reasoning, algorithms and formal logic, but is much slower and calls for more effort, learning capacity and

²⁴⁹ Perry, 1985.

²⁵⁰ Helsloot and Ruitenbergh, 2004.

²⁵¹ Fitzpatrick, C. and D.S. Mileti (1994). ‘Public Risk Communication,’ in: *Disasters, Collective Behavior, and Social Organization*, Dynes, R.R. Tierney K.J. (eds), pp. 73-75.

²⁵² Kirschenbaum, A. (2006). Families and Disaster behaviour: A Reassessment of family preparedness. *International Journal of Mass Emergencies and Disasters*. Vol. 24, pp. 111-143.

²⁵³ Perry, 1985.

²⁵⁴ Helsloot, I. and R. Beerens (2009). Citizens' Response to a Large Electrical Power Outage in the Netherlands in 2007. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, 17(1), 64-68.

²⁵⁵ Cutter, S. L., & K. Barnes (1982). Evacuation behavior and Three Mile Island. *Disasters*, 2, 116-124.

²⁵⁶ Bonkiewicz, L. and R.B. Ruback (2012). The Role of the Police in Evacuations Responding to the Social Impact of a Disaster. *Police Quarterly*, 15(2), 137-156.

²⁵⁷ Dynes, R.R. and E.L. Quarantelli (1973). The family and community context of individual reactions to disaster.

consciousness.²⁵⁸ Neurobiological research and other studies have shown that both processes have their advantages and disadvantages, distortions and limitations. In situations in which the two processes point in different directions, the intuitive process often makes the difference, especially in the case of time pressure and uncertainty.²⁵⁹ This intuitive decision-making process enables individuals to respond appropriately in the situation of not having adequate preparation time or as a result of the sudden occurrence of a threat.

In the social sciences it is common acknowledged that individuals are often self-resilient during and in the aftermath of crises.^{260 261 262 263} Even without the involvement of authorities, most individuals are able to rescue themselves and sometimes, others. Nevertheless some common assumptions by authorities (and the news media) are that individuals panic, become passive and misbehave.²⁶⁴ These assumptions have been identified as ‘myths’.

Myth 1: Citizens panic during crisis

Individuals’ initial fear during a crisis is quickly replaced by concern over the safety of one’s person, family and neighbours. People generally help one another during a crisis; others leave the affected area by routes deemed safe at the time. Individuals rarely panic; if panic does occur, it usually affects only a small number of people and lasts for a short period of time.²⁶⁵

Within the academic community, there is little consensus of the definition of the term “panic”. There are basically two understandings in the scientific literature. The older usage associates panic with extreme and irrational fear; the other sees panic as a manifestation of flight behaviour in which open, social norms are discarded.²⁶⁶ In both visions there are two central themes. First, panic is regarded as irrational. This position has been criticised by those who have conducted empirical research on the behaviour of citizens in emergency situations. These researchers conclude that citizens usually behave in very constructive ways that are far from irrational, though the intent may not always be apparent to the onlooker.²⁶⁷ Second, panic is assumed to be contagious. Empirical research has demonstrated this assertion to be wrong too. Sometimes, a few individuals may panic but this sentiment almost never manifests itself more generally. Although panic seldom occurs, there are documented situations in which it may happen. Such conditions include:

- Perception of immediate and serious danger;
- Perception that only a few “escape routes” exist;
- Perception that escape routes are closing, which requires an immediate response; and
- Lack of communication.

²⁵⁸ Kahneman, D. (2003). A perspective on judgment and choice: Mapping bounded rationality. *American Psychologist* 58(9), pp. 697-720.

²⁵⁹ Slovic, Paul, Ellen Peters, Melissa L. Finucane & Donald G. MacGregor (2005). Affect, Risk and Decision Making. *Health Psychology*. 24(4), pp. S35-S40.

²⁶⁰ Dynes, R.R. (1994) Community Emergency Planning: False Assumptions and Inappropriate Analogies. *International Journal of Mass Emergencies and Disasters*. 12 (2).

²⁶¹ Perry and Lindell, 2003.

²⁶² Helsloot and Ruitenber, 2004.

²⁶³ Scanlon et al., 2013.

²⁶⁴ Dynes, 1994

²⁶⁵ Perry and Lindell, 2003.

²⁶⁶ Quarantelli, E. L. (1954). The nature and conditions of panic. *American Journal of Sociology*, 267-275.

²⁶⁷ Quarantelli, E.L. (1985). An assessment of conflicting views on mental health: the consequences of traumatic events. In *Trauma and Its Wake*, C Figley, pp. 173-218. New York: Brunner-Mazel; Helsloot, I. & H. Ruitenber (2004). Citizen Response to Disasters: a Survey of Literature and Some Practical Implications. In: *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*. 12(3), pp. 98-111.

2005, London Bombings

After the 2005 London bombings, in which 56 people died, research shows that citizens responded with “cohesion, unity, and mutual co-operation”²⁶⁸. Most people trapped in subway carriages remained calm and even calmed the few people that did experience significant stress. Citizens were also actively searching for victims and were helping those in need.²⁶⁹

1989, Flight crash Dryden, Ontario

Ordinary citizens appear to be able responding creatively to unusual situations, like in the case of the flight crash near Dryden, Ontario, on 10 March 1989: “At an earlier incident, when an Air Ontario flight crashed in deep snow near the airport of Dryden in Northern Ontario, a private citizen – he lived near the crash site – put on his snow shoes and marked a trail in a wide circle around the crash site, thus making sure no dazed survivor would wander off into the bush without that being evident.”²⁷⁰

Myth 2: Individuals are helpless and dependent

Contrary to popular belief, individuals are rarely left helpless or dependent solely on external assistance during crises. Rescue, the care of injured and even the initial recovery is largely in the hands of those most directly affected and supported by the local services that are still able to perform their functions. Even after the acute phase of a sudden crisis, individuals remain largely self-reliant. In fact, in the case of sheltering after an evacuation most individuals, sometimes more than 90 per cent, are sheltered by family, friends, unknown individuals or organisations.²⁷¹

2004, Manawatu flood

It was the community and especially the farmers who utilised pre-existing networks and their own equipment to manage the Manawatu flood of February 2004, one of the largest emergency management events in recent times in New Zealand.²⁷²

1995, Flood in the Netherlands

In 1995, inhabitants in the centre of the Netherlands evacuated certain areas spontaneously before flooding occurred. Research uncovered that most citizens moved out of their homes in an orderly fashion two days before the official evacuation order was issued. Most citizens went to family or friends by means of their own transport.²⁷³

2005, Hurricane Katrina

“In contrast to the terrible failures of government, communities, individuals and small groups responded immediately to Katrina. The community of Ville Platte exemplified the generous self-organizing capacity that always appears in disasters. They organized their ‘home-made rescue and relief efforts’ around the slogan ‘If not us, then who?’ A community of 11,000 people, with an average yearly income of only 5,300 dollar for the majority of its residents, was able to serve 5,000 displaced and traumatized victims of Katrina, inviting them to share their homes and community not as refugees or evacuees, but as ‘company’. Those with boats went to New Orleans to join ‘The Cajun Navy’. They rescued people from rooftops, picked up the dead,

²⁶⁸ Sheppard, Ben., Rubic, J.G., Wardman, J.K and Wessely, S. “Terrorism and Dispelling the Myth of a Panic Prone Public”, *Journal of Public Health Policy*, 2006, Vol. 27, pp. 219–245. [p. 235]

²⁶⁹ Ibid.

²⁷⁰ Scanlon et al., 2013.

²⁷¹ Tierney, 1989.

²⁷² Smith, W, C. Davies-Colley, A. Mackay and G. Bankoff (2011). Social Impact of the 2004 Manawatu Floods and the “Hollowing Out” of Rural New Zealand. *Disasters*.

²⁷³ Helsloot and Ruitenber, 2004.

*transported injured to trauma centres”.*²⁷⁴

2009, Turkish Airlines crash (The Netherlands)

*On February 25th 2009, a Turkish Airlines Boeing 737-800 crashed approximately 1.5 km before Amsterdam Schiphol Airport in the Netherlands. The passenger aircraft with 135 people on board crashed in to a soggy field and broke into three pieces prior to crossing a motorway. Fortunately the wreckage did not catch fire. Most passengers escaped through the emergency exits and the breaks in the aircraft frame, including some of the most heavily injured. About 25 bystanders, most of them motorists rushed to the scene and helped passengers out of the plane and brought them to a neighbouring empty farmer shelter. The less injured victims helped other passengers out of the wreckage and assisted those in the farm shelter. Some heavily injured victims, who could not be moved were encouraged by bystanders (“the ambulance will arrive within a few minutes”), opened suitcases searching for clothing to keep the victims warm, and went back into the plane to search for travel companions of heavily injured victims. Only six living victims had to be rescued by the professional emergency responders. After the injured were cared for, a farmer with a tractor with flat wagon transported the dead over the soggy field.*²⁷⁵

Myth 3: Looting occurs frequently during and after crises

Looting, remains the most persistent behavioural “myth” associated with crisis situations and especially in the case of large-scale evacuation.²⁷⁶ Sometimes foraging for much essential provisions is regarded as looting. As a result, state authorities have responded accordingly, opening fire on several notable occasions such as the Great Fire of San Francisco in 1906 and in New Orleans in 2005.²⁷⁷ Alleged incidents of looting are given inordinate media attention as are the steps taken to suppress it. The notion that crises are often followed by looting has long been contradicted by empirical evidence.²⁷⁸ In the rare cases when looting does occur, it is largely done by lone individuals from outside the community. The distinction between crises caused by natural hazards or public unrest is important in this case. The scientific literature points to a marked distinction between how individuals behave during a public disorder event and how they behave following a natural hazard: When public disorder occurs, incidents of looting may take place.²⁷⁹

Evacuation behaviour

Although individuals generally remain law-abiding, do not panic and show altruistic behaviour, they do not always fully comply with recommendations or orders from authorities. Nor do citizens always remove themselves from harm.²⁸⁰ In particular, in most evacuations, not everyone at risk or in areas in which evacuations are ordered or recommended, participate in the evacuation.

²⁷⁴ Wheatley, M.J. (2006). *Leadership and the New Science: Discovering Order in a Chaotic World*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers: San Francisco.

²⁷⁵ Scholtens, A. and J. Groenendaal (2011). *Zelfredzaamheid Tijdens de Poldercrash*. [Self-resilience during the Poldercrash]. The Hague, Netherlands: Boom Lemma Uitgevers.

²⁷⁶ Tierney K., C. Bevc and E. Kuligowski (2006). Metaphors Matter: Disaster Myths, Media Frames and their Consequences in Hurricane Katrina. *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*. Vol. 604, pp. 57-81.

²⁷⁷ Solnit, R. (2009). *A Paradise Built in Hell: The Extraordinary Communities that Arise in Disaster*. New York: Viking.

²⁷⁸ Quarantelli, 1954.

²⁷⁹ Tierney et al., 2006.

²⁸⁰ Bonkiewicz, L. and R.B. Ruback (2012). The Role of the Police in Evacuations Responding to the Social Impact of a Disaster. *Police Quarterly*, 15(2), 137-156.

Sorensen and Vogt provide several explanations for this observed non-compliance, such as not having access to transportation, being mobility impaired, not being able to afford to evacuate, needing to work, needing to provide care, thinking one's location is safe.²⁸¹ Another explanation for non-compliant behaviour is the “cry wolf” effect. Cry wolf effects are defined by Sorensen and Vogt as the non-compliance with warning behaviour that might be expected from individuals who have responded to too many “false alarm” warning messages. Finally, “warning fatigue” and the inappropriateness of warning messages for special populations with limited sight or hearing are also noted by the authors as possible explanations for non-compliance.²⁸²

According to Sorensen and Vogt, evacuation rates vary for different types of crisis.²⁸³ Evacuation rates are very high for most hazardous material accidents, where compliance according to the authors may be in the high 90% range. Evacuation rates are typically low for slow onset events such as riverine floods. Evacuation rates vary in severe weather incidents, such as hurricanes and tropical storms, depending on the strength of the storm and location.

A variable which affects individuals' decision to evacuate is the presence of pets or other animals such as livestock.

1985, Hurricane Elena

In Hurricane Elena, a tropical storm that affected parts of the United States Gulf Coast in August and September 1985, it was found that 25% of evacuees left their pets at home while they were gone. Most evacuees either took their pets to a friend or relative. The 11 % of evacuees who took their pets to shelters left the animals in vehicles for the duration of the stay.²⁸⁴ In a flood evacuation, Heath found that half of the pet owners evacuated with their pets and the other half did not.²⁸⁵ According to Sorensen and Vogt in a protracted evacuation or one in which toxic fumes are involved, leaving pets behind could be a significant problem as premature reentry by evacuees could further place individuals at risk.²⁸⁶ The authors discuss different studies in which individuals routinely returned to their homes to care for livestock. In a chemical crisis, it was found that 60% of the evacuees had dogs and cats. Of those, 49% evacuated with their pets, 41% initially left them home but later attempted to rescue them, and only 10% left them home without a rescue attempt.

Situational altruism

To understand individual behaviour in crisis situations, and the overall urge to help others, it is helpful to use Dynes concept of “situational altruism”.²⁸⁷ A crisis situation is so specific and extraordinary that according to Dynes existing forms of individual and collective altruism no longer suffice. For example: in the aftermath of an earthquake people may not be able to visit a hospital or depend on the police. There is a distinctly new situation “where new victims have been created and there is doubt that the existing institutional resources [such as hospitals or the police] can deal with their needs”.²⁸⁸ As a result, people have a renewed sense of helping others.

²⁸¹ Sorensen and Vogt, 2006.

²⁸² Ibid.

²⁸³ Ibid.

²⁸⁴ Sorensen and Vogt, 2006.

²⁸⁵ Heath, S. E., P.H. Kass, A.M. Beck and L.T. Glickman (2001). Risk factors for pet evacuation failure after a slow-onset disaster. *Journal of the American Veterinary Association*, 218, 1905-1910.

²⁸⁶ Sorensen and Vogt, 2006.

²⁸⁷ Dynes, R.R. (1994). *Situational Altruism: Toward an Explanation Of Pathologies in Disaster Assistance*, paper presented at XIIIth World Congress of Sociology, Bielefeld

²⁸⁸ Ibid.

Dynes suggests situational altruism is facilitated by (1) the idea that there is a significant negative change in the “situation” of others (i.e. through media reports people come to understand that others are in a bad situation and are in need of help), (2) a shift in normative patterns (value priorities shift towards greater emphasis on helping victims) and (3) changes in the social structure.²⁸⁹ Dynes identifies three significant changes in the social structure:

- 1) There is often a short term “mass assault” of emergency response in which “many individuals and organizations enter the emergency social system”.
- 2) Individuals immediately “activate kin relationships”. Those in need rely on their friends and family for shelter and other help. But relatives actively inform themselves of the situation of their family as well. In the 2007 California Wildfires, Sutton et al. found that people used various forms of media to stay in touch with their family (mobile phones, social media, etc.)²⁹⁰
- 3) Local organisations (such as church groups) or volunteer-based organisations such as the Red Cross often offer a great deal of help as well.

Helsloot and Ruitenbergh argue that situational altruism and other forms of pro-social behaviour are actually so abundant that governments should expect to encounter it one way or another.²⁹¹

1985, The Mexico City earthquake

The Disaster Research Centre of the University of Delaware found in a study after the Mexico City earthquake in 1985 that at least 10% of the total city population was involved with volunteer work. That means: no less than 2 million volunteers. While official reports stated the earthquake killed 4541 people, the real number of deadly victims is estimated at 10.000 to 35.000. Especially in the first hours after the incident, when emergency teams were not optimal organized yet, the local population had an important role in supporting and saving victims. This example shows that, besides planning their own crisis organisation, authorities have to prepare and facilitate support within the community.

5.2.4 Recovery and aftermath

Time and again research reveals that most individuals affected by crisis situations will develop relatively little psychosocial complaints and maintain normal levels of functioning.²⁹²
²⁹³

The degree to which individuals develop psychological complaints after a crisis situation depends on multiple factors. The ability to find meaning in life, the sense of being able to influence life and the outcome of events and the idea that positive and negative experiences can be useful – that is hardiness – are among the main factors that determine the extent to which individuals can cope with crises.²⁹⁴ Another factor is the extent to which individuals

²⁸⁹ Ibid.

²⁹⁰ Sutton, J., L. Palen and I. Shklovski (2008). 'Backchannels on the Front Lines: Emergent Uses of Social Media in the 2007 Southern California Wildfires', Proceedings of the 5th International ISCRAM Conference – Washington, DC, USA, May 2008

²⁹¹ Helsloot and Ruitenbergh, 2004.

²⁹² Bonanno, G. A. (2004). *Loss, Trauma and Human Resilience: have we underestimated the human capacity to thrive after extremely aversive events?* American Psychologist, vol. 59, pp 20- 28.

²⁹³ Ibid.

²⁹⁴ Hoijtink, L. M., J.H.M. te Brake and M.L.A. Dücker (2011). Resilience Monitor.

have a good functioning and supportive social networks also affects the ability to cope with high impact situations. This can, for instance, consist of family, friends, acquaintances, colleagues and or neighbours and offers a so called safety net whenever the feeling emerges of being unable to cope with the consequences of a stressful situation. It provides the impression that one does not have to deal with the dramatic situation alone, which positively affects psychosocial functioning.²⁹⁵ According to Hoijtink et al.²⁹⁶, socio-economic characteristics such as gender, age, income, education, household composition and ethnicity are also related to the degree in which people can overcome a shock. According to Norris and Elrod, most vulnerable people are mothers with small children who belong to an ethnic minority and have lower education.²⁹⁷ The influence of ethnicity is still unclear, though it is generally assumed that being an ethnic minority has a negative influence on individual's ability to cope with crises.²⁹⁸ Likewise, the influence of religion or spirituality to crisis coping behaviour is also ambiguous²⁹⁹, especially as Pargament et al³⁰⁰ explain that some people develop positive coping mechanisms (i.e., God wants me to protect myself) and others negative coping mechanisms (i.e., whatever will happen will happen).

5.2.5 Individual dynamics in typical crisis situations

There are a multitude of factors as to why individuals prepare themselves and act in a particular manner during the warning, response and aftermath phase for different types of crisis. Consequently, different conclusions can be drawn.

Firstly, in many cases individuals do not deliberately take preparatory action to crisis situations. Crises are regarded as rare events and the chance of becoming involved in such an event is often perceived to be very low. The degree to which individuals are adequately prepared for crises seems to be most determined by the skills, knowledge and resources that they possess in ordinary life.

Second, several factors may enhance or hinder the degree to which individuals are able and willing to prepare themselves to the threat, whether it is in the non-warning or the warning phase. First, the nature of the threat affects the response to threats. Highly visible threats will cause a more swift response by individuals than less visible threats. Threats that can be easily recalled from similar instances will gain more attention than threats that are less easily recalled. But independent from the threat itself, socio-economic factors, the social environment and the personality of the individual may also enhance or hamper preparation and response. Ultimately, the nature of the threat and the background of the individual are key to determining whether individuals take preparatory action and are actually prepared for the crises.

Third, regardless of the crisis type, whether it concerns man-made disasters or floods, individuals tend to behave altruistically and rationally, rather than typically “mythical”

²⁹⁵ Fukuyama, F. (2001). *Social capital, Civil Society and Development*. Third World Quarterly, Vol. 22, No. 1, pp. 7-20.

²⁹⁶ Hoijtink et al., 2011.

²⁹⁷ Norris, F.H. and C.L. Elrod (2006). *Psychological consequences of disaster: a review of past literature*. Chapter 2 In: Norris, F.H.; Galea, S.; Friedman, M.J.; Watson, P.J. (eds). *Methods for Disaster Mental Health Research*. New York: The Guilford Press.

²⁹⁸ Ibid.

²⁹⁹ Hoijtink et al., 2011.

³⁰⁰ Pargament, K.I., H.G. Koenig and L.M. Perez (2000). The many methods of religious coping: Development and initial validation of the RCOPE. *J. Clin. Psychol.*, 56: 519–543.

behaviour (e.g., becoming helpless, dependent or resorting to looting). Without the assistance and help of individual citizens, professional responders and organisations are unable to mitigate the consequences of crisis situations. Even in the aftermath of crisis situations individuals tend to watch after each other and provide help. Individuals are more self-reliant than many contingency plans expect and emergency responders prepare for. Only in very specific situations such, as cases of public unrest and public order incidents, individuals may behave irrationally and employ disobedient behaviour.

Finally, we can conclude that the self-reliant behaviour of individuals can, and should be supported by timeless and deliberate communication. If the risks (likelihood and consequences) are explicitly and swiftly communicated – before and during the manifestation of the threat, and individuals are called upon to take responsibility for their own safety, as well as others, this may drive individuation to act appropriately and in a self-reliant manner. If this is done, responding organisations and agencies and focus their attention on those that are most vulnerable.

5.3 ORGANISATIONAL DYNAMICS

Having discussed the individual dynamics in crisis situations, it is equally important to determine the extent to which organisations play a role in crisis situations. As the previous discussion on situational altruism already has shown that citizens feel the need to help those in need, often this help is not organised individually, but by groups and organisations.

In this sub-section partners will focus on emergent phenomena in organisational dynamics rather than on regular crisis management organisations, as crisis management and emergency management organisations will be the focus of the report on “*The role of emergency response agencies in crises*” (COSMIC Task 1.3), leading to Deliverable 1.3 (Report on the role of main stakeholders in crisis situations) and Deliverable 1.4 (Model of crisis concepts and dynamics).

Based on the examples we discussed in this sub-section it is difficult to link the organisational dynamics to the typical crisis situations detailed in Chapter 2 of this report, as organisational dynamics, as described in the scientific literature, are quite general and abstract. In fact, it is very likely that all of the organisations we have described here will be present in one of the typical crisis situations in one form or another.

5.3.1 Preparation

Much of the organisational preparation for crisis situations is conducted by emergency management agencies. As previously discussed, their preparation efforts will be detailed extensively in the report in Deliverable 1.3 (Report on the role of main stakeholders in crisis situations). Accordingly, partners will consider how other groups and organisations prepare for different types of crises.

Private organisations, such as businesses, have historically not put much emphasis on preparation.³⁰¹ Arguably this lack of preparation by businesses is similar to the explanation for citizens primarily preparing for certain types of crisis situations. If citizens do not feel the

³⁰¹ Webb, Gary R., Kathleen J. Tierney and James M. Dahlhamer, “Businesses and disasters: empirical patterns and unanswered questions”, *Natural Hazards Review*, Vol. 1, Issue 2, 2000, pp. 83 – 90.

need to prepare it is very likely that organisations which are comprised of the same citizens do not feel the need either. If businesses take preparedness measures this is often in the form of stocking first aid supplies or teaching their employees first aid.³⁰² Few organisations have contingency plans in the case of crisis situations.³⁰³

However, according to Webb et al, if we look at the long-term recovery of businesses after a crisis situation “previous disaster experience, level of disaster preparedness, and use of external sources of aid were not found to significantly affect the long-term economic viability of businesses”.³⁰⁴ Rather, the economic sector that a business operates in, the physical impact of the disaster and the influence (perceived or actual) of the disaster on the broader economic outlook are among the main determinants of long-term recovery of a business.

5.3.2 Response

Organisations can take many shapes and sizes: the most common organisational form in crisis response situations is the emergency management agency, such as the police or the fire brigade.³⁰⁵ These types of organisations are heavily institutionalised and have their own organisational culture, modus operandi, etc. Citizens, on the other hand, sometimes group together in a volunteer fashion (e.g., by providing disaster aid or by organising ad hoc search and rescue operations) or are forced on each other to survive a dangerous situation by helping each other.³⁰⁶ Consequently, the organisational dynamics of these types of organisations vary greatly.

		T A S K S	
		Regular	Non-regular
ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE	Old (Normal)	I Established	III Extending
	New (Ad Hoc)	II Expanding	IV Emergent

Figure 1. Disaster Organization Typology.

Figure 23: Disaster Organization Typology.³⁰⁷

To make sense of these different kinds of organisational dynamics, Dynes and Quarantelli³⁰⁸ offer four types of “organized behavioural responses”³⁰⁹: established, expanding and organisations extending and emergent groups. This typology basically states “that organized

³⁰² Ibid.

³⁰³ Ibid.

³⁰⁴ Webb et al., 2002.

³⁰⁵ Quarantelli, E.L., (1993), ‘Community Crises: An Exploratory Comparison of the Characteristics and Consequences of Disasters and Riots,’ *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, 1(2).

³⁰⁶ Scanlon et al., 2013.

³⁰⁷ Harrauld, John R. (1990), “Feedback from the field. Contingency planning: building the infrastructure for crisis decision making”, *International Journal of Mass Emergencies and Disasters*, Vol. 8, Issue 2, pp. 137 - 150.

³⁰⁸ Quarantelli, Enrico Louis "Organizations Under Stress", Pp. 3-19 in *Symposium Emergency Operations*, edited by R. Bricton. Santa Monica, CA.: System Development Corporation.

³⁰⁹ Quarantelli, 1993.

behaviour can involve either regular or non-regular tasks and that the structures to carry out these tasks can either exist before a disaster or come into being after impact”.³¹⁰ The typology has since been expanded by authors such as Drabek³¹¹, Bardo³¹², Wachtendorf and Kendra³¹³ and Voorhees.³¹⁴

Type 1: Established organisations (with regular tasks and old structures)

An established organisational response is present in most countries in the form of emergency agencies or organisations which are specifically tasked with disaster management.³¹⁵ Often, as Dynes argues, these established organisations work with “a myopic view of the emergency period”.³¹⁶ An example of the involvement of established organisations is that of the “city police force directing traffic around the impact zone after a tornado has struck a community” or the fire brigade putting out fires in response to an earthquake.

Type 2: Expanding organisations (with regular tasks and new structures)

A second type is an expanding organisation with regular tasks. These organisations are “often the result of community and organizational planning”³¹⁷. Prior to a crisis situation they exist mostly on paper. A good example is that actions of Red Cross Volunteers “running a shelter after a hurricane.”³¹⁸

2005, Hurricane Katrina

“Local traditional religious groups accustomed to providing food and other help to disadvantaged people on a daily basis in churches and mosques suddenly and unexpectedly had to take on and train many volunteers or to provide new kinds of services.”³¹⁹

Type 3: Extending organisations (with non-regular tasks and old structures)

The third type is an extending (existing) organisation which “undertakes non-regular tasks”. Dynes provides an example of a construction company which digs through debris during a rescue operation. Another example of this type behaviour was present during Hurricane Katrina (2005):

³¹⁰ Rodríguez, Havidán, Joseph Trainor and Enrico Louis Quarantelli, "Rising to the Challenges of a Catastrophe: The Emergent and Prosocial Behavior following Hurricane Katrina", *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, Vol. 604, March 2006, pp. 82 – 101.

³¹¹ Drabek, Thomas E., *The Professional Emergency Manager: Structures and Strategies for Success*. Institute of Behavioral Science, University of Colorado, Boulder Colorado, 1987.

³¹² Bardo, John W., "Organizational Response to Disaster: A Typology of Adaptation and Change", Vol. 3, Issue 2 and 3, September 1978, pp. 87–104.

³¹³ Wachtendorf, Tricia and James M. Kendra (2004), “Considering Convergence, Coordination and Social Capital in Disasters”, *Presentation to the Canadian Risk and Hazards Network 1st Annual Symposium Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada*, November 19, 2004.

³¹⁴ Voorhees, William R., "New Yorkers Respond to the World Trade Center Attack: An Anatomy of an Emergent Volunteer Organization", *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, Vol. 16, Issue 1, March 2008, pp. 3 - 13.

³¹⁵ Olsson, Stefan (ed.), *Crisis Management in the European Union, Cooperation in the Face of Emergencies*, Springer Verlag, Heidelberg, 2009; Wendling, Cecile, *The European Union Response to Emergencies: A Sociological Neo-Institutionalist Approach*, European University Institute, Florence, 2009; Quarantelli, Enrico Louis, “Disaster Planning, Emergency Management and Civil Protection: The Historical Development of Organized Efforts To Plan For and To Respond To Disasters”, *Disaster Research Centre, Preliminary Papers*; 301, 2000.

³¹⁶ Dynes, 1990.

³¹⁷ Scanlon et al., 2013.

³¹⁸ Dynes, Russell R. and B. Aguirre (1979). Organizational Adaption to Crises: Mechanism of Coordination and Structural Change. *Disasters* (3), pp. 71-74.

³¹⁹ Rodriguez et al., 2006, p. 96.

1998, Swissair Airplane Crash

“When Swissair 111 crashed into the Atlantic Ocean off Peggy’s Cove, Nova Scotia, the first responders were fishermen who immediately headed out to sea to search for survivors. What they found was aircraft debris and pieces of bodies. (Only one body was recovered relatively intact.) Within half an hour a Royal Canadian Navy ship arrived on scene. The ship contacted the fishing boats, asked them to line up so the area could be searched systemically using grid patterns and told them to bring everything they recovered to her, not to shore: she used helicopters to fly the recovered bodies and debris to an Air Force hangar in Shearwater. The fishing boats had started out on their own but were soon an integral part of emergency response”.

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Type 4: Emergent groups (with new tasks and new structures)

The fourth and final type of organisation is an emergent group. Emergent groups are present in most crisis situations, but are very different in comparison with the other- types. They have “no pre-existing structures such as group membership, tasks, roles or expertise that can be identified ex ante”.³²¹ More specifically emergent groups can be defined as “emergent response groups as collectives of individuals who use non-routine resources and activities to apply to non-routine domains and tasks, using non-routine organisational arrangements”.³²²

1958, Pennsylvania Snow Storm Entrapment

“On March 19-20, 1958, 800 persons found themselves trapped in a restaurant on the Pennsylvania Turnpike when snow made travel impossible. The travellers were a mix of races and ages and occupation but not a cross-section of society – many were young healthy truck drivers. Although there was ambulance present there were no police or firefighters and the leadership role was taken by a physician, some military personnel and some traveling salesmen. The ordinary citizens did have communications with the outside world – the telephones were working – and the food supply proved adequate – though the restaurant did run out of bread. However, the emergent leaders arranged for the restaurant to be divided into areas – for example one part was set aside for child care, another for smoking – and assigned tasks to specific people. Once the turnpike was re-opened, the emergent group of ordinary citizens disbanded. The entire response though the short-lived emergency was handled by ordinary people.”³²³

It is no surprise that the nature of emergent groups is difficult to characterise: “It is impossible to predict which organizations will and will not engage in disaster response; what tasks, people, and knowledge are needed; and how expertise will be coordinated in an emergent group.”³²⁴ Furthermore, “research has found that emergent response groups have unclear and fluid boundaries; fleeting and unclear membership; unclear, fluid, and dispersed leadership; highly unstable task definitions and assignments as environmental conditions continuously change; and geographic dispersion that makes communication difficult.”³²⁵

*Organisational dynamics in emergent groups***2001, 9/11 (Emergent groups)**

It began with a single person asking rescue workers what they needed to do their job. That

³²⁰ Scanlon, Joseph and Chris Stoney. *Forensics if Necessary: Similarities and Changes in Canadian Mass Death Incidents*. <http://www.crhnet.ca/resources/onlineBook/Scanlon.pdf>

³²¹ Majchrzak, Anna, Sirkka L. Jarvenpaa and Andrea B. Hollingshead, "Coordinating Expertise Among Emergent Groups Responding to Disasters", *Organization Science*, Vol. 18, Issue 1, January/February 2007, pp. 147 - 161.

³²² Ibid.

³²³ Scanlon et al., 2013.

³²⁴ Majchrzak et al., 2007.

³²⁵ Ibid.

person then solicited the needed items from local merchants and redistributed them to the workers at Ground Zero. This process was repeated by many others and soon a temporary site was established at Pier 40 to supply the Ground Zero rescue workers. [The site was usually called Clarkson Village] Over the next 2 weeks, several hundred persons volunteered to help in this effort. Participants have suggested that during the 2-week, 24/7 effort well over a thousand New York City residents volunteered their services. The number of volunteers is significant given the lack of affiliation or coordination with official disaster relief organizations. The effort was home-grown out of the needs of immediate post 9/11 attack.’³²⁶

To provide a better understanding of emergent citizen groups in crisis situations Voorhees’ provides an analysis of the Clarkson Village volunteers. Voorhees identifies five organisational characteristics present in emergent groups:

- 1) An emergent group structure is necessarily ad hoc. Nevertheless volunteers quickly develop routines and procedures so they can work together better. These rules are not strictly enforced (it is even frowned upon when volunteers order other volunteers to perform specific tasks), but there is a general sense that people should adhere to them. An example Voorhees provides is that safety vests were handed out to those volunteers who worked close to a road. As more and more volunteers arrived people were required to register (by other volunteers) so as to make sure no one could steal supplies.
- 2) One of the “basic tasks” of an emergent group is to quickly ensure organisational legitimacy. Without legitimacy an emergent group can be sent away by regular emergency services or other authorities. Also “consensus on the organization's goals will be problematic and ultimately the organizing principles of the organization will be poorly defined”. The Clarkson Village Volunteers were, in an early stage of the aftermath, able to supply aid and supplies to the official rescue workers. As a result the New York Police and other municipal organisations made sure that they could stay in the area they set up in.
- 3) One of the difficult aspects in an emergent group is that of organisational communication. In the Clark Village group a communication system developed itself when several “semi-permanent” volunteers started to recognize each other. These volunteers eventually “controlled most of the intra-organizational communication channels”.
- 4) A (hierarchical) leadership structure emerges after a certain period of time. In the Clarkson Village group it was based both on expertise (e.g. a cook took charge of the kitchen area, and people sought out his advice) and seniority. The volunteers who were present most often were perceived as having more legitimate power than other volunteers. The latter point is closely related to that fact that many semi-permanent volunteers controlled a lot of the communication channels.
- 5) An emergent group has “an organic, evolving structure”. In it the contribution of volunteers is constantly shifting. People are going home to get rest, or people arrive because they want to help out. As long as the aid effort continued to develop the organisational structure of the Clarkson Village group grew as well. This was amongst other reasons fostered by the fact that many more institutionalised groups, such as churches etc., started helping out.

Voorhees suggests that these characteristics will be present in one form or another in most emergent groups.³²⁷

³²⁶ Ibid.

³²⁷ Ibid.

5.3.3 Recovery and aftermath

In the recovery phase of a crisis the organisational dynamics are very similar to the response phase. Often, there is a larger presence of Type 1 organisations (e.g., police and fire brigade), but depending on the size of the crisis situation Type 2 (e.g., volunteers of the Red Cross), Type 3 (e.g., companies that initiate rescue operations) and emergent groups are also present. One of the reasons for the presence of all the types of organisations lies in the fact that most communities aren't very often struck by disasters. There is therefore no need to task specific organisations with a possible recovery effort. Sometimes a more formal recovery plan exists in certain communities and countries, but the unpredictable nature of a crisis situation basically allows no planning as to whether the organisations tasked with recovery will be able to perform their tasks.

Wachtendorf and Kendra³²⁸ suggest that groups such as the Clarkson Village volunteers often become institutionalised and become integrated with future traditional crisis management recovery and preparation efforts. Citizens also organise themselves in response to a lack of recovery efforts. For example, after the 1994 Northridge Earthquake a number of citizens felt they didn't receive the help they needed.³²⁹

In short, in the response and recovery phase of a crisis, organisations and citizens cooperate in new organisational structures to face the challenges they are confronted with.

5.3.4 Organisational dynamics in typical crisis situations

It appears to be very difficult to predict what kind of behaviour organisations and groups will exhibit, largely because each crisis situation consists of many different and sometimes distinct variables. As such, citizens and groups are required to respond differently to each new disaster. Nevertheless, it can be argued that the preparation phase will be (mostly) executed by Type 1 organisations (e.g., emergency services, etc.) and the other types of organisations are present in the other phases of each typical crisis situation. Partners have found that it is likely that there will be more Type 2 (e.g., volunteers of the Red Cross), Type 3 (e.g., companies that initiate rescue operations) organisations and emergent groups when a crisis situation is heavier and longer. If emergency agencies are not able to cope with the impact of a particular large-scale disaster, it can be expected that other types of organisations and groups will fill the gap.

5.4 SOCIETAL DYNAMICS

In this sub-section, partners will examine the societal dynamics before, during and after a crisis situation.

³²⁸ Wachtendorf, T. & Kendra, J.M. (2004), Considering Convergence, Coordination and Social Capital in Disasters, Presentation to the Canadian Risk and Hazards Network 1St Annual Symposium Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada November 19, 2004

³²⁹ Bolin, R. and Lois Stanford, "The Northridge Earthquake: Community-based Approaches to Unmet Recovery Needs", *Disasters*, Vol. 22, Issue 1, March 1998, pp. 21 - 38.

5.4.1 Preparation

Without sufficient *information and communication* it is impossible for a society (or community within a society) to prepare itself for worst-case scenarios. In the preparation phase of a crisis risks and their consequences have to be communicated.

Longstaff endorses the importance of the distribution of information preceding to and during a crisis, but only if it is “correct and correctly transmitted”.³³⁰ People can ask themselves about the danger of an impending flood or hurricane; do they have to evacuate or must windows and doors being closed? The reliability of the information, as well as the person distributing information is of great importance. In developing countries local information sources are often trusted more than the official authorities: “A trusted source of information is the most important resilience asset that any individual or group can have.” The resilience of a community increases if communication systems (like telecom networks and ICT) continue, regardless of the confrontation with a disaster. In that sense the growing use of social media is an interesting development. Another aspect that stresses the importance of communication during a crisis is meaning making, one of the important crisis leadership tasks, described by Boin et al. as “the production of facts, images and spectacles aimed at influencing socio-political uncertainty and conflict generated by crises”.³³¹

If we distinguish between flash crises (a fast developing crisis, such as a terrorist attack or chemical explosion) and creeping crises (a slow-burning and slow-developing crisis), citizens and governments have the ability to more readily adequately prepare themselves in the latter case. Societal preparation for the flash crises is much more difficult.

The Moffat Community Flood Resilience Group

The risk of flooding from the river Annan that the local community faces, encouraged citizens in Scotland to initiate the Moffat Community Flood Resilience Group. In cooperation, and with support from the Scottish Flood Forum, concerned citizens were able to take a pro-active role, by checking, monitoring and notifying the local government if a drain needed to be unblocked. Symbolically the residents “adopted” a drain. They mapped ownership of the local riverbank and spotted decaying or risky trees and alerted the owners. With the use of a map they addressed risks and helped agencies to understand why flooding occurred in certain areas. Two meteorologists, living in the Scottish community, were able to interpret the SEPA flood warnings using their knowledge of the local environment and were able to advise the community on likely local impacts. One of the most important results is that the group (and so the community) gained more insight in the possible threats and how to resist them.³³²

5.4.2 Response

In the response to a crisis two societal dynamics can be distinguished. First, as previously illustrated, Dynes has shown that situational altruism facilitates social support. The willingness of the members of a community, family, friends and other relatives to help results

³³⁰ Longstaff, P. (2005). *Security, resilience, and communication in unpredictable environments such as terrorism, natural disasters, and complex technology*. Syracuse, New York: Author.

³³¹ Boin, A., P't Hart, E. Stern and B. Sundelius (2005). *The politics of crisis management, public leadership under pressure*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

³³² IFRC (2012). *Understanding community resilience and program factors that strengthen them. A comprehensive study of Red Cross Red Crescent Societies tsunami operation*.

in “the mobilisation of social support”.³³³ However, when it becomes visible that the need for support and assistance is much higher than the availability of resources, the morality of the supporting volunteers will decrease quickly, resulting in a “deterioration of social support”. Social support can be distinguished between three aspects: *received support*, *social embeddedness* and *perceived support*. The mobilization of social support can be coupled to received support, while (a lack of) social embeddedness and perceived support are more in the sphere of the deterioration of social support.

When help is needed the most, supporters provide it the most. Immediately after a disaster occurs former boundaries, as between races, incomes and social classes, disappear momentarily. Terms such as ‘altruistic community’³³⁴, ‘democracy of distress’³³⁵, ‘heroic and honeymoon phases’³³⁶, ‘therapeutic community’³³⁷, ‘post-disaster utopia’³³⁸ and ‘stage of euphoria’³³⁹ are connected with this phase.

Quarantelli describes how the spontaneous reactions after a disaster result in a heart-warming realm; a lot of individuals become one and the society seems to be one family.³⁴⁰ The solidarity between community members will increase and because of the emergence of *new prominent* problems existing conflicts within a society disappear. The best metaphor to compare the process of ‘first aid’ after a disaster with is the pyramid. First victims rely on their family members; second there is an important role for friends, neighbours and organisations such as churches and social groups. After a few hours or days the official services replace the first responders and from that moment they will provide aid. Emerging support is provided by the rule of relative needs, but both in the case of aid from the community and when aid is offered by authorities, the process described will not be able to avoid inequities in the delivery of assistance.³⁴¹ That is, pre-existing relationships will often mean that some groups of victims have relative advantages in receiving aid compared to other groups.

Although the development of social support seems to be sufficient to provide the first aid needed, it will not be sufficient in the period after the first hours. The first reason is that the need (and the expectations) for support exceeds the availability, with the consequence that victims become disillusioned because of the lack of support. When the proportion of victims to non-victims increases (one of the characteristics of natural hazards), psychological and social effects (such as stress) emerge more and more. Not only do the most vulnerable victims expect support, but so do the victims that remain relatively secure. Second, social support may not remain within a community, rather it may phase out over time. This is the period of

³³³ Kaniasty, K. & F.H. Norris. (2004). Social support in the aftermath of disasters, catastrophes, and acts of terrorism: altruistic, overwhelmed, uncertain, antagonistic, and patriotic communities. In: *Bioterrorism, Psychological and Public Health Interventions*. Cambridge. Chapter 12, pp. 200-229.

³³⁴ Kutak, R.I. (1938). The sociology of crises: the Louisville flood of 1937. In *Social Forces*. 17, pp. 66-72.

³³⁵ Wallace, A. (1957). *Tornado in Worcester*. Disaster Study Number Three. Washington, DC: Committee on Disaster Studies, National Academy of Sciences: National Research Council.

³³⁶ Wolfenstein, M. (1957). *Disaster: A Psychological Essay*. Glencoe: Free Press.

³³⁷ Fritz, C.E. (1961). Disasters. In *Contemporary Social Problems*, R.K. Merton and R.A. Nisbet, pp. 651-694. New York: Harcourt.

³³⁸ Barton, A.M. (1969). *Communities in Disaster*. Garden City, NJ: Doubleday.

³³⁹ Frederick, C. (1980). Effects of natural vs. human-induced violence upon victims. *Evaluation and Change, special issue*, pp. 71-75.

³⁴⁰ Quarantelli, E.L. (1985). An assessment of conflicting views on mental health: the consequences of traumatic events. In *Trauma and Its Wake*, C Figley, pp. 173-218. New York: Brunner-Mazel.

³⁴¹ Kaniasty, K. & F.H. Norris. (1995). In search of altruistic community: patterns of social support mobilization following Hurricane Hugo. *American Journal of Community Psychology*. 23(4), pp. 447-477.

the deterioration of support. An important factor is the disruption of the relationships within a society, caused by reasons such as death, injuries and necessary removals.³⁴² Sometimes a disaster means the end of social contacts between former neighbours. After hurricane Katrina and the flooding of New Orleans in 2005, many people were forced to move to other states in the USA. The third dislocating effect of a disaster is that social activities, and so the social cohesion, are damaged. “Simply because physical environments, settings and places instrumental for maintaining a sense of continuity and interpersonal contacts are damaged or destroyed.”³⁴³ The feeling of being one community will reduce. Furthermore it is imaginable that within a society, conflicts arise that can be attributed to the disaster. The interpersonal relationships become more sensitive if the former standards are in stake.

5.4.3 Recovery

Nel and Righarts stress the linkage between natural disasters and the increasing risk of violent civil conflicts.³⁴⁴ As a result of the “proximate and structural macro-social effects” of disasters, motives, incentives and opportunities for conflicts become visible in the society. Where interpersonal contacts and relationships are strengthened in the preparation phase and response phase, because people have to respond to a disaster together; after a crisis the society can disintegrate as a result of different and sometimes conflicting positions and interests. ‘T Hart argues that crises contain always “multiple levels of conflict”.³⁴⁵ The opinions of individuals within a society of a crisis differ. In his research on the importance of symbols and rituals of crisis, he stresses that, in the recovery phase, different groups of individuals within a society assess a crisis in different ways. In part, this may be attributed to their income, social status and position in society before and after the crisis, consequently, different causes and consequences will be indicated. Individuals will discuss the best solutions and the way in which will be dealt with the new situation, resulting in new *winners* and *losers*. As a consequence, whilst the community may have been in unity prior to a crisis, as a result of a crisis, this unity can disintegration, resulting in a situation of different groups with more reluctance and aversion than previously.

As argued by Landau and Saul, following their experience following the terrorist attacks on the 11 September 2001, meaning making can be an important instrument in reaching a common understanding within a community, which in turn can influence the ability of a community to recover from a crisis.³⁴⁶

Kaniasty and Norris summarise the different concepts that form the societal dynamics in periods around a disaster in the figure, depicted below.³⁴⁷

³⁴² Kaniasty and Norris, 2004.

³⁴³ Kaniasty and Norris, 2004.

³⁴⁴ Nel, P. & M. Righarts (2008). Natural Disasters and the Risk of Violent Civil Conflict. In: *International Studies Quarterly*. 52(1), pp. 159-185.

³⁴⁵ Hart, P. (1993). Symbols, Rituals and Power: The Lost Dimensions of Crisis Management, in: *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*. 1(1), pp. 36-50.

³⁴⁶ Landau, J. & Saul, J. (2004). Facilitating family and community resilience in response to major disaster. In F. Walsh and M. McGoldrick (Eds.), *Living beyond loss*. New York: Norton.

³⁴⁷ Kaniasty and Norris, 2004.

Figure 24: Forming concepts for societal dynamics.

5.4.4 Communities and community resilience

Where the definition of individual behaviour is relative clear, the definition of a *community* is not less so. McMillan and Chavis define a community as: ‘*a feeling that members have of belonging, a feeling that members matter to one another and to the group, and a shared faith that members’ needs will be met through their commitment to be together.*’³⁴⁸ Especially in periods of and after crises, communities can assist people by reacting and respond in the right manner and by rebuilding the society afterwards.

The community can be considered both as a geographic territory and as an emotional attachment to a place. The geographic factor distinguishes if a community is ‘local’ or not. Whether or not individuals are resilient depends not only on their personal characteristics and skills, but also on the capacities of the community wherein citizens live. Communities are built up out of relationships between citizens and neighbours, the presence of voluntary groups (sometimes organisations) and dialogues between citizens and local authorities and can both facilitate and constrain resilience of their individual members. But a strong community does not arise from nowhere. The capacities that can be attributed to the possible resilience of a community are economic development, social capital, information and communication, and community competence.³⁴⁹ These capacities are partially the same as the characteristics distinguished by the International Red Cross of a safe and resilient community. Accordingly, within this report, community resilience refers to “*A process linking a set of networked adaptive capacities to a positive trajectory of functioning and adaptation in constituent populations after a disturbance*”.³⁵⁰

5.4.5 Characteristics of resilience

There are four determining factors for a resilient community:

1. Economic development
2. Social capital
3. Sufficient information and communication
4. Community competences

³⁴⁸ McMillan, D.W., & Chavis, D.M. (1986). Sense of community: A definition and theory. *Journal of Community Psychology*, 14(1), 6-23.

³⁴⁹ Norris et al., (2007). Community Resilience as a Metaphor, Theory, Set of Capacities, and Strategy for Disaster Readiness. In: *American Journal of Community Psychology*. 41, pp. 127-150.

³⁵⁰ Norris et al., 2007.

The first factor for a resilient community is the level of *economic development (1)*. According to Adger economic development includes aspects such as access to housing, health services, schools and employment.³⁵¹ As there are many interdependencies at the macroeconomic level, it is not only important to focus on the capacities of individual persons and business, but also on the capacities and possibilities of the entities that depend on them and on which they depend.³⁵² Empirical research by Norris et al. shows that the location of a disaster and the difference between the Western world and developing countries result in psychological distress rather than the type of disaster (natural disaster, man-made or technological).³⁵³ In developing countries the quality of housing is relatively poor, the access to employment is low, as are the capacities to redevelop the society. The poorest people live on locations that are vulnerable to floods and volcano eruptions, and may become more and more vulnerable. The inequality in economic development is not the only determining factor for the vulnerability for disasters, but determines mostly the capacities for mobilizing aid and support after disasters. Ideally, first aid is supposed to go to those who need it most, but in reality wealth and (political) influence matter. These rules do not only describe the direction of support within a society, but also between societies.

The basic idea of *social capital (2)*, the second characteristic of a resilient community, is ‘investment in social relations with expected returns’. It means that individuals within a community invest, access and use the resources embedded in social networks to gain returns.³⁵⁴ There is a lot of debate about the question of whether social capital is an individual, collective or multi-level asset.³⁵⁵ Because in this paragraph we zoom in on the community, a collective (and multi-level) construction, we accept the idea that social capital can be an individual characteristic, but we don’t use that approach here.

Social capital can be an important source of aid, especially in times of crises. Within the social capital, sources (such as family, friends, neighbours and other relatives) and types (material, emotional and informational) of support can be distinguished. A distinction can be made between received support/aid (someone who was cared for after he became homeless through a tsunami) and perceived support (the idea that you will be helped when a disaster hits you). Another aspect of social capital includes the new norms that emerge, which prescribe the behaviour of citizens in the period to, during and after a disaster. Riad et al. studied the willingness of people to evacuate before hurricanes Hugo and Andrew came on land.³⁵⁶ The social capital was a determining factor to leave or to stay. Residents with a stronger network, and so with stronger (not by definition more) support, were twice as likely to leave their houses behind. Furthermore, the perspective of rebuilding the community after a disaster is more present in communities with a high social cohesion. Putnam argues that

³⁵¹ Adger, W. Neil (2000). Social and ecological resilience: Are they related? In: *Progress in Human Geography*, 24(3), 347–364.

³⁵² Rose, Adam (2004). Defining and measuring economic resilience to disasters. In: *Disaster prevention and management*, 13(4), pp. 307-314.

³⁵³ Norris et al., 2007.

³⁵⁴ Lin, N. (2001). *Social capital: A theory of social structure and action*. New York: Cambridge University Press.

³⁵⁵ Wellman, B., & Frank, K. (2001). Network capital in a multilevel world: Getting support from personal communities. In N. Lin, K. Cook, & R. Burt (Eds.), *Social capital: Theory and research* (pp. 233–273). New York: Aldine de Gruyter.

³⁵⁶ Riad, J., Norris, F., & Ruback, R. B. (1999). Predicting evacuation in two major disasters: Risk perceptions, social influence, and access to resources. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 29, pp. 918–934.

‘social capital’ is about “features of social organization such as networks, norms and social trust that facilitate coordination and cooperation for mutual benefit.”³⁵⁷

Apart from economic development, social capital, sufficient information and communication (3) (described in the preparation phase), the community competences (4) are labelled as a factor for the possible resilience of a community.

Community competences are associated with collective action and collective decision-making and have to do with collective efficacy and empowerment. Cottrell describes a competent community in general as a community in which ‘the various component parts of the community (1) are able to collaborate effectively in identifying the problems and needs of the community; (2) can achieve a working consensus on goals and priorities; (3) can agree on ways and means to implement the agreed upon goals; and (4) can collaborate effectively in the required actions.’³⁵⁸ Some of these characteristics are essential for the development of social capital as well as sufficient information and communication. Accordingly, social capital and the level of information and communication are prerequisites for community competences. Brown and Kulig argued that the capacity for ‘meaningful, intentional actions’ determines the level of community resilience.³⁵⁹ These mutual actions within a society are not only necessary to bounce back after a disaster, but also to change their environments to mitigate the effects of a new disaster in the future.

Furthermore, Norris et al. argues that the strength and effectiveness of community responses are determined by different factors. Sufficient resources (economic, natural) are crucial to get access to the groups that can make a difference. It is also important that there is a culture that ‘permits challenges to authority’. Institutions for facilitating and coordinating responses are important too, as well the political access to the decision-making process for citizens who want to be engaged in.

2004, Tsunami Sri Lanka

“In Sri Lanka, the Danish Red Cross (DRC) ran a CBDRR programme in two districts. Communities in Ampara had been affected by the 2004 tsunami, while inland communities in Monaragala had not. The DRC found that it was easier to engage the communities which had been affected by the tsunami, as they had a greater awareness of the risks they faced. This illustrates the difference between working in pre-disaster and post-disaster situations and how it can have an impact on the level of motivation within a community.”³⁶⁰

³⁵⁷ Putnam, R. (1995). Bowling alone: America’s Declining Social Capital, in *Journal of Democracy*. Pp. 75-78.

³⁵⁸ Cottrell, L., Jr. (1976). The competent community. In B. Kaplan, R. Wilson, & A. Leighton (Eds.), *Further explorations in social psychiatry* (pp. 195–209). New York: Basic Books, Inc.

³⁵⁹ Brown, D., & Kulig, J. (1996/97). The concept of resiliency: Theoretical lessons from community research. *Health and Canadian Society*, 4, 29–52.

³⁶⁰ IFRC (2012). *Understanding community resilience and program factors that strengthen them. A comprehensive study of Red Cross Red Crescent Societies tsunami operation.*

Figure 25: Community resilience as a set of networked adaptive qualities.³⁶¹

The four factors described above (and schematised in the four circles in figure 25) influence the level in which a community facilitates its own resilience. An absence of those factors will have a constraining effect on resilience.

In addition to these factors, the International Red Cross identifies six characteristics of a safe and resilient community.³⁶² This description is based on the communities' own identification of what safe and resilient is, and furthermore, what factors can enlarge those properties. By monitoring the distinguished characteristics, it's possible to identify which communities are vulnerable in certain areas and certain situations and which approach (in the aspect of search and rescue) is eventually necessary to rebuild a community after a disaster. Some communities need support from official instances; others have the capacities to save themselves.

- 1) The idea that human health and knowledge is essential is central for a community to be safe and resilient. Possible ways to improve these characteristics include; first aid training, learning to undertake damage assessments or training communities to assess their own community preparedness. It is essential for communities to be aware of their own vulnerabilities, as well as possessing the knowledge to protect or renovate the community. The distinction between traditional (local) and contemporary knowledge can and should be made. The health of citizens is an important factor too; in communities with a low level of hygiene and sanitary facilities there are too many weaknesses, making it difficult to rely on the resilience of the society. Furthermore, self-confidence and the possibility of a community can be influenced by low standards of human health.
- 2) To be resilient, it is important that society is well organised. By absence of community cohesion and internal community capacity, it seems to be impossible to recover from the impact of shocks and stresses, simply because too few people are able to bounce back. Furthermore, by a lack of a common understanding everybody will choose his or her own way and the *community response* will be weak.

³⁶¹ Norris et al., 2007, p. 136.

³⁶² IFRC (2012). *Understanding community resilience and program factors that strengthen them. A comprehensive study of Red Cross Red Crescent Societies tsunami operation.*

- 3) If a disaster affects a community, it is important that a community has the capacity to mobilise and request advice and support from several actors in society. This underpins the importance of external relationships to provide assistance, as well as the ability of the community to mobilise themselves to access it. If the local or national political system does not include citizens in decision-making and does not give them the opportunity to mitigate the effects of disasters in the future, their resilient capacities will decrease.
- 4) To respond directly after a disaster occurs, a community needs the infrastructure and services that are necessary to respond. Roads can assist in delivering aid services, but information and communication technology, including emerging social media, is essential in connecting people with one another. As infrastructure failures are clearly a primary cause of disruptions in disasters, strategies for improving the disaster resilience of communities must focus on improving infrastructure resilience.³⁶³
- 5) Building a resilient community is expensive. Though the aid is based on improvisation and emergency plans are not necessary, technologies are needed to empower a community. Moreover, sufficient employment within a society that guarantees jobs to citizens is essential to maintain an active community. When citizens have perspectives for a job, their motivation to invest in resilience is even stronger.
- 6) A safe and resilient community can manage its natural assets. Within a society with rich natural sources, the members feel the necessity to protect their land for having a prosperous future. In a community in Indonesia, where members were asked about the most important characteristics of a resilient community, members stated that ‘planting trees is more important than evacuation’. Communities that lack natural assets often neglect preparation for disasters, and, should such a disaster occur, the result is that the community will have to be entirely rebuilt.

Although these findings from the International Red Cross are focused on non-Western communities, the distinguished characteristics can be considered in relation to Western societies. However, the degree to which those factors are present in different countries will differ.

5.4.6 Why the need for resilience?

Why then is it necessary to adequately organize local communities? What is their contribution to the preparation of a disaster and the process of rebuilding? The Worldbank underpins the building of communities by three reasons:³⁶⁴

1. Most people saved from major disasters are rescued by relatives and neighbours within the first 24 hours, before professional responders have the opportunities to arrive. After the 1995 Kobe earthquake, 80 percent of all rescued people were saved by their neighbours and other relatives. So, while local and national authorities are responsible for civil protection in hazard events, members of the affected community are always the first responders and should be empowered in that role. Or, as Wenger et al. describe: “Disaster literature is replete with findings indicating that initial search

³⁶³ American Lifelines Alliance (2006). Power Systems, Water, Transportation and Communications Lifelines Interdependencies. March. Available online at http://www.cimap.vt.edu/2DOC/ALA_Lifeline_Report_Final_Draft_030606.pdf.

³⁶⁴ Worldbank. *Community based Disaster Risk Management*. Knowledge-note 2-1.

- and rescue activity, casualty care, and restoration of services are accomplished by the victims themselves...”³⁶⁵
2. Strong and effective community-based disaster risk management (DRM) requires initiatives out of the community and linkages to the day-to-day life of the community. Linking disaster risk awareness and preparedness activities to local cultural events can be extremely effective in maintaining a culture of preparedness.
 3. In addition to the support described above, building effective and sustainable capacity for community-based disaster risk management (DRM) requires the formal recognition and support of local and national authorities. In addition to providing financial and technical assistance, local and national governments should develop legislation on and institutionalize the role of community-based organisations (CBO’s).

The reasons mentioned above, are based on experiences during disasters in Japan (especially during earthquakes like Kobe in 1995 and the tsunami in 2011). Also in the United States there is a visible call for creating community dynamics through the local and national government. For example, Flynn suggested that instead of treating ‘citizens as helpless targets and potential victims’ in their efforts to prepare citizens for disasters in general and especially terrorist attacks, Washington should ‘arm Americans with greater confidence in their ability to prepare for and recover from terrorist strikes and disasters of all types.’³⁶⁶ A key example of community dynamics can be seen when considering the resilience of Londoner’s following the 2005 London attacks; ‘That objective (crippling the city’s public transportation system) was foiled when resolute commuters showed up to board the trains the next morning.’

Today’s challenges require the broad engagement of civil society and therefore of local communities. In particular, crises caused by nature or human made activities can be managed by resilient citizens: well informed and capable to respond and renovate society. A study in August 2006, sponsored by the US Department of Homeland Security, found that nine out of ten Americans believed that being prepared for emergencies was important. However, a poll in the same month by Time Magazine found that only 16 percent of the Americans thought that they were “very well prepared” for an emergency.³⁶⁷

5.4.7 Societal resilience and typical crisis situations

Knowledge about what types of crises can affect a community and what the possible impact of a disaster will be is the starting point of a resilient community. Partners have found that communities will have to identify the risks they face and plan their actions accordingly. Societal dynamics such as the mobilisation of social support and, afterwards, the deterioration of social support will more or less occur in every crisis situation. Those processes are the general reactions in the response phase after a crisis, regardless of the types of crisis.

The different typical crisis situations, described in Chapter 2 of this report, ask for different reactions in affected communities. On the one hand is resilience in some cases more important than in others. The magnitude of the disaster and the level of dislocation determine the necessity of resilience. On the other hand have communities more the ability to prepare

³⁶⁵ Wenger, D.E., T.F. James & C.E. Faupel (1985). *Disaster Belief and Emergency Planning*. New York; Irvington.

³⁶⁶ Flynn, S.E. (2008). America the Resilient. Defying Terrorism and Mitigating Natural Disasters. In: *Foreign Affairs*. 87(2).

³⁶⁷ Ibid.

themselves for the impact of natural disasters like earthquakes, floods and forest fires in comparison to man-made disasters as terroristic attacks and bombings.

Especially in the case of creeping crises, in which vulnerable conditions and pressures build up slowly, people within communities can prepare themselves by building houses on higher locations (long term) or evacuations (short term).³⁶⁸ Communities that are more often faced with a typical crisis situation, such as those experience by the earthquakes in Italy or floods in the northwest of Europe, acknowledge that there are certain measures they can take to mitigate the threat of further crises in the future. The use of social media, to improve the function of search and rescue teams, can help communities in their preparation phase and the developers of this social media applications have to pay attention to the typical characteristics of both the community and the threatening disaster.

5.5 CONCLUSION

The aim of this chapter has been to identify individual, organisational and societal dynamics in crisis situations. By doing so, partners have found some striking similarities across these different dynamics in crisis situations:

- 1) Citizens have a strong desire to help those who suffer. Individually, citizens are rarely passive and often exhibit pro-social behaviour during crisis situations. This behaviour is often reflected in both organisations and communities. Accordingly, when the COSMIC consortium turns its attention to new technologies, this conclusion is helpful as it illustrates the amount of work people are willing to do.
- 2) Individual, organisational and societal dynamics are largely dependent on the time it takes a crisis situation to develop and its destruction; not necessarily on the type of crisis (although, clearly, certain crisis types such as earthquakes often occur without a warning period and its dynamics will be similar to all so-called flash crises). For the remainder of the COSMIC project this conclusion provides valuable insights for the (possible) use of new technologies and/or applications, through which emergency services can complete their tasks more effectively.
- 3) The role of government in the immediate aftermath of a crisis situation is often limited. Emergency management agencies are either not present, and may be otherwise occupied with a limited number of citizens, or unable to mount an effective response. If the COSMIC consortium identifies new methods for citizens to deploy new technologies for their benefit, and for businesses and governments to tap into these benefits, this will be a valuable output for the project.

Due to varying context-dependent variables it has not been possible to link the individual, organisational and societal dynamics to the specific crisis types in a manner that benefits the COSMIC project and provides sufficient generalizable explanatory power. Nevertheless, this limitation is valuable in and of itself, since it shows that social dynamics in crisis situations are subject to a changing social and natural environment. This chapter should therefore provide a useful guide for the other tasks in the COSMIC project, as well as the creation of guidelines for emergency officials (Work package 6).

³⁶⁸ McConnell, A. (2003). Overview: Crisis management, influences, responses and evaluation. In: *Parliamentary Affairs*. 56(3), 393-409.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

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6 CONCLUSION

The purpose of this report has been to provide a preliminary understanding of the types of crises that European Member States are exposed to and how it impacts the security of citizens. The findings of this report provide a useful backdrop to being able to understand, in future work packages, what contribution social media is able to make to crisis management, as it is necessary for the consortium to understand how different types of crises present a threat to European Member States.

The present chapter will provide a summary of findings from each of the four analytical chapters in this report. Accordingly, it will proceed in four sub-sections: a summary of “typical” crises that present a threat to European Member States, a summary of the different groups in European Member States that are at risk of being affected by typical crises, an understanding of how crises typically affect the security of the citizen and lastly, a consideration of how different groups appear to organise themselves to respond to different types of crises and furthermore what impact these different types of crises have on the organisation of groups. The chapter will conclude by considering the implications of these results for the projects next steps.

6.1 MAPPING EUROPEAN CRISES

Chapter 2 involved a mapping exercise which sought to understand what types of crises affected the security of citizens in European Member States over the last 10 years (2003 to 2013). In order to map crises that European Member States had been exposed to partners made use of two crisis related databases: OFDA/CRED International Disaster Database (EM-DAT) and the Global Terrorism Database (GTD). Both of which are well respected in research relating to security, and provide a rich resource for this mapping exercise.

Findings from this mapping sub-task revealed that there are four types of crises that were “typical” to Europe, in that they occurred most often: flood, extreme temperature, storm and wildfire. During this mapping exercise, partners were also interested in understanding which types of crises were considered to have had a high physical impact and a high economic cost. In this sense, high physical impact was measured according to the number of people affected (over 2000 citizens affected). Crises with a high economic impact cost over \$150 million. Accordingly, partners identified six types of crises to have had a high physical and high societal impact: flood, extreme temperature, storm, wildfire, earthquake and man-made crises. These findings fed into subsequent chapters (3-5), where the six types of crises were used by partners to help focus their analysis.

6.2 GROUP IMPACTS

Chapter 3 involved partners identifying the various groups that were affected by the six different types of crises. As part of the chapter, partners sought to understand not only “who” was impacted by different types of crises, but “how” they were impacted. To do so, partners examined incident data (e.g., from EM-DAT), official reports, journal articles and news items relating to selected case studies of those typical high physical and high social impact crises

identified in Chapter 2. By doing so partners aimed to identify whether different types of crises had different types of impacts.³⁶⁹

In each of the six case studies that were assessed, similar findings were found with regard to the different sub-groups that were impacted. In all six case studies citizens, critical infrastructure and the government were affected in the immediate aftermath of the crisis. In addition, in five out of the six crises (Flood, extreme temperature, wildfire, earthquake and man-made disaster) there was evidence to suggest that different types of industry had also been affected. This was not found with regard to the case study used to assess storms. However, it is highly unlikely that the amount of damage suffered by Cyclone Xynthia did not result in some form of physical or social impact as was experienced by citizens and critical infrastructure.

When considering the micro-level of groups that were impacted, there were both similarities and differences across the different types of crises:

- *Citizens*: In all instances citizens were physically affected. However, in some case studies, citizens' were also psychologically affected (e.g., man-made crisis). There were also instances where citizens property was affected, thus further affected citizens (e.g., storm, earthquake and floods). There were also two instances where partners found evidence of the crisis affecting the sense of community within a society (man-made crisis and floods).
- *Critical infrastructure*: All of the case studies revealed that critical infrastructure had been affected. In some instances, transportation, the provision of power, water and agriculture were severely affected (e.g., flood, storm, wildfire). In other crisis, such as extreme temperatures, the extent of damage to critical infrastructure is limited to those that were placed under pressure to respond to the crisis (transportation, power and water). Findings from this analysis also revealed that in some situations, authorities (e.g., the fire service) are put under additional pressure to help respond to a crisis; for instance during a wildfire. Partners were also able to reveal that during one crisis, man-made, communication was also affected. Finally, partners found that in some situations (e.g., earthquake and man-made crises) there was also the possibility that schools may also be affected (e.g., closed due to lack of transport).
- *Business*: The majority of the case studies assessed in chapter three illustrate that many crises impact local business, ranging from destruction to premises to loss of earnings due to the unfolding circumstances. In addition, as a result of the destruction caused by a crisis (e.g., earthquake or flood) cultural heritage and tourism were also affected. Findings from chapter three, also show that in some instances, for instance, a flood, insurance companies are also affected by extensive pay outs.
- *Government*: Following a crisis, both local and national governments are affected by unfolding events. This may be in the form of having to provide financial aid to those affected, as seen with the case study on storms and wildfires. In addition, some crises can be affected politically, as seen with the perceived inadequate handling of the

³⁶⁹ It is worth noting that the findings of this chapter were somewhat limited by the availability of crisis related information, for instance, in an official report of the 2007 UK floods, the psychological impact of the floods was referred to, but not quantified, thus making it difficult to truly understand the extent of the impact.

wildfires in Greece in 2007. In addition to the nation's government being affected, some crises, such as the 2007 Greece wildfires may result in a nation requiring assistance from neighbouring countries, for example, through the European Union Monitoring and Information Centre (MIC).

As highlighted in the conclusion of chapter three, the analysis conducted in this chapter revealed that, when one group is affected this can cause another group to also be affected (e.g., the impact of damage to critical infrastructure can impact citizens and the functioning of industry). It is therefore necessary to keep in mind that the extent of the impact on different groups is highly dependent on the scale of the crisis.

6.3 THE SECURITY OF THE CITIZEN

The purpose of chapter four was to identify how “typical” crises affect the security of the citizen and furthermore, how groups in society (e.g., policy makers, authorities, humanitarian organisations etc.) guarantee citizens' security.

Findings from this chapter illustrate that crises affect the security of the citizen in a multitude of ways, including: the physical and mental well-being, the destruction of communities and supporting critical infrastructure, the loss of personal property, the loss of life and historically, in extreme cases, the destruction of an entire community.

As part of the work involved in assessing how crises affect the security of the citizens, partners were interested in understanding how society is able to guarantee this security. Partners found that in order to mitigate the threat, crises require monitoring, prediction, preparation, intervention plans and dedicated organisations. Partners showed how these mitigation efforts are approached within European Member States at the national and EU level by assessing relevant legislative frameworks, as well as by examining the Community Mechanism for Civil Protection and the GMES Emergency Response Service.

In addition to assessing how the security of the citizen is guaranteed by the state, partners also demonstrated how security is guaranteed by international humanitarian organisations such as the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) and Civil Society (non-governmental) Organisations (CSOs), whose flexibility renders them very effective in many difficult occasions.

Organised societies protect citizens not only via material means but also via sets of principles, expressed as policy and legislation frameworks, to which new, emerging crisis management methods, such as those treated by COSMIC, must be compliant. To this end, the chapter examined regulations, guidelines and warning systems that are being introduced at European level to help build resilience within European communities to tackle future crises. Partners also highlighted the Commission's expressed intention of drafting guidelines in the form of good practice to adequately prepare for disasters, in line with the United Nations Hyogo Framework for Action, aimed at building the resilience of nations and communities to such phenomena.

Lastly, partners found that in Europe there is concern at policy level about the combined effects of climatic change, which are increasingly considered responsible for a multiplicity of crises such as heat waves, floods and storms. A recent example is the European Commission's

announcement in April 2013 of its strategy to strengthen Europe's preparedness towards different types of disasters, which is embedded in the framework of adaptation measures to tackle climate change.

6.4 SOCIETAL DYNAMICS

In contrast to the other chapters in this report, chapter five aimed to examine how individuals, organisations and society appears to organise themselves to respond to crises. By doing so, partners have been able to identify processes and reactions that are common in the immediate aftermath of a disaster, especially in the immediate aftermath of a crisis. Since societal dynamics are more dependent on context-dependent variables than on specific crisis types, partners were unable to conduct this analysis based on different types of crises, however, their analysis made use of the various types of crises as identified in Chapter 2.

The main findings relating to how individuals, organisation and society organise themselves to respond to different types of crises include:

- *Individuals*: Individual dynamics during crises are dependent on (citizen) preparation, (early) warning, and government interventions (or lack thereof) during the response and recovery phases of a crisis. The degree to which individuals are able to cope with these unexpected crises largely depends on the skills, knowledge and resources they have developed over time, as well as their experience to previous crises.
- *Organisations*: During the response phase of a crisis, extending and emerging organisations are active. Some examples of disasters in the West demonstrate that some extending organisations take on other roles than they would normally be responsible for, at the same time, other organisations emerge to become responsible for new tasks.
- *Society*: In the aftermath of a crisis two processes can be distinguished. In the first hours the 'mobilisation of social support' is visible, motivated by a form of altruism. When the proportion of victims to non-victims increases, the motivation of helpers decreases and the process of 'deterioration of support' begins. The affected society has to appeal to their own strengths and possibilities and are accordingly expanding their resilience. The main determining factors for community resilience include; economic development, social capital, sufficient information and communication and community competences.

The results of this chapter will enable partners to further understand the complexities involved in how different groups within society organise themselves to respond to a crisis, which in turn, will impact the different information and communication needs in different types of crises. It is important to realise that factors such as the economic situation and the absence or presence of social capital may determine how a society reacts after a disaster before planning how search and rescue teams approach an affected area.

6.5 MOVING FORWARD

The findings from this report are useful for understanding the various types of crises that European Member States have been exposed to in the last 10 years, including who was affected, how security is guaranteed and how individuals, organisations and society appear to

organise themselves to respond to different types of crises. Besides the findings about societal dynamics are useful in realising which reactions can be expected in an affected area, community or society.

The findings of this report are essential for other work efforts in work package 1 and will help support the development of a typology of crisis situations in Deliverable 1.4. In addition, the findings from this report will also support future efforts in Task 1.2, namely identifying typical search and rescue operations, as well as enabling partners to further focus their efforts on the six identified types of crises.